

List of most relevant weeds and associated problems, the most common used herbicides, and current weed management practices

All the partners of the AGROSUS project

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report is aimed to **list the most relevant weeds and associated problems, the most common used herbicides and current weed management practices** in the eleven biogeographical regions of Europe (Alpine – Anatolian – Arctic – Atlantic – Black-Sea – Boreal – Continental – Macaronesian – Mediterranean – Pannonian – Steppic). The weeds, herbicides and agroecological strategies here listed have been collected from all AGROSUS partners from a deep literature search but considering also the farmers' questionnaires, the in-person interviews and co-creation workshops with stakeholders, and their own experience in the field for each of the economically relevant crops included in the project.

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List of Contents

Important weeds in European key crops in the eleven biogeographical regions of Europe	5
Herbicides in Use: Current Status and Perspectives in the Different Biogeographic Regions of Europe	90
Agroecological strategies as realistic alternatives for sustainable weed management in key European crops. A review	120

Important weeds in European key crops in the eleven biogeographical regions of Europe

Abstract

In crop production, weed management is one of the more expensive and time-consuming tasks. The European Union (EU) has promoted the use of agroecological (AE) weed management strategies since 2009, with the Directive 2009/128/EC, which aims to achieve the sustainable use of pesticides in all the EU. Agroecological strategies are based on prioritizing the use of non-chemical weed control methods for weed management and trying to achieve an equilibrium in ecosystems. One of the most important steps to establish an agroecological strategy is to identify the weeds present in the crop, as the basis for choosing the most adequate measures to manage weeds. In December 2019, the European Commission presented The European Green Deal, which main objective is a sustainable EU economy, and pretends that food systems would be fair, healthy and environmentally friendly. Considering these policies, it is a great challenge for farmers and agricultural technicians to establish sustainable weed control measures within an AE strategy. Knowing weed biology and ecology, farmers and technicians would be able to manage them with more appropriate tools and resources. The aim of this work, is to report the weeds present on the main crops cultivated in the European Union to help farmers, weed managers and other stakeholders identify the most problematic weeds in their fields, as the first step for establishing sustainable weed management strategies.

Introduction

Weeds compete with crops for water, nutrients and space, so they are an important threat for crop production (Kaur et al., 2018). In the current context of climate change, with high temperatures and scarcity of water, it is predictable that weeds would be more competitive than crops because they have great adaptability to adverse climatic conditions (Karkanis et al., 2018). Nevertheless, weeds are part of agricultural ecosystems (Bridges, 2017), and they play important roles, like hosting beneficial natural enemies (Altieri and Whitcomb, 1979; De Menezes and Soares, 2016) or noxious pests (Oliveira and Fontes, 2008; Saeed et al., 2015).

Weeds also contribute to biodiversity maintenance, they provide food and nest to many species (Marshall et al., 2003) and are fundamental for the survival of pollinators and natural enemies of pests (Yvoz et al., 2021). Agricultural practices and adopted weed control measures affect weed species presence, abundance and distribution (Marshall et al., 2003; Kati and Karamaouna 2023). It is very important to design a proper strategy for weed management (Monteiro and Santos, 2022) which can favour the weeds that are beneficial for the agricultural ecosystem and control the non-desired ones (Gaba et al., 2017; Yvoz et al., 2021). However, to plan such a weed management strategy, on one hand it is necessary to possess in-depth knowledge about weed species, their biology, ecology, and their function in the ecosystems, and on the other hand about the available weed control methods and their possible effects on weed distribution. (Bajwa et al., 2015; Gaba et al., 2017; Monteiro and Santos, 2022). In the European Union (EU) from 2009, with the entry into force of Directive 2009/128/EC of the European Parliament and of the European Council establishing a framework for Community action to achieve the sustainable use of pesticides, Integrated Pest Management of Pests, including weeds, is mandatory. Recently, with the Green Deal Policies (December 2019), the EU is trying to further reduce the use of the most contaminant pesticides, comprised herbicides, and as a consequence there will be fewer herbicides available to control weeds in the next years. One of the main objectives of the Green Deal is that the EU has to create a fair, healthy, and environmentally friendly food system for the EU, with the objective of developing a more sustainable food system based on the use of new technologies and sustainable practices, like precision agriculture, agroecological practices, or organic farming, which will contribute to the goal of reaching a circular economy.

The first step for designing any weed management strategy is to identify the weeds present in the field (Guerrero et al., 2012; Schirzadifar et al., 2020; Mohidem et al., 2021). In fact, previous research papers have been published summarising the most problematic weeds in some of the main European crops. Schroeder et al. (1993) conducted a survey weed among scientists to collect information about the main weeds in ten main crop systems of Europe, e.g., winter and spring cereals, maize and sorghum, potatoes, sunflower and soybean, colza (winter rapeseed), sugar beet, and temperate orchards and irrigated Mediterranean orchards, with the purpose of identify possible targets for biological control. Later, Weber and Gut (2004) also carried out a similar survey, asking weed scientists throughout Europe to determine

problematic weeds that were spreading in agroecosystems, reporting a total of 281 species from 26 European countries.

Although previous works have reported an important number and diversity of weeds present in European crops, this information has to be updated from the perspective of agroecological management, and this is the purpose of this review. The most problematic weeds present in the most important crops of the eleven biogeographical regions of Europe are listed in this review to help farmers, weed managers, technicians, and other stakeholders identify the weeds present in their fields. The review will serve as the starting point to establish adequate integrated and sustainable agroecosystem through agroecological weed management strategies.

Important weeds in arable crops

Arable crops are divided in summer and winter arable crops. In this review, we consider the crops listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Arable crops whose main weeds are reported in this review.

Summer arable crops	Winter arable crops
Maize	Wheat
Rice	Barley
Sunflower	Oat
Soybean	Triticale
Potato	Rapeseed

Summer arable crops

Maize

Maize (*Zea mays* L.) is one of the world's most important crops, both for its food and feed uses. If we focus on the production of dry grain, the global area cultivated with maize is

approximately 197 million ha (FAOSTAT, 2024). The main areas of maize production are located in America (USA, Central and South America), Asia (China, with temperate maize, and tropical maize in South and South-East Asia), part of Africa (sub-Saharan Africa), and Europe, and maize is the crop with the second largest production area after wheat. In 2020, global maize production amounted to about 1162.4 million Mg (Americas—50.1%, Asia—31.4%, Europe—10.7%, Africa—7.7%, and Oceania—0.1%) (Kubiak et al., 2022). Maize is a high-yielding crop, producing 5.8 Mg/ha (Erenstein et al., 2022). From 2018 to date, the main countries growing maize in the European Union (EU) are Hungary, Poland, Serbia, France and Romania, the latter being the main producer (Eurostat, 2024).

Weeds are a major problem in maize cultivation, especially in the initial growth stages of the plants, when maize grows slowly and weeds can easily develop and compete with maize (Idziak et al., 2022). The main weed species found in maize fields throughout the different Biogeographical areas of the European Union are listed in Table 2. Some studies indicate that weed interference causes 50% yield losses in maize fields (Williams et al., 2008), and these losses can range from 5% to even more than 80% depending on the growing conditions (Gharde et al., 2018). In the USA, the potential yield loss from weeds is 50%, representing a threat to the domestic market of \$26.7 billion in cost (Landau et al., 2021). In Europe, Poland is a major corn producer, with 6.7 million Mg per year according to the FAO (FAOSTAT, 2024), along with Ukraine, which exported more than 26 million Mg of maize in 2023 alone during the war (Trademap.org, 2024). Gołębiowska et al. (2015) analysed changes in weed populations in various periods between 1963 and 2013 in Poland, observing in the latter period an increase in the density of *Setaria pumila* (Poir.) Roem. & Schult., *Setaria viridis* L. P. Beauv., *Solanum nigrum* L., and *Aethusa cynapium* L., as well as the emergence of new expansive species, such as *Abutilon theophrasti* Medik. Regardless of the period, *Echinochloa crus-galli* (L.) P. Beauv., and *Chenopodium album* L. were the most dominant weeds. Idziak et al. (2022) performed a trial to evaluate the effect of mechanical control and herbicides applied in pre- and post-emergence on sweet corn weeds in Poland between 2017 and 2019. The weeds reported were mainly *C. album*, *Brassica napus* L., *Geranium pusillum* L., and *Fallopia convolvulus* (L.) A. Löve. Other weeds were not present every year. They found that weeds caused a 30% reduction in maize yield under favourable growing conditions for the crop, while

the reduction increased to 93% under unfavourable growing conditions. The most effective method for weed control was hand weeding, but it was very expensive and labour consuming.

In Serbia, one million ha is used to grow maize, and weeds can cause yield losses of 13% to 90% depending on the type and density of weeds (Nedeljković et al., 2021). Brankov et al. (2021) conducted a trial to determine the benefits of growing maize in a crop rotation with winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.), and observed that in the control fields, the main annual weeds found were *A. theophrasti*, *Amaranthus hybridus* L., *Amaranthus retroflexus* L., *C. album*, *Chenopodium hybridum* L., *Datura Stramonium* L., and *S. nigrum*, while the perennial weeds present were *Sorghum halepense* (L.) Pers., *Cynodon dactylon* (L.) Pers., *Cirsium arvense* (L.) Scop., and *Convolvulus arvensis* L..

In France, maize is the second most cultivated crop, with 3.2 million ha (10% of arable land), behind winter wheat. The cultivated area increased significantly from 455,000 ha in 1955 to almost 3.2 million ha in 2010 (Fried et al., 2019a). Surveys conducted in the 1970s and the 2000s showed that there were weed species whose presence was maintained over time, such as *C. album*, *E. crus-galli*, *Persicaria maculosa* Gray, *Persicaria lapathifolia* (L.) Delarbre, and *A. retroflexus*; other species such as *S. nigrum*, and *Mercurialis annua* L. increased their frequency, and some weeds that were not present in the 1970s are present today, e.g. the dicotyledonous weeds *Calystegia sepium* (L.) R.Br., *Sonchus asper* (L.) Hill, *Senecio vulgaris* L., or *D. stramonium*, and the grasses *Poa annua* L., *Setaria verticillata* (L.) P.Beauv., and *Lolium multiflorum* Lam. (Fried et al., 2019a). In 2016, the European Food Safety Authority officially reported the presence of annual teosintes, the closest wild relatives of maize (EFSA, 2016), as weeds in maize crops in France and Spain, being *Zea mays* subsp. *huehuetenangensis* (Iltis & Doebley) Doebley, *Zea mays* subsp. *parviglumis* Iltis & Doebley, and *Zea mexicana* (Schrad.) Kuntze the most problematic ones for maize crops (Le Corre et al., 2020).

In Hungary, corn had the largest sown area until 2022, but has since fallen back to 2nd place behind wheat. Approximately 36.34% of the 2.25 million ha of grain sowing area is dedicated to corn. This is something like 816,643 ha reported in 2022 (KSH, 2024). The three most important weed species in maize crops are *Ambrosia artemisiifolia* L., *E. crus-galli*, and *C. album*. It was observed a rapid expansion of several annual grass weeds such as *S. pumila*, *S. viridis*, *Panicum miliaceum* L., and *Digitaria sanguinalis* (L.) Scop., and a rapid spread of

invasive alien weed species such as *A. artemisiifolia*, *A. theophrasti*, *Asclepias syriaca* L., and *Cyperus esculentus* L. (Novák et al., 2012; Krähmer et al., 2020).

In Ukraine, 3.6 million ha is used to grow maize (Ministry of Agrarian Policy and Food of Ukraine, 2024), and losses from weeds can sometimes reach 80% (Rudska, 2021). A lot of research on corn crops in Ukraine's continental and steppe areas shows that the most troublesome weeds are: *C. arvensis* (one plant per 1 m² during the growing season lowers grain yield by 1c/ha), *Cenchrus americanus* (L.) Morrone, *A. retroflexus*, and *C. album* (each lowering grain yield by 0.50 to 0.60 c/ha) (Zadorozhny and Kolodiy, 2014). Some authors also note that weeding corn crops with such weeds as *C. arvensis* and *C. arvensis* can reduce the yield by 50–55%. And for weeds weighing more than 5 kg per 1 m², corn does not form generative organs at all (Matiukha et al., 2010).

In Belgium, *C. esculentus* is widespread in arable crops, including maize, where it is very difficult to control due to the presence of tubers in the fields (De Ryck et al., 2021).

Table 2. Main weed species in maize crops in different biogeographical areas of the European Union.

Maize			
Family	Main weed species	Biogeographical area	References
Apiaceae	<i>Aethusa cynapium</i>	CONT	Gołębiowska et al., 2015
Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus palmeri</i>	MED	Montull and Torra, 2023
	<i>Amaranthus hybridus</i>	CONT,	Brankov et al., 2021
	<i>Amaranthus retroflexus</i>	ALP, ATL, CONT, MED, PAN, STP	Lovelli et al., 2010; Meissle et al. 2010; Novák et al., 2012; Zadorozhny and Kolodiy, 2014; Fried et al., 2019a; Týr, 2019; Brankov et al., 2021
	<i>Chenopodium album</i>	ALP, ATL, CONT, STP, PAN, STP,	Ileana et al., 2007; Týr, 2019; Meissle et al. 2010; Novák et al., 2012; Zadorozhny and Kolodiy, 2014; Gołębiowska et al., 2015; Fried et al., 2019a; Krähmer et al., 2020; Brankov

et al., 2021; Zwalczamychwasty, 2023.

	<i>Chenopodium hybridum</i>	CONT,	Brankov et al., 2021
Apocynaceae	<i>Asclepias syriaca</i>	PAN	Novák et al., 2012; Krähmer et al., 2020
Asteraceae	<i>Ambrosia artemisiifolia</i>	PAN	Novák et al., 2012; Krähmer et al., 2020
	<i>Cirsium arvense</i>	ALP, CONT, STP, PAN	Matiukha et al., 2010; Meissle et al. 2010; Zalai et al., 2014; Zadorozhny and Kolodiy, 2014; Týr, 2019; Yankov and Drumeva, 2020; Brankov et al., 2021
	<i>Senecio vulgaris</i>	ATL, CONT,	Fried et al., 2019a
	<i>Sonchus asper</i>	ATL, CONT,	Fried et al., 2019a
	<i>Sonchus arvensis</i>	CONT, STP	Olshanskyi et al., 2021
	<i>Sonchus oleraceus</i>	ALP, CONT, MED	Dorado et al., 2009; Týr, 2019
	<i>Xanthium strumarium</i>	CONT, MED, PAN, STP	Dorado et al., 2009; Meissle et al. 2010
Brassicaceae	<i>Brassica napus</i>	CONT	Idziak et al., 2022
Convolvulaceae	<i>Calystegia sepium</i>	ATL, CONT,	Meissle et al. 2010; Fried et al., 2019a
	<i>Convolvulus arvensis</i>	CONT, MED STP, PAN	Matiukha et al., 2010; Meissle et al. 2010, Zalai et al., 2014; Brankov et al., 2021
Cyperaceae	<i>Cyperus</i> spp.	MED	Dorado et al., 2009
	<i>Cyperus esculentus</i>	ATL, PAN	Novák et al., 2012; Krähmer et al., 2020; De Ryck et al., 2021

Euphorbiaceae	<i>Mercurialis annua</i>	ATL, CONT,	Fried et al., 2019a
Geraniaceae	<i>Geranium pusillum</i>	CONT	Idziak et al., 2022
Malvaceae	<i>Abutilon theophrasti</i>	CONT, MED, PAN	Dorado et al., 2009; Meissle et al. 2010; Novák et al., 2012; Gołębiowska et al., 2015; Krähmer et al., 2020; Brankov et al., 2021
Poaceae	<i>Cenchrus americanus</i>	STP	Zadorozhny and Kolodiy, 2014
	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	CONT,	Brankov et al., 2021
	<i>Digitaria sanguinalis</i>	CONT, MED, PAN	Dorado et al., 2009; Meissle et al., 2010; Novák et al., 2012; Krähmer et al., 2020; Montull and Torra, 2023
	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	ALP, ATL, CONT, MED, PAN	Dorado et al., 2009; Meissle et al. 2010; Novák et al., 2012; Gołębiowska et al., 2015; Fried et al., 2019a; Týr, 2019; Krähmer et al., 2020; Montull and Torra, 2023; Zwalczych, 2023
	<i>Elymus repens</i>	CONT, STP	Meissle et al., 2010
	<i>Lolium multiflorum</i>	ATL, CONT,	Fried et al., 2019a
	<i>Panicum dichotomiflorum</i>	MED	Montull and Torra, 2023
	<i>Panicum miliaceum</i>	PAN	Novák et al., 2012; Krähmer et al., 2020;
	<i>Poa annua</i>	ATL, CONT,	Fried et al., 2019a
	<i>Setaria</i> spp.	MED, PAN	Meissle et al., 2010; Montull and Torra, 2023;
	<i>Setaria pumila</i>	CONT, PAN	Novák et al., 2012; Gołębiowska et al., 2015; Krähmer et al., 2020;
	<i>Setaria viridis</i>	CONT, PAN	Novák et al., 2013; Gołębiowska et al., 2015; Krähmer et al., 2020;

	<i>Setaria verticillata</i>	ATL, CONT,	Fried et al., 2019a
	<i>Sorghum halepense</i>	CONT, MED, PAN, STP	Dorado et al., 2009; Meissle et al. 2010; Brankov et al., 2021
	<i>Zea mays</i> subsp. <i>huehuetenangensis</i>	ATL, MED	Le Corre et al., 2020; EFSA, 2016;
	<i>Zea mays</i> subsp. <i>parviglumis</i>	ATL, MED	Le Corre et al., 2020; EFSA, 2016
	<i>Zea mexicana</i>	ATL, MED	Le Corre et al., 2020; EFSA, 2016
Polygonaceae	<i>Fallopia convolvulus</i>	ATL, CONT	Meissle et al., 2010; Idziak et al., 2022
	<i>Persicaria maculosa</i>	ATL, CONT,	Fried et al., 2019a
	<i>Persicaria lapathifolia</i>	ATL, CONT,	Fried et al., 2019a
	<i>Polygonum aviculare</i>	ATL, CONT	Meissle et al., 2010
Solanaceae	<i>Datura ferox</i>	MED	Dorado et al., 2009
	<i>Datura stramonium</i>	ATL, CONT, MED, PAN	Dorado et al., 2009; Meissle et al. 2010; Fried et al., 2019a; Brankov et al., 2021
	<i>Solanum nigrum</i>	ATL, CONT, MED	Dorado et al., 2009; Meissle et al. 2010; Gołębiowska et al., 2015; Fried et al., 2019a; Brankov et al., 2021

ALP= Alpine; ATL=Atlantic; CONT=Continental; MED=Mediterranean; PAN=Pannonian; STP= Steppic

Rice

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) is one of the world's most important crops, being the source of food for more than half of the world's population. More than 150 million hectares are dedicated to rice cultivation worldwide, producing more than 470 million Mg (Fahad et al., 2019). It is mainly produced in East, South and Southeast Asia, with China, India, Indonesia, and Vietnam (Chen

and Zhao, 2023). China is the main producer, while India is the country with the largest area dedicated to the cultivation of this crop, although outside Asia, countries such as Brazil are also important producers (Hussain et al., 2020b). In Europe, Italy is the leading rice producer, dedicating 234,000 ha of land to rice cultivation, accounting for 52% of the rice area in Europe (Orlando et al., 2020), while Spain is in second position with 105,000 ha dedicated to rice cultivation (Gómez de Barreda et al., 2021).

As the world's population continues to grow, the demand for rice is increasing, and production and yields are expected to increase by 7.2% and 11.8% by 2025 and 2026, respectively (Gadal et al., 2019). Therefore, the management of rice cultivation is very important in order to reduce yield losses.

Weeds are a major problem in rice cultivation and can cause yield losses of between 10% and 96% when not properly controlled. In India, for example, weeds were found to cause 12.5% of yield losses in rice crops (Fahad et al., 2019). Three types of weeds can be found in rice fields: (1) grass weeds, like *Echinochloa colonum* (L.) Link, *E. crus-galli*, *Echinochloa oryzicola* (Vasinger) Vasinger, *Echinochloa oryzoides* (Ard.) Fritsch, *C. americanus*, *Digitaria longiflora* (Retz.) Pers., *Dactyloctenium aegyptium* (L.) Willd., and *C. dactylon*, (2) sedges like *Cyperus Rotundus* L., *Cyperus iria* L., and *Cyperus difformis* L., and (3) broad-leaved weeds like *Eclipta prostrata* (L.) L., *Commelina benghalensis* L., *Sphenoclea zeylanica* Gaertn., *Ludwigia perennis* L., *Pontederia vaginalis* Burm.f., and *Ageratum conyzoides* L. (Fahad et al., 2019). In Europe, *Echinochloa* spp., *Leptochloa* spp., *Heteranthera* spp., *Bolboschoenus maritimus* (L.) Palla, *Schoenoplectiella mucronata* (L.) J.Jung & H.K.Choi, *Alisma plantago-aquatica* L., *C. esculentus*, *Oryza sativa* L. (*red rice*) and *C. difformis*, are the most important and problematic weeds (Ferrero and Nguyen, 2004; Scarabel et al., 2020; Gómez de Barreda et al., 2021).

Table 3. Main weed species in rice crops in different biogeographical areas of the European Union.

RICE			
Family	Main weed species	Biogeographical area	References
Alismataceae	<i>Alisma plantago-aquatica</i>	MED	Scarabel et al., 2020; Gómez de Barreda et al., 2021

Cyperaceae	<i>Cyperus difformis</i>	MED	Scarabel et al., 2020; Gómez de Barreda et al., 2021
	<i>Cyperus esculentus</i>	MED	Scarabel et al., 2020; Gómez de Barreda et al., 2021
	<i>Schoenoplectiella mucronata</i>	MED	Scarabel et al., 2020
Poaceae	<i>Echinochloa</i> spp.	MED	Scarabel et al., 2020;
	<i>Leptochloa</i> spp.	MED	Gómez de Barreda et al., 2021
	<i>Oryza sativa</i>	MED	Scarabel et al., 2020; Gómez de Barreda et al., 2021
Pontederiaceae	<i>Heteranthera</i> spp.	MED	Gómez de Barreda et al., 2021

MED=Mediterranean

Sunflower

Sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.) is a widespread crop worldwide in temperate subtropical and tropical climates, considered by farmers as a rustic, cheap and easy to manage crop (Debaeke et al., 2021). It is one of the most important crops in the world, mainly because of the many uses sunflower can have (Stoicesa et al., 2022), especially oil production, supplying 14% of the world's oil demand, which represents an annual production of more than 58 million Mg (Stefanic et al., 2023).

Sunflower cultivation has increased markedly over time, going from 10 million Mg for 9.6 million ha in 1975 to 52 MnT for 27 Mha in 2018 (Pilorgé, 2020). Two thirds of the world's sunflower production is concentrated in Europe, including Russia, Ukraine and Turkey. Other countries of relevance in worldwide sunflower production are Argentina, China, and the United States (Pilorgé, 2020). Globally, Russia is the largest producer, followed by Ukraine and Argentina. Within the European Union, the main sunflower producers are Bulgaria, Romania, France and Hungary, with a production of 2,140,590, 2,106,570, 1,798,380, and 1,286,200 Mg, respectively (FAOSTAT, 2024).

Sunflower is not a good species to compete against weeds due to low growth in the early periods and low planting density, which means that weeds can cause more than 58% yield losses (Stefanic et al., 2023). Weeds affecting sunflower crops vary from country to country. In USA sunflower fields, Mouillon et al. (2020) found *A. theophrasti*, *A. hybridus*, *C. album*, *C. sepium*, *Setaria faberi* R.A.W.Herrm., *Sinapis arvensis* L., *A. artemisiifolia*, and *Persicaria pensylvanica* (L.) M.Gómez between 2016 and 2017. The main weeds affecting sunflower in different biogeographical areas of the EU are listed in Table 3. In a study in Croatia, Štefanić et al. (2021) |found between 2016 and 2017 mainly *A. artemisiifolia*, *S. viridis*, *E. crus-galli*, *C. album* L., *Matricaria chamomilla* L., and *Plantago major* L., among others. In Ukraine, we can find *A. retroflexus*, *S. arvensis*, *Xanthium strumarium* L., *C. album* L., *S. viridis*, *C. arvense*, *Lactuca tatarica* C.A. Mey., and *Lappula squarrosa* Dumort (Hutianskyi et al., 2021), *C. arvensis*, *E. repens* L. (Antipova and Chorny, 2021). In Bulgaria, *Amaranthus* spp., *S. arvensis*, *C. album* L., *Setaria* spp., *E. crus-galli*, *S. halepense*, *C. arvense*, *C. arvensis* are the most common weed species (Tonev et al., 2020), whereas in Russia one can find *C. arvensis*, *Sonchus arvensis* L., *C. dactylon*, *Equisetum arvense* L., *C. album* L., *S. viridis*, *E. crus-galli*, *X. strumarium*, *A. retroflexus*, and *Capsella bursa-pastoris* Medik (Tonev et al., 2020). In Spain, González Torres et al. (2008) highlighted the invasive presence of *Orobanche* spp. in sunflower fields. In Hungary, the most important weeds in sunflower are the annual monocotyledon *E. crus-galli* and *D. sanguinalis*, *Setaria* spp; the dicotyledon *A. retroflexus*, *C. album*, *Polygonum* spp.; the invasive *A. artemisiifolia* and *A. theophrasti*, and the perennial monocotyledon *S. halepense*; dicotyledon *C. arvensis* and *C. arvense* (Hunyadi et al., 2000; Novák et al., 2012).

Table 4. Main weed species in sunflower crops in different Biogeographical areas of the European Union.

SUNFLOWER			
Family	Main weed species	Biogeographical area	References
Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus</i> spp.	CONT,	Tonev et al., 2020
	<i>Amaranthus retroflexus</i>	CONT, PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000; Novák et al., 2012; Hutianskyi et al., 2021;

	<i>Chenopodium album</i>	CONT, PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000; Novák et al., 2012; Tonev et al., 2020 Hutianskyi et al., 2021; Štefanić et al., 2021
Asteraceae	<i>Ambrosia artemisiifolia</i>	CONT, PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000; Novák et al., 2012; Kukorelli and Kerekes, 2020; Štefanić et al., 2021
	<i>Cirsium arvense</i>	CONT, STP, PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000; Novák et al., 2012; Novák et al., 2012; Tonev et al., 2020; Hutianskyi et al., 2021; Hutianskyi et al., 2022;
	<i>Lactuca tatarica</i>	CONT,	Hutianskyi et al., 2021
	<i>Matricaria chamomilla</i>	CONT	Štefanić et al., 2021
	<i>Sonchus arvensis</i>	CONT, STP	Tonev et al., 2020; Olshanskyi et al., 2021
	<i>Xanthium strumarium</i>	CONT,	Hutianskyi et al., 2021
	<i>Sinapis arvensis</i>	CONT,	Hutianskyi et al., 2021
Boraginaceae	<i>Lappula squarrosa</i>	CONT,	Hutianskyi et al., 2021
	<i>Convolvulus arvensis</i>	CONT, PAN, STP	Hunyadi et al., 2000; Novák et al., 2012; Antipova and Chornyy, 2021; Hrytsiuk et al., 2023;
Malvaceae	<i>Abutilon theophrasti</i>	PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000; Novák et al., 2012; Kukorelli and Kerekes, 2020
Plantaginaceae	<i>Plantago major</i>	CONT	Štefanić et al., 2021
Orobanchaceae	<i>Orobanche</i> spp.	MED	González Torres et al., 2008
	<i>Digitaria sanguinalis</i>	MED, PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000; Novák et al., 2012; Montull and Torra, 2023

	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	CONT, MED, PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000; Novák et al., 2012; Tonev et al., 2020; Štefanić et al., 2021; Montull and Torra, 2023
	<i>Elymus repens</i>	CONT, STP	Antipova and Chornyy, 2021, CABI, 2023
	<i>Panicum dichotomiflorum</i>	MED	Montull and Torra, 2023
	<i>Setaria</i> spp.	CONT, MED, PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000; Novák et al., 2012; Tonev et al., 2020; Montull and Torra, 2023;
	<i>Setaria viridis</i>	CONT	Hutianskyi et al., 2021; Štefanić et al., 2021
	<i>Sorghum halepense</i>	CONT, PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000; Novák et al., 2012; Tonev et al., 2020
Polygonaceae	<i>Polygonum</i> spp.	PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000; Novák et al., 2012

CONT=Continental; MED=Mediterranean; PAN= Pannonian; STP= Steppic

Soybean

Soybean (*Glycine max* (L.) Merr.) is a crop that is noted for its high protein and oil content, which makes it a product from which different derivatives such as oils, flours, fuels, etc. can be obtained (Voora et al., 2020). Its world production has doubled since 2000 thanks to the increase in arable land devoted to its cultivation and the increase in crop yields (Song et al., 2021). In addition to its nutritional importance, it is an important crop in the market, thanks to exports from countries where it is produced (Voora et al., 2020).

Brazil, the United States of America and Argentina are the world's leading soybean producers, followed by China and India, producing about 92% between the five countries (Karges et al., 2022). In Europe, Russia, Ukraine and Italy lead soybean production, with a production of 6,003,152.63, 3,443,800 and 943,400 Mg in 2022, respectively (FAOSTAT, 2022).

Soybean is a crop vulnerable to weed interference, as it is sown at wide spacing to allow branches to develop and allow it to fully expand in the later stages of growth, this late canopy growth makes it easier for weeds to develop (Song et al., 2020a). In North America, weeds cause annual losses of 25 billion dollars in maize and soybean fields (Ahmad et al., 2021), in India, they can lead to a 31.4% reduction in yields (Gharde et al., 2018), even reaching very high losses (84%) in tests carried out in Austria due to the presence of *A. artemisiifolia* (Hall et al., 2021).

Several weed species can be found in soybean fields, such as *Amaranthus tuberculatus* (Moq.) J.D.Sauer, *Erigeron canadensis* L., *Ambrosia trifida* L., *Ipomoea hederacea* Jacq., *X. strumarium*, *S. halepense*, and *Amaranthus* spp., although the type of weeds will depend on the location of the field (Shea et al., 2020). For example, in fields in the United States, one can observe *X. strumarium*, *S. faberi*, *Ipomoea purpurea* (L.) Roth, *A. theophrasti*, *A. tuberculatus* or *C. album*, among others (Landau et al., 2022). Stefanic et al (2022) compared weed infestations in Croatian soybean fields where the seeds were sown at various spacings, and found that the most common weeds were *A. retroflexus*, *A. artemisiifolia*, *C. album*, *D. stramonium*, *S. viridis*, and *S. halepense*. Predominant weeds in soybean fields in Hungary are mainly dicotyledons like *C. album*, *Portulaca oleracea* L. and the monocotyledon *E. crus-galli*, the invasive *artemisiifolia*, and the perennial *C. arvensis*. We would like to highlight to *Hibiscus trionum* L. from Asia, which are heat-demanding and drought-tolerant species (Hunyadi et al., 2000; Novák et al., 2012). In Table 4 are reported the main weeds that can be found in soybean crops of the EU, indicating in which Biogeographical area they are present.

Table 5. Main weed species in soybean crops in different Biogeographical areas of the European Union.

SOYBEAN			
Family	Main weed species	Biogeographical area	References
Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus palmeri</i>	MED	Montull and Torra, 2023
	<i>Amaranthus retroflexus</i>	CONT	Stefanic et al., 2022
	<i>Chenopodium album</i>	CONT, PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000; Novák et al., 2012; Stefanic et al., 2022;

Asteraceae	<i>Ambrosia artemisiifolia</i>	CONT, PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000; Novák et al., 2012; Hall et al., 2021; Stefanic et al., 2022
	<i>Cirsium arvense</i>	STP	Penescu et al., 2017
	<i>Sonchus arvensis</i>	STP	Penescu et al., 2017
	<i>Xanthium strumarium</i>	STP	Penescu et al., 2017
Convolvulaceae	<i>Convolvulus arvensis</i>	PAN, STP	Hunyadi et al., 2000; Novák et al., 2012; Penescu et al., 2017
Poaceae	<i>Digitaria sanguinalis</i>	MED	Montull and Torra, 2023
	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	PAN, MED	Hunyadi et al., 2000; Novák et al., 2012; Montull and Torra, 2023
	<i>Panicum dichotomiflorum</i>	MED	Montull and Torra, 2023
	<i>Setaria</i> spp.	MED	Montull and Torra, 2023
	<i>Setaria viridis</i>	CONT	Stefanic et al., 2022
	<i>Sorghum halepense</i>	CONT, STP	Penescu et al., 2017; Stefanic et al., 2022
Portulacaceae	<i>Portulaca oleracea</i>	PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000; Novák et al., 2012
Solanaceae	<i>Datura stramonium</i>	CONT	Stefanic et al., 2022
	<i>Solanum nigrum</i>	STP	Penescu et al., 2017

CONT= Continental; MED=Mediterranean; PAN= Pannonian; STP= Steppic

Potato

Potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) is a crop with long cultivation history and of great importance due to its adaptability, yield capacity, and nutritional value (Devaux et al., 2021). Potato is one of the most important vegetable crops worldwide, being cultivated in 79% of the countries, with a world production of 400 million Mg grown on a total area of 19.25 million hectares

(Abdallah et al., 2021). According to FAO (FAOSTAT, 2024), China, India, Ukraine, Russia and the USA are the top 5 potato producers worldwide in 2022.

Its production in Europe has decreased over time, being one of the main producers after the expansion of cultivation in Europe following the discovery of America, until today, where production is not so high due to the decrease in demand for fresh potatoes in recent decades (Goffart et al., 2022). Despite this, north-western European countries such as Belgium, France, Germany, the Netherlands, UK and Denmark, have increased or maintained their potato cropped area and production over the last decade (Goffart et al., 2022). The three biggest potato producers in 2022 were Germany, France and the Netherlands, with a production of 10.683.400, 8.067.380, 6.915.900 Mg, respectively (FAOSTAT, 2024).

In potato, weeds are particularly harmful at the beginning of the growing season (primary weed infestation) and at the end of this period (secondary weed infestation) (Barbaś and Sawicka, 2020). In the early periods, while the crop is not yet established, weeds can achieve significant reductions in crop yields of up to 70-80%, by not only competing with the crop for nutrients or light, but also by reducing soil fertility, or by being hosts for insects, nematodes or potato diseases (Abdallah et al., 2023; El-Ganainy et al., 2022; Yadav et al., 2021).

Weed communities associated with potato vary according to location, e.g. in India you can find broad-leaves like *Hydrocotyle javanica* Thunb., *P. major*, *Oxalis corniculata* L., *Senecio densiflorus* Wall, *Oxalis griffithii* Edgew. & Hook.f., *Persicaria nepalensis* (Meisn.) Miyabe, or *Solanum aculeatissimum* Jacq., and narrow-leaves like *Spergula arvensis* L., *Cyperus cyperoides* (L.) Kuntze, *Arundinella nepalensis* Trin., *Arundinella khasiana* Nees ex Steud., *Digitaria ciliaris* (Retz.) Koeler, *Imperata cylindrica* (L.) Raeusch., *Commelina diffusa* Burm.f., *Arthraxon* spp. *Urochloa reptans* (L.) Stapf, *Capillipedium assimile* (Steud.) A.Camus, *Paspalum orbiculare* G.Forst., *Cyperus* spp., and others (Yadav et al., 2021). In Egypt, El-Ganainy et al. (2022) found *C. album*, *Sisymbrium irio* L., *Coronopus* spp., *Cichorium pumilum* Jacq., *Malva parviflora* L., and *S. oleraceus* as broad-leaves weeds, while *Avena fatua* L. and *Lolium* spp. were the prevalent grass weeds.

In Poland, Barbaś and Sawicka (2020) found *E. crus-galli*, *C. album*, *Stellaria media* (L.) Vill., *Anchusa arvensis* (L.) M.Bieb., and *Viola arvensis* Murray as predominant weeds, meanwhile Pszczółkowski et al. (2020) found monocotyledonous *E. crus-galli*, *C. americanus*, *S. viridis*, and

only occasionally, *A. fatua* and *P. annua*, and dicotyledonous *Anthemis arvensis* L. and *F. convolvulus*, and less abundantly *V. arvensis*, *Veronica hederifolia* L., *C. arvense*, and *S. media*. The most common weeds are in potato fields in Hungary the dicotyledon *A. retroflexus*, *D. stramonium*, *S. nigrum*, *A. artemisiifolia*, *C. album* and the monocotyledon *E. crus-galli*, *D. sanguinalis*. The perennials *C. arvensis* beside *C. arvense* occur patchily (Novák et al., 2012; Hunyadi et al. 2000). Järvan et al. (2013) in organic farms in Estonia *C. arvense*, *S. arvensis*, *C. album* and *T. arvense*. In Table 5 are listed the main weeds that can be present in potato crops of the EU, indicating in which Biogeographical area they are more commonly found.

Table 6. Main weed species in potato crops in different Biogeographical areas of the European Union.

POTATO			
Family	Main weed species	Biogeographical area	References
Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus retroflexus</i>	PAN	Hunyadi et al. 2000; Novák et al., 2012
	<i>Chenopodium album</i>	ATL, BOR, CONT, PAN	Hunyadi et al. 2000; Novák et al., 2012; Järvan et al., 2013; Barbaś and Sawicka, 2020; Schmidt et al., 2019; Zwalczych, 2023
Asteraceae	<i>Ambrosia artemisiifolia</i>	PAN	Hunyadi et al. 2000; Novák et al., 2012
	<i>Anthemis arvensis</i>	CONT	Pszczółkowski et al., 2020
	<i>Cirsium arvense</i>	BOR, CONT, PAN	Hunyadi et al. 2000; Novák et al., 2012; Järvan et al., 2013; Pszczółkowski et al., 2020

	<i>Matricaria</i> spp	ATL	Schmidt et al., 2019
	<i>Matricaria discoidea</i>	ARC	IINH, 2023
	<i>Senecio vulgaris</i>	ARC	IINH, 2023
	<i>Sonchus arvensis</i>	BOR	Järvan et al., 2013
	<i>Capsella bursa-pastoris</i>	ARC	IINH, 2023
Boraginaceae	<i>Anchusa arvensis</i>	CONT	Barbaś and Sawicka, 2020
Brassicaceae	<i>Thlaspi arvense</i>	ATL, BOR	Järvan et al., 2013; Schmidt et al., 2019
Caryophyllaceae	<i>Stellaria media</i>	ARC, CONT	Barbaś and Sawicka, 2020; Pszczółkowski et al., 2020; IINH, 2023
Convolvulaceae	<i>Convolvulus arvensis</i>	PAN	Hunyadi et al. 2000; Novák et al., 2012
Equisetaceae	<i>Equisetum arvense</i>	BOR	BalticAgro Blogi, 2019
Plantaginaceae	<i>Veronica</i> spp	ATL	Schmidt et al., 2019
	<i>Veronica hederifolia</i>	ATL, CONT	Pszczółkowski et al., 2020; Schmidt et al., 2019
Poaceae	<i>Avena fatua</i>	CONT	Pszczółkowski et al., 2020
	<i>Cenchrus americanus</i>	CONT	Pszczółkowski et al., 2020
	<i>Digitaria sanguinalis</i>	MED, PAN	Hunyadi et al. 2000; Novák et al., 2012; Dezsó et al., 2023; Montull and Torra, 2023
	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	CONT, MED, PAN	Hunyadi et al. 2000; Novák et al., 2012; Barbaś and Sawicka,

			2020; Pszczółkowski et al., 2020; Montull and Torra, 2023; Zwalczych, 2023
	<i>Elymus repens</i>	ARC	IINH, 2023
	<i>Panicum dichotomiflorum</i>	MED	Montull and Torra, 2023
	<i>Poa annua</i>	ATL, CONT	Pszczółkowski et al., 2020, Schmidt et al., 2019
	<i>Poa pratensis</i>	ARC, CONT	IINH, 2023
	<i>Setaria</i> spp.	MED	Montull and Torra, 2023
	<i>Setaria viridis</i>	CONT	Pszczółkowski et al., 2020
Polygonaceae	<i>Fallopia convolvulus</i>	ATL, CONT	Pszczółkowski et al., 2020; Schmidt et al., 2019
	<i>Polygonum aviculare</i>	ARC, PAN	Dezsó et al., 2023; IINH, 2023
	<i>Rumex longifolius</i>	ARC	IINH, 2023
Rosaceae	<i>Aphanes arvensis</i>	ATL	Schmidt et al., 2019
Rubiaceae	<i>Galium aparine</i>	ATL	Schmidt et al., 2019
Solanaceae	<i>Datura stramonium</i>	PAN	Hunyadi et al. 2000; Novák et al., 2012; Dezsó et al., 2023
	<i>Solanum nigrum</i>	PAN	Hunyadi et al. 2000; Novák et al., 2012
Violaceae	<i>Viola arvensis</i>	ATL, CONT	Barbaś and Sawicka, 2020; Pszczółkowski et

ATL= Atlantic; ARC=Arctic; BOR=Boreal; CONT=Continental; MED=Mediterranean; PAN=Pannonian

Winter arable crops

Wheat

Wheat is the most sown and traded crop in the world with more than 216 million ha, more than half of the world's wheat production is used in human diets and the remainder is used to the animal feed and processing industry (Pequeno et al., 2021). Under the term wheat, we can include the species *T. aestivum* (bread wheat) or *Triticum turgidum* L. spp. *durum* Desf. (durum wheat). The first is mainly used to obtain flour for bread production and have higher yield potential than the second, which is used to obtain semolina for the pasta industry and tends to grow in more stressful environments as it has a higher tolerance than the bread wheat (Giunta et al., 2019).

According to the FAO (FAOSTAT, 2024), the three largest wheat producers in 2022 were China, India and Russia, with 137,720,000, 107,742,070, and 104,233,944 produced Mg, respectively. In Europe, in addition to Russia, the largest wheat producers were France, Germany, Ukraine and Turkey, with 34,632,380, 22,587,300, 20,729,240, and 19,750,000 Mg produced in 2022 (FAOSTAT, 2024).

Weeds are the most important pest in wheat and can potentially reduce yields more than insect and diseases as they are generally more competitive for resources (water, light and nutrients) than wheat (Jabran et al., 2017). When weeds are left uncontrolled, yield losses range from 10-50% (Nakka et al., 2019), with an overall average of 24% according to Jabran et al. (2017). Adeux et al. (2019) assessed that grain yield loss ranged from very low percentages to as high as 56% depending on the weed community (the more diverse the community, the lower the yield loss). These yield losses result in significant economic losses, In Australia, the overall cost of weeds to Australian grain growers has been estimated at AUD 3.3 billion annually (Llewellyn et al., 2016).

Jiang et al. (2018) found *Vicia sativa* L., *Lapsanastrum apogonoides* (Maxim.) Pak & K.Bremer, and *E. canadensis* in winter wheat fields in China. Nakka et al. (2019) reported *Lolium* spp., *Alopecurus* spp., *Phalaris* spp., *Avena* spp., *Bromus* spp., *Raphanus raphanistrum* L., *C. album*, and *Bassia scoparia* (L.) A.J.Scott as the most common and economically weeds in wheat cropping systems in USA. Krähmer et al. (2020) analysed the results of interviews with farmers where the ranking of weeds in wheat fields in Denmark and France was observed. In Denmark, the 5 most important weeds in the years 2001 to 2004 were *P. annua*, *V. arvensis*, *S. media*, *C. bursa-pastoris*, and *Veronica arvensis* L., while in France between 2003 and 2006 *Galium aparine* L., *V. hederifolia*, *S. media*, *V. arvensis*, and *S. vulgaris* were most important. Also in France, Gaba et al. (2018) found *A. fatua*, *Alopecurus myosuroides* Huds., *Lolium* spp., *Festuca myuros* L., *Veronica persica* Poir., and *V. hederifolia*. Arslan (2018), observed *S. arvensis*, *Vicia lens* (L.) Coss. & Germ. , *C. arvensis*, *G. aparine*, *Vaccaria hispanica* (Mill.) Rauschert, *Lolium perenne* L., *L. multiflorum* and *Avena sterilis* L. among other weeds in wheat fields in Turkey. In Germany, Schumacher et al. (2018) found that the weed communities were dominated by *A. myosuroides*, *G. aparine*, *V. arvensis*, *F. convolvulus*, and *V. persica*. Hofmeijer et al. (2019) found among other *A. myosuroides*, *L. perenne*, *L. multiflorum*, *Poa trivialis* L., *V. persica*, *Myosotis* spp., *Trifolium repens* L., and *C. arvensis* in Swiss wheat fields. In Ukraine, spring weeds such as *A. artemisiifolia*, *A. retroflexus*, *C. album*, *E. crus-galli*, *C. americanus*, and *F. convolvulus*, as well as perennial weeds and root species such as *C. arvensis* and *S. arvensis*, were the predominant weeds in the agroecosystems observed by Shevchenko et al. (2023) and Hrytsiuk et al. (2020). Novák et al. (2012) and Kazinczi et al. (2023) found that the most common weeds are in wheat in Hungary are the dicotyledon *Tripleurospermum inodorum* (L.) Sch.Bip., *A. artemisiifolia*, *G. aparine*, *Delphinium consolida* L. and the perannial *C. arvense*, *C. arvensis* and the monocotyledon *Apera spica-venti* (L.) P.Beauv. and *L. multiflorum*. In Estonia, the most common weeds are *T. inodorum*, *V. persica* Poiret and *Elymus repens* (Madsen et al., 2023).

Table 7. Main weed species in wheat crops in different Biogeographical areas of the European Union.

WHEAT			
Family	Main weed species	Biogeographical area	References
Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus retroflexus</i>	STP	Shevchenko et al., 2023

	<i>Chenopodium album</i>	PAN, STP	Varga et al., 2017; Kazinczi et al., 2023; Shevchenko et al., 2023
Asteraceae	<i>Ambrosia artemisiifolia</i>	PAN, STP	Novák et al., 2012; Shevchenko et al., 2023; Kazinczi et al., 2023
	<i>Centaurea cyanus</i>	CONT	Stankiewicz-Kosyl et al., 2021
	<i>Cirsium arvense</i>	CONT, PAN, STP	Novák et al., 2012; Penesce et al., 2017; Varga et al., 2017; Hutianskyi et al., 2022; Kazinczi et al., 2023;
	<i>Helianthus annuus</i>	PAN	Kazinczi et al., 2023
	<i>Matricaria chamomilla</i>	STP	Penesce et al., 2017
	<i>Senecio vulgaris</i>	ATL, CONT	Krähmer et al., 2020
	<i>Sonchus arvensis</i>	CONT, STP	Olshanskyi et al., 2021
	<i>Tripleurospermum inodorum</i>	BOR, PAN	Novák et al., 2012; Varga et al., 2017, ; Madsen et al., 2023; Kazinczi et al., 2023
Brassicaceae	<i>Capsella bursa-pastoris</i>	CONT, PAN	Krähmer et al., 2020; Kazinczi et al., 2023
	<i>Descurainia sophia</i>	PAN	Kazinczi et al., 2023
	<i>Sinapis arvensis</i>	CONT	Hrytsiuk et al., 2020
Boraginaceae	<i>Myosotis</i> spp.	CONT	Hofmeijer et al., 2019
Caryophyllaceae	<i>Stellaria media</i>	ATL, CONT, PAN, STP	Penesce et al., 2017; Krähmer et al., 2020; Kazinczi et al., 2023

Convolvulaceae	<i>Convolvulus arvensis</i>	CONT, PAN, STP	Novák et al., 2012; Hofmeijer et al., 2019; Hrytsiuk et al., 2020; Kazinczi et al., 2023
Equicetaceae	<i>Equisetum arvense</i>	BOR	BalticAgro Blogi, 2019
Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium repens</i>	CONT	Hofmeijer et al., 2019
Lamiaceae	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	PAN	Kazinczi et al., 2023
Papaveraceae	<i>Papaver rhoeas</i>	CONT, PAN, STP	Penesce et al., 2017; Stankiewicz-Kosyl et al., 2020; Kazinczi et al., 2023
Plantaginaceae	<i>Veronica arvensis</i>	CONT	Krähmer et al., 2020
	<i>Veronica hederifolia</i>	ATL, CONT, PAN	Gaba et al., 2018; Krähmer et al., 2020; Kazinczi et al., 2023
	<i>Veronica persica</i>	ATL, BOR, CONT	Gaba et al., 2018; Schumacher et al., 2018; Hofmeijer et al., 2019; Madsen et al., 2023
Poaceae	<i>Alopecurus myosuroides</i>	ATL, CONT	Gaba et al., 2018; Schumacher et al., 2018; Hofmeijer et al., 2019; Wenda-Piesik et al., 2022
	<i>Apera spica-venti</i>	BOR, CONT, PAN	Novák et al., 2012; Synowiec et al., 2021; Kazinczi et al., 2023; Syngenta, 2024

	<i>Avena fatua</i>	ATL, BOR, CONT, STP	Penesce et al., 2017; Gaba et al., 2018; AFB, 2023
	<i>Bromus secalinus</i>	CONT	Zwalczamychwasty, 2023
	<i>Cenchrus americanus</i>	CONT	Hrytsiuk et al., 2020
	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	STP	Shevchenko et al., 2023
	<i>Elymus repens</i>	BOR, CONT, STP	Madsen et al., 2023; CABI, 2023
	<i>Festuca myuros</i>	ATL	Gaba et al., 2018
	<i>Lolium .sp.</i>	ATL, CONT	Gaba et al., 2018
	<i>Lolium multiflorum</i>	CONT, PAN	Novák et al., 2012; Hofmeijer et al., 2019; Kazinczi et al., 2023
	<i>Lolium perenne</i>	CONT	Hofmeijer et al., 2019
	<i>Poa annua</i>	CONT	Krähmer et al., 2020
	<i>Poa trivialis</i>	CONT	Hofmeijer et al., 2019
Polygonaceae	<i>Fallopia convolvulus</i>	CONT, STP, PAN	Schumacher et al., 2018; Kazinczi et al., 2023; Shevchenko et al., 2023
	<i>Polygonum aviculare</i>	PAN	Kazinczi et al., 2023
Ranunculaceae	<i>Consolida regalis</i>	PAN	Kazinczi et al., 2023
	<i>Delphinium consolida</i>	PAN	Novák et al., 2012; Kazinczi et al., 2023
Rubiaceae	<i>Galium aparine</i>	ATL, CONT, PAN, STP	Novák et al., 2012; Penesce et al., 2017; Varga et al., 2017; Schumacher et al., 2018; Krähmer et al.,

		2020; Kazinczi et al., 2023; Zwalczamychwasty, 2023
Violaceae	ATL, CONT, PAN	Schumacher et al., 2018; Krähmer et al., 2020; Kazinczi et al., 2023
	<i>Viola arvensis</i>	

ATL= Atlantic; BOR=Boreal; CONT=Continental; PAN=Pannonian; STP= Steppic

Barley

Barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.) is one of the most important cereal crops in the world. It is a species with a high tolerance to some stresses such as salinity or drought, which allows it to adapt and spread in different parts of the world. This crop has various uses, the main ones being animal and human food, and is the raw material for brewing beer (Geng et al., 2022). In addition to their carbohydrate, lipid and protein content, barley grains contain minerals, vitamins, flavonoids, tocopherols, phenolic acids, etc., which give them functional properties such as anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer and cholesterol-lowering properties, among others (Obadi et al., 2021).

Russia, Australia and France were the largest barley producers in 2022, with 23,393,510, 14,377,284.33 and 11,285,440 Mg, respectively (FAOSTAT, 2024). In Europe, other top barley-producing countries are Germany (11,207,100 Mg), Turkey (8,500,000 Mg), the UK (7,385,000 Mg) and Spain (7,029,720 Mg) (FAOSTAT, 2024).

Although barley is a crop that can compete with weeds, depending on species and density, yield losses due to weeds can vary between 20% and 50% (Negewo et al., 2006; Ngow et al., 2020). For example, Ayana et al. (2021), observed an increase in grain yield of up to almost three times when weeds such as *S. pumila*, *Snowdenia polystachya* (Fresen.) Pilg., *Polygonum* spp., and *C. album* were controlled. Also, there are barley varieties that are more competitive than others. Izquierdo et al. (2003) observed that *Lolium rigidum* Gaudin was able to decrease by 40-60% in two barley varieties more susceptible to weeds.

Some of the weeds that can be observed in barley fields include *Chenopodium murale* L., *Melilotus indicus* (L.) All., *Rumex obtusifolius* L., *C. album*, *S. arvensis*, *Erigeron trilobus* Boiss., *C. arvensis*, *Medicago polymorpha* L., *Euphorbia granulata* Forssk., *Polypogon monspeliensis* (L.) Desf., *C. dactylon*, and common *A. fatua*, as observed by Naeem et al. (2021) in Pakistani fields.

Krähmer et al. (2020) collected data from interviews in Denmark in which *V. arvensis*, *P. annua*, *S. media*, *F. convolvulus*, *C. bursa-pastoris*, and *C. album* were ranked as the most important weeds in barley fields. In Poland, Woźniak (2020) observed that the weed community varied according to the phenological stage of the barley and the type of rotation, with some weeds being found as *F. convolvulus*, *Papaver rhoeas* L., *G. aparine*, *A. spica-venti*, *T. inodorum*, *S. arvensis*, and *D. consolida*. Pala (2020a) found *S. arvensis*, *A. sterilis*, *A. fatua*, *Ranunculus arvensis* L., *P. rhoeas*, *C. arvensis*, and *V. lens* in barley fields in Turkey. Between 2015 and 2016, Alonso-Ayuso et al. (2018) found *Lamium amplexicaule* L., *Xanthium spinosum* L., *C. arvensis* L., *C. album*, *Setaria* spp., and *S. oleraceus* among others in Spanish barley fields. Also in Spain, Santín-Montanyá and Sombrero Sacristán (2019) observed *A. sterilis*, *Bromus diandrus* Roth, *G. aparine*, *Buglossoides arvensis* (L.) I.M.Johnst., *P. rhoeas*, *Polygonum aviculare* L., and *S. arvensis* in barley fields. In Hungary, the weed flora of winter barley is similar to that of winter wheat, almost the same. So, the most common weeds are in barley: *T. inodorum*., *G. aparine*, *D. consolida* and *A. fatua* (Novák et al., 2012). In the case of spring sowing, the weed flora changes. The dominant species are also *T. inodorum* and *G. aparine* but *F. convolvulus*, *S. arvensis*, *P. rhoeas* and *A. spica-venti* appear as well. In Finland, *C. album*, *V. arvensis* and *Galeopsis* spp. are most abundant weed species (Kauppi et al., 2021), while in Estonia *C. album*, *S. media* and *T. arvensis* are main weed species in barley fields (Järvan et al., 2013).

Table 8. Main weed species in barley crops in different Biogeographical areas of the European Union.

BARLEY			
Family	Main weed species	Biogeographical area	References
Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus retroflexus</i>	CONT, STP	Krähmer et al., 2020; Shevchenko et al., 2023

	<i>Chenopodium album</i>	BOR; MED, STP	Alonso-Ayuso et al., 2018; Järvan et al., 2013; Kauppi et al., 2021; Shevchenko et al., 2023
Asteraceae	<i>Ambrosia artemisiifolia</i>	STP	Shevchenko et al., 2023
	<i>Matricaria discoidea</i>	ARC	IINH, 2023
	<i>Senecio vulgaris</i>	ARC	IINH, 2023
	<i>Sonchus oleraceus</i>	MED	Alonso-Ayuso et al., 2018
	<i>Tripleurospermum inodorum</i>	CONT, PAN	Novák et al., 2012; Woźniak, 2020
	<i>Xanthium spinosum</i>	MED	Alonso-Ayuso et al., 2018
Brassicaceae	<i>Capsella bursa-pastoris</i>	ARC, CONT	Krähmer et al., 2020; IINH, 2023
	<i>Sinapis arvensis</i>	CONT, MED, PAN	Novák et al., 2012; Santín- Montanyá and Sombrero Sacristán, 2019; Woźniak, 2020
	<i>Thlaspi arvense</i>	BOR	Järvan et al., 2013
Boraginaceae	<i>Buglossoides arvensis</i>	MED	Santín-Montanyá and Sombrero Sacristán, 2019
Caryophyllaceae	<i>Stellaria media</i>	ARC, BOR, CONT	Järvan et al., 2013; Krähmer et al., 2020; IINH, 2023
Convolvulaceae	<i>Convolvulus arvensis</i>	MED	Alonso-Ayuso et al., 2018
Lamiaceae	<i>Lamium amplexicaule</i>	MED	Alonso-Ayuso et al., 2018
	<i>Galeopsis</i> spp.	BOR	Kauppi et al., 2021
	<i>Galeopsis tetrahit</i>	ALP	Zwalczych, 2023
Papaveraceae	<i>Papaver rhoas</i>	CONT; MED, PAN	Novák et al., 2012; Santín- Montanyá and Sombrero Sacristán, 2019; Woźniak, 2020

Poaceae	<i>Apera spica-venti</i>	CONT, PAN	Novák et al., 2012; Woźniak, 2020
	<i>Avena sterilis</i>	MED	Santín-Montanyá and Sombrero Sacristán, 2019
	<i>Avena fatua</i>	BOR, CONT, PAN	Novák et al., 2012; AFB, 2023; Zwalczych, 2023
	<i>Bromus diandrus</i>	MED	Santín-Montanyá and Sombrero Sacristán, 2019
	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	STP	Shevchenko et al., 2023
	<i>Elymus repens</i>	ARC	IINH, 2023
	<i>Lolium rigidum</i>	MED	Izquierdo et al., 2003
	<i>Poa annua</i>	CONT	Krähmer et al., 2020
	<i>Poa pratensis</i>	ARC	IINH, 2023
	<i>Setaria glauca</i>	STP	Shevchenko et al., 2023
	<i>Setaria spp.</i>	MED	Alonso-Ayuso et al., 2018
Polygonaceae	<i>Fallopia convolvulus</i>	CONT, PAN, STP	Krähmer et al., 2020, Novák et al., 2012; Woźniak, 2020; Shevchenko et al., 2023
	<i>Polygonum aviculare</i>	ARC, MED	Santín-Montanyá and Sombrero Sacristán, 2019, IINH, 2023
	<i>Rumex longifolius</i>	ARC	IINH, 2023
Ranunculaceae	<i>Delphinium consolida</i>	CONT, PAN	Novák et al., 2012; Woźniak, 2020
Rubiaceae	<i>Galium aparine</i>	CONT, MED, PAN	Novák et al., 2012; Santín-Montanyá and Sombrero Sacristán, 2019; Woźniak, 2020

Violaceae	<i>Viola arvensis</i>	BOR, CONT	Kauppi et al., 2021; Krähmer et al., 2020
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ARC=Arctic; ALP=Alpine; BOR=Boreal; CONT=Continental; MED= Mediterranean; PAN=Pannonian; STP= Steppic

Oat

Oat (*Avena sativa* L.) is considered a minor grain cereal and its production began to decline in the second half of the 20th century, but there is now increasing interest in the crop because of its nutritional properties for human food, animal feed, health care and cosmetics (Mäkinen et al., 2024). It is an important source of carbohydrates, dietary soluble fiber, balanced protein, lipids, minerals, vitamins, and different phenolic compounds such as a unique oats antioxidants called avenanthramides (Tang et al., 2023). Thanks to its nutritional composition, oat is a functional food with various health benefits (Paudel et al., 2021), especially in gluten-free diets for coeliacs (Smulders et al., 2018).

Canada was the major producer of oat in 2022, with a production of 5,226,465 Mg, followed by Russia with 4,529,953.68 Mg and Australia with 1,734,873.71 Mg (FAOSTAT, 2024). Besides Russia, in Europe the main oat producing countries were Poland with 1,500,840 Mg produced, Finland with 1,221,730 Mg, UK and Northern Ireland with 1,107,000 Mg and Spain with 867,850 Mg produced in 2022 (FAOSTAT, 2024).

Weeds in competition with crops for water, nutrients, and space can lead to substantial economic losses, for example, *A. fatua* and *Avena sterilis subsp. ludoviciana* (Durieu) Nyman are two species considered as weeds of the same genus as oats, which can cause yield losses of up to 70% (Bajwa et al., 2017; Li et al., 2018).

The weeds that can be observed in oat fields can be very diverse. Weisberger et al. (2019) found in USA oat fields between 2015 and 2016 *S. pumila*, *S. faberi*, *P. pensylvanicum*, *D. sanguinalis* and *C. album*. Nguyen and Liebman (2022) observed in a USA field under crop rotation for 4 years with maize, soybean, oat and red clover, *S. faberi*, *A. tuberculatus*, *C. album*, *D. sanguinalis*, *E. crus-galli*, *C. americanus*, and *Taraxacum officinale* Weber ex Wiggers. In Morocco, Boutagayout et al. (2023) found *S. oleraceus*, *A. retroflexus*, *Silene diversifolia* Oth., *Lysimachia arvensis* (L.) U.Manns & Anderb., *Plantago lagopus* L., *M. parviflora*, *Rumex*

crispus L., *Cichorium intybus* L. *P. aviculare* and *Glebionis coronaria* (L.) Cass. ex Spach in intercropping fields between 2018 and 2020.

In Poland, *C. album*, *Galinsoga parviflora* Cav., *T. inodorum*, *P. aviculare*, *S. media*, *E. crus-galli*, *S. pumila*, *A. spica-venti*, and *E. repens* among other species were observed by Andruszczak et al. (2010). Fradgley et al. (2017) found in UK fields *V. persica*, *A. myosuroides*, *P. annua*, *Agrostis stolonifera* L., *Agrostis gigantea* Roth, *E. repens*, *R. obtusifolius*, *R. crispus*, and *S. arvensis*. In Danish oat fields, Bitarafan and Andreasen (2020) observed *L. arvensis*, *C. bursa-pastoris*, *C. album*, *Geranium molle* L., *P. maculosa*, *P. aviculare*, *Silene noctiflora* L., *S. arvensis*, *V. persica* and *V. arvensis* Murray. In Estonia, in organic farming *C. arvense*, *C. album*, *T. arvense*, *Lamium purpureum* L. are very common (Järvan et al., 2013).

Table 9. Main weed species in oat crops in different Biogeographical areas of the European Union.

BARLEY			
Family	Main weed species	Biogeographical area	References
Amaranthaceae	<i>Chenopodium album</i>	BOR, CONT	Andruszczak et al., 2010; Bitarafan and Andreasen, 2020;
Asteraceae	<i>Cirsium arvense</i>	BOR	Järvan et al., 2013
	<i>Galinsoga parviflora</i>	CONT	Andruszczak et al., 2010
	<i>Sonchus arvensis</i>	CONT	Bitarafan and Andreasen, 2020
	<i>Tripleurospermum inodorum</i>	CONT	Andruszczak et al., 2010
Brassicaceae	<i>Capsella bursa-pastoris</i>	CONT	Bitarafan and Andreasen, 2020
	<i>Sinapis arvensis</i>	ATL	Fradgley et al., 2017
	<i>Thlaspi arvense</i>	BOR	Järvan et al., 2013
Caryophyllaceae	<i>Stellaria media</i>	CONT	Andruszczak et al., 2010
	<i>Silene noctiflora</i>	CONT	Bitarafan and Andreasen, 2020
Equisetaceae	<i>Equisetum arvense</i>	BOR	BalticAgro Blogi, 2019

Geraniaceae	<i>Geranium molle</i>	CONT	Bitarafan and Andreasen, 2020
Lamiaceae	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	BOR	Järvan et al., 2013
	<i>Galeopsis tetrahit</i>	ALP	Zwalczamychwasty, 2023
	<i>Veronica persica</i>	ATL, CONT	Bitarafan and Andreasen, 2020; Fradgley et al., 2017
Poaceae	<i>Agrostis gigantea</i>	ATL	Fradgley et al., 2017
	<i>Agrostis stolonifera</i>	ATL	Fradgley et al., 2017
	<i>Alopecurus myosuroides</i>	ATL	Fradgley et al., 2017
	<i>Apera spica-venti</i>	CONT	Andruszczak et al., 2010
	<i>Avena fatua</i>	CONT, BOR	AFB, 2023; Zwalczamychwasty, 2023
	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	CONT	Andruszczak et al., 2010
	<i>Elymus repens</i>	ATL, CONT	Andruszczak et al., 2010; Fradgley et al., 2017
	<i>Poa annua</i>	ATL	Fradgley et al., 2017
	<i>Setaria pumila</i>	CONT	Andruszczak et al., 2010
Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria maculosa</i>	CONT	Bitarafan and Andreasen, 2020
	<i>Polygonum aviculare</i>	CONT	Andruszczak et al., 2010; Bitarafan and Andreasen, 2020
	<i>Rumex crispus</i>	ATL	Fradgley et al., 2017
	<i>Rumex obtusifolius</i>	ATL	Fradgley et al., 2017
Primulaceae	<i>Lysimachia arvensis</i>	CONT	Bitarafan and Andreasen, 2020
Violaceae	<i>Viola arvensis</i>	CONT	Bitarafan and Andreasen, 2020

ALP=Alpine; ATL= Atlantic; BOR=Boreal; CONT=Continental

Triticale

Triticale (x *Triticosecale* Wittm. ex A. Camus) is a hybrid developed via crossing wheat (*Triticum* spp.) and rye (*Secale cereale* L.) that combines the hardiness and nutrient use efficiency of rye and the high grain yield and nutritional qualities of wheat (Jastrzębska et al., 2023). It is much more tolerant than wheat to saline and low pH soils, and less susceptible to rusts (Schillinger and Archer, 2020). Due to its high protein content and amino acid profile, the grain is mainly used in the food industry, although it can also be converted to chemicals, biomaterials, biocomponents, and biofuels and energy in biorefineries (Szempliński et al., 2021).

Triticale production has been increasing over the last 20 years, with more than 15 million Mg produced annually in more than 40 countries around the world (Wójcik-Gront and Studnicki, 2021). More than 90% of the world's triticale production is concentrated in Europe (Jastrzębska et al., 2023), with Poland being the main producer, followed by Germany, France, Belarus, and Spain with 5,440,270, 1,929,700, 1,613,730, 1,192,879.87, 634,890 Mg produced in 2022, respectively (FAOSTAT, 2024).

Weeds can cause yield losses in triticale in the range of 26 to 40 %, and much larger reductions can be achieved without proper weed control (Jastrzębska et al., 2023). Different weed species can be found in triticale fields. Between 2013 and 2016, Sawicka et al. (2020) found in Poland fields *A. arvensis*, *A. spica-venti*, *B. napus*, *Centaurea cyanus* L., *C. album*, *C. arvensis*, *Galeopsis ladanum* L., *G. aparine*, *E. arvensis*, *L. amplexicaule*, *P. lapathifolia*, *F. convolvulus*, *P. aviculare*, *S. media*, *T. officinale*, *Vicia cracca* L., *V. sativa*, *V. arvensis*, *Vicia pubescens* (DC.) Link, and *V. persica*. Feledyn-Szewczyk et al. (2020) found *V. arvensis* Murr., *S. media*, *C. bursa-pastoris*, *A. spica-venti*, and *P. rhoeas* in triticale fields in Poland between 2015 and 2017. In other Polish farms in the same period, Sobkowicz and Tendziagolska (2022) found *C. album*, *V. arvensis*, and *E. crus-galli*. In Hungary, the weed flora of triticale is similar to that of winter wheat, and winter barley. So, the most common weeds are in barley: *T. inodorum*, *G. aparine* beside these *A. fatua* has a bigger meaning (Hunyadi et al., 2000; Novák et al., 2012).

Table 10. Main weed species in triticale crops in the Alpine Biogeographical area of the European Union.

TRITICALE			
Family	Main weed species	Biogeographical area	References
Amaranthaceae	<i>Chenopodium album</i>	CONT	Sawicka et al., 2020; Sobkowicz and Tendziagolska, 2022
Asteraceae	<i>Anthemis arvensis</i>	CONT	Sawicka et al., 2020
	<i>Centaurea cyanus</i>	CONT	Sawicka et al., 2020
	<i>Cirsium arvense</i>	CONT	Sawicka et al., 2020
	<i>Tripleurospermum inodorum</i>	PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000; Novák et al., 2012
Brassicaceae	<i>Brassica napus</i>	CONT	Sawicka et al., 2020
	<i>Capsella bursa-pastoris</i>	CONT	Feledyn-Szewczyk et al., 2020
Caryophyllaceae	<i>Stellaria media</i>	CONT	Feledyn-Szewczyk et al., 2020; Sawicka et al., 2020
Equisetaceae	<i>Equisetum arvense</i>	CONT	Sawicka et al., 2020
Fabaceae	<i>Vicia cracca</i>	CONT	Sawicka et al., 2020
	<i>Vicia sativa</i>	CONT	Sawicka et al., 2020
	<i>Vicia pubescens</i>	CONT	Sawicka et al., 2020
Lamiaceae	<i>Lamium amplexicaule</i>	CONT	Sawicka et al., 2020
	<i>Galeopsis ladanum</i>	CONT	Sawicka et al., 2020
	<i>Galeopsis tetrahit</i>	ALP	Zwalczych, 2023
Papaveraceae	<i>Papaver rhoas</i>	CONT	Feledyn-Szewczyk et al., 2020
Plantaginaceae	<i>Veronica persica</i>	CONT	Sawicka et al., 2020
Poaceae	<i>Apera spica-venti</i>	CONT	Feledyn-Szewczyk et al., 2020; Sawicka et al., 2020
	<i>Avena fatua</i>	PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000; Novák et al., 2012

	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	CONT	Sobkowicz and Tendziagolska, 2022
Polygonaceae	<i>Fallopia convolvulus</i>	CONT	Sawicka et al., 2020
	<i>Persicaria lapathifolia</i>	CONT	Sawicka et al., 2020
	<i>Polygonum aviculare</i>	CONT	Sawicka et al., 2020
Rubiaceae	<i>Galium aparine</i>	CONT, PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000; Novák et al., 2012; Sawicka et al., 2020
Violaceae	<i>Viola arvensis</i>	CONT	Feledyn-Szewczyk et al., 2020; Sawicka et al., 2020; Sobkowicz and Tendziagolska, 2022

ALP=Alpine; CONT= Continental; PAN=Pannonian

Rapeseed

Rapeseed (*Brassica napus* L.) is a vegetable oil crop originated from the spontaneous hybridization 7500 years ago between turnip rape (*Brassica rapa* L.) and cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* L.) (Raboanatahiry et al., 2021). Rapeseed is one of the most economically important oilseeds crops grown worldwide, mainly for the production of vegetable oil, ranking as the second-highest yielding oil crop, accounting for just over 12% of world major vegetable oil in 2021 (Zheng and Liu, 2022). It can also be used to produce biofuels or high-protein meal used mainly for animal feed (Grădilă et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2022).

Canada, China, India, and Australia are the main rapeseed producers (Zheng et al., 2020), with a production in 2022 of 18,694,768, 15,531,400, 11,963,090, and 6,820,286.77 Mg, respectively (FAOSTAT, 2024). Europe is also a major rapeseed producer, with France, Russia, Germany, and Poland, being the main rapeseed producing countries, producing 4,516,540, 4,514,241.04, 4,294,900, and 3,487,070 Mg in 2022 (FAOSTAT, 2024).

Together with diseases and pests, weeds cause significant yield losses in oilseed rape, ranging from 20-30 % to more than 60 % when competition with weeds is very high (Hussain et al., 2020a). For example, in Canada, losses caused by weeds in rapeseed fields vary between 18%

and 35% depending on the area, resulting in economic losses of 2.21 billion Canadian dollars (Geddes et al., 2022).

A. fatua is the most economically important weed in Western Canada, whereas *Bromus tectorum* L., *S. viridis*, and *G. aparine*, also cause numerous losses (Cornelsen et al., 2023). In Australia, *L. rigidum*, *Crassula* spp. L., *Fumaria* spp. L., *Hyacinthoides non-scripta* (L.) Chouard ex Rothm., *Papaver* spp. L. and *Hordeum murinum* L. are some of the weeds that can be found in rapeseed fields (Mwendwa et al., 2020). Grădilă et al. (2020) found different weeds in 2 locations in Romania, at Dâlga the predominant weeds were *P. rhoeas*, *G. aparine*, *P. persicaria*, *C. arvense*, and *Sonchus* spp. meanwhile at Tămădău *V. arvensis* Murray., *G. aparine*, *Euphorbia cyparissias* L., *T. inodorum*, *C. arvense*, and *R. raphanistrum* were the predominant weed species. Gawęda and Haliniarz (2022), found *V. arvensis* Murr., *S. asper*, *S. arvensis*, *C. album*, *Euphorbia helioscopia* L., *A. retroflexus*, *C. arvense*, and *V. arvensis* in fields in Poland between 2013 and 2017. Predominant weeds found in Hungarian rapeseed fields include the dicotyledon *T. inodorum*, *Galium aparine*, *Sinapis arvensis*, *Papaver rhoeas*, and the monocotyledon *Apera spica-venti*.

Table 11. Main weed species in rapeseed crops in different Biogeographical areas of the European Union.

RAPASEED			
Family	Main weed species	Biogeographical area	References
Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus retroflexus</i>	CONT	Gawęda and Haliniarz, 2022
	<i>Chenopodium album</i>	CONT	Gawęda and Haliniarz, 2022
Asteraceae	<i>Centaurea cyanus</i>	CONT	Stankiewicz-Kosyl et al., 2021
	<i>Cirsium arvense</i>	CONT, STP	Grădilă et al., 2020; Gawęda and Haliniarz, 2022

	<i>Sonchus asper</i>	CONT	Gawęda and Haliniarz, 2022
	<i>Sonchus arvensis</i>	CONT	Gawęda and Haliniarz, 2022
	<i>Sonchus</i> spp.	STP	Grădilă et al., 2020
	<i>Tripleurospermum inodorum</i>	PAN, STP	Novák et. al, 2012; Grădilă et al., 2020
Brassicaceae	<i>Sinapis arvensis</i>	PAN	Novák et. al, 2012
	<i>Raphanus raphanistrum</i>	STP	Grădilă et al., 2020
Euphorbiaceae	<i>Euphorbia cyparissias</i>	STP	Grădilă et al., 2020
	<i>Euphorbia helioscopia</i>	CONT	Gawęda and Haliniarz, 2022
Papaveraceae	<i>Papaver rhoeas</i>	STP	Grădilă et al., 2020
Plantaginaceae	<i>Veronica arvensis</i>	CONT	Gawęda and Haliniarz, 2022
Poaceae	<i>Bromus secalinus</i>	CONT	Zwalczamychwasty, 2023
Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria maculosa</i>	SRP	Grădilă et al., 2020
Rubiaceae	<i>Galium aparine</i>	CONT, PAN, STP	; Novák et. al, 2012; Grădilă et al., 2020
Violaceae	<i>Viola arvensis</i>	STP	Grădilă et al., 2020; Gawęda and Haliniarz, 2022

CONT=Continental; PAN=Pannonian; STP=Steppic

Important weeds in horticultural crops

Cabbage

Cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* var. *capitata*) is a vegetable crop produced worldwide due to its wide adaptability, high nutrition, and unique flavour (Kong et al., 2021). Numerous epidemiological studies have affirmed that the consumption of cruciferous vegetables, like cabbage, is beneficial to health by reducing the risk of developing diseases such as cancer, Alzheimer's, etc., thanks to its rich nutritional value, mainly the presence of antioxidant phytochemicals such as vitamins C and E, carotenoids, and flavonoids (Moreb et al., 2020).

Asia is the world's leading cabbage producer, with China, India, and the Republic of Korea as the 3 largest producers worldwide, with a production in 2022 of 34,986,293.94, 9,825,000 and 2,428,893.92 Mg, respectively (FAOSTAT, 2024). Europe is also a major producer of cabbage worldwide, with Russia, Ukraine, Turkey, and Poland accounting for 2,298,209, 1,533,450, 964,296, and 687,500 Mg produced in 2022 (FAOSTAT, 2024). In Poland, for example, cabbage cultivation accounts for about 30% of the total production of ground vegetables (Moreb et al., 2020).

Weed management is essential to obtain not only a high crop yield, but also to improve the growing and developmental conditions of the cabbages, which ultimately affect their chemical composition. Weeds limit the crop's access to light, resulting in unshaped heads, and lower the soil temperature, leading to delayed ripening of the cabbages (Golian et al., 2023). Yield losses due to weeds can be as high as 40% to 80% (Atal et al., 2021).

Some of the weeds that can be observed in Chinese cabbage fields include *P. oleracea*, *Descurainia sophia* (L.) Webb ex Prantl, and *G. parviflora* (Zhao et al., 2022). In United States, Sharpe et al. (2021) found *R. raphanistrum*, *Oenothera laciniata* Hill, *C. rotundus*, *Lepidium didymum* L., *Geranium carolinianum* L., and *Lepidium virginicum* L. among the most troublesome weeds between 2016 and 2018, while Lounsbury et al. (2022) found *A. retroflexus*, *C. album*, *D. sanguinalis*, *E. canadensis*, and *P. oleracea*, among some other weed species. In some fields in the Netherlands, Juventia et al. (2021) found *Agrostemma githago* L., *Gypsophila* sp, *C. cyanus*, *Carthamus tinctorius* L., *Eleusine coracana* (L.) Gaertn., *Visnaga daucooides* Gaertn., *Gilia capitata* Sims, *Coreopsis grandiflora* Hogg ex Sweet 'Early Sunrise', *Cosmos bipinnatus* Cav., *Glebionis segetum* Fourr., *Papaver* spp., and *Phacelia tanacetifolia* Benth. In Hungary, Hunyadi et al. (2000) found that the weeds which ripen seed end of the summer are the most frequent in cabbage fields like *Chenopodium* spp., *Amaranthus* spp., *G. parviflora*, *M. annua*, the monocotyledon *E. crus-galli*, *D. sanguinalis* and *Setaria* spp..

Table 12. Main weed species in cabbage crops in different Biogeographical areas of the European Union.

CABBAGE			
Family	Main weed species	Biogeographical area	References
Apiaceae	<i>Visnaga daucoides</i>	ATL	Juventia et al., 2021
Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus</i> spp.	PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000
	<i>Amaranthus retroflexus</i>	PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000
	<i>Chenopodium album</i>	PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000
	<i>Chenopodium</i> spp.	PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000
Asteraceae	<i>Carthamus tinctorius</i>	ATL	Juventia et al., 2021
	<i>Centaurea cyanus</i>	ATL	Juventia et al., 2021
	<i>Coreopsis grandiflora</i>	ATL	Juventia et al., 2021
	<i>Cosmos bipinnatus</i>	ATL	Juventia et al., 2021
	<i>Galinsoga parviflora</i>	PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000
	<i>Glebionis segetum</i>	ATL	Juventia et al., 2021
	<i>Matricaria discoidea</i>	ARC	IINH, 2023
	<i>Senecio vulgaris</i>	ARC	IINH, 2023
Brassicaceae	<i>Capsella bursa-pastoris</i>	ARC	IINH, 2023
Boraginaceae	<i>Phacelia tanacetifolia</i>	ATL	Juventia et al., 2021
Caryophyllaceae	<i>Agrostemma githago</i>	ATL	Juventia et al., 2021
	<i>Gypsophila</i> sp.	ATL	Juventia et al., 2021
	<i>Stellaria media</i>	ARC	IINH, 2023
Euphorbiaceae	<i>Mercurialis annua</i>	PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000
Papaveraceae	<i>Papaver</i> spp	ATL	Juventia et al., 2021
Poaceae	<i>Digitaria sanguinalis</i>	PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000
	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000

	<i>Eleusine coracana</i>	ATL	Juventia et al., 2021
	<i>Elymus repens</i>	ARC	IINH, 2023
	<i>Poa pratensis</i>	ARC	IINH, 2023
	<i>Setaria</i> spp.	PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000
Polemoniaceae	<i>Gilia capitata</i>	ATL	Juventia et al., 2021
Polygonaceae	<i>Polygonum aviculare</i>	ARC	IINH, 2023
	<i>Rumex longifolius</i>	ARC	IINH, 2023

ARC=Arctic; ATL=Atlantic; PAN=Pannonian

Carrot

Carrot (*Daucus carota* L.) is one of the most cultivated vegetables in the world, ranking in the top 10 worldwide vegetable crops (Ahmad et al., 2019). Its importance is mainly due to its high nutritional value, providing the human diet with carotenoids, anthocyanins, phenolic compounds, and ascorbic acid, among other nutrients (Ahmad et al., 2019; Que et al., 2019).

China is the world's largest producer of carrots, with a total production in 2022 of 18,768,100.3 Mg, followed by Uzbekistan and the United States of America with 3,915,983.46 and 1,381,461 Mg, respectively (FAOSTAT, 2024). In Europe, Russia is the number one producer of carrots and turnips, with a production of 1,362,175.81 Mg in 2022, followed by the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland with 887,502 Mg, Turkey with 790,983 Mg, Germany with 780,490 Mg and Ukraine with 748,930 Mg (FAOSTAT, 2024).

Weed interference in carrots reduces overall root yield, reduces quality by stimulating misshapen root development, and makes mechanical harvesting more difficult (Colquhoun et al., 2018). When infestation is high, yield losses can range up to 60%, with losses of more than 90% in extreme cases (Kendra et al., 2019; Reginaldo et al., 2021). In Switzerland, for example, a high infestation of *C. esculentus* caused yield losses of 61% (Total et al., 2018).

Different types of weeds can be found in carrot fields. Carlesi et al. (2021) encountered *Fumaria officinalis* L., *S. oleraceus*, *P. lapathifolium*, *P. oleracea*, and *S. nigrum* in carrot fields in Italy. In Spain, Alfaro-Fernández et al. (2017) registered and classified the weeds present in carrot and celery crops encountering *Equisetum ramosissimum* Desf., *S. verticillata*, *A. retroflexus*, *Salsola vermiculata* L., *C. arvensis*, and *Urtica urens* L. among others. The dominant weed species in Hungarian carrot fields vary

based on the climate and cultivation techniques. They include *E. crus-galli*, *D. sanguinalis*, *Setaria* spp. (monocotyledon) and *Amaranthus* spp., *Chenopodium* spp., *Polygonum* spp., and the invasive *A. artemisiifolia* (dicotyledon) (Hunyadi et al., 2000).

Table 13. Main weed species in carrot crops in different Biogeographical areas of the European Union.

CARROT			
Family	Main weed species	Biogeographical area	References
Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus retroflexus</i>	MED, PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000; Alfaro-Fernández et al., 2017
	<i>Chenopodium album</i>	PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000
	<i>Salsola vermiculata</i>	MED	Alfaro-Fernández et al., 2017
Asteraceae	<i>Matricaria discoidea</i>	ARC	IINH, 2023
	<i>Senecio vulgaris</i>	ARC	IINH, 2023
	<i>Sonchus oleraceus</i>	MED	Carlesi et al., 2021
Brassicaceae	<i>Capsella bursa-pastoris</i>	ARC	IINH, 2023
Caryophyllaceae	<i>Stellaria media</i>	ARC	IINH, 2023
Convolvulaceae	<i>Convolvulus arvensis</i>	MED	Alfaro-Fernández et al., 2017
Cyperaceae	<i>Cyperus esculentus</i>	ALP, CONT	Total et al., 2018
Equicetaceae	<i>Equisetum ramosissimum</i>	MED	Alfaro-Fernández et al., 2017
Papaveraceae	<i>Fumaria officinalis</i>	MED	Carlesi et al., 2021
Poaceae	<i>Digitaria sanguinalis</i>	PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000
	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000
	<i>Elymus repens</i>	ARC	IINH, 2023
	<i>Poa pratensis</i>	ARC	IINH, 2023
	<i>Setaria verticillata</i>	MED	Alfaro-Fernández et al., 2017
Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria lapathifolia</i>	MED	Carlesi et al., 2021

	<i>Polygonum aviculare</i>	ARC, PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000; IINH, 2023
	<i>Rumex longifolius</i>	ARC	IINH, 2023
Portulacaceae	<i>Portulaca oleracea</i>	MED	Carlesi et al., 2021
Solanaceae	<i>Solanum nigrum</i>	MED	Carlesi et al., 2021
Urticaceae	<i>Urtica urens</i>	MED	Alfaro-Fernández et al., 2017

ARC=Arctic; ATL=Atlantic; CONT= Continental; MED= Mediterranean; PAN=Pannonian

Lettuce

Lettuce (*Lactuca sativa* L.) is a leafy vegetable crop that is notable for its high water content, low calorie content and the presence of beneficial compounds such as vitamins, pigments or phenolic compounds, which are attributed with numerous healthy properties for humans (Shi et al., 2022).

According to FAO (FAOSTAT, 2024), the main worldwide producers of lettuce and radicchio in 2022 are China, the United States and India, with a production of 14,982,813.3, 3,298,933, and 1,161,251.37 Mg, respectively. Spain, Italy, Belgium and Turkey are the leading producers of lettuce and radicchio in Europe, with 969,190, 638,180, 600,640, and 561,990 Mg produced in 2022, respectively (FAOSTAT, 2024).

Due to its small size, especially at the beginning of the cycle, lettuce has a low capacity to compete with weeds in the environment (Pereira et al., 2023), so weed control is very important for high yields in lettuce production. The yield of vegetables may be decreased by 45-95% in the case of weed–vegetable competition (Mennan et al., 2020b). In the case of lettuce, losses due to weeds can range from 20-40% when infestation is moderate, and even up to loss of the entire crop when infestation is high (Shem-Tov et al., 2006). Weeds not only reduce crop yields, but also crop quality by reducing leaf size, firmness, and concentration of nutrients and beneficial compounds such as carotenoids (Casadesei et al., 2020).

Various weed species can be observed in lettuce fields. In Australia, Kristiansen et al. (2008) found *D. sanguinalis*, *Paspalum dilatatum* Poir., *S. pumila*, *P. aviculare*, *H. trionum* L., *E. crus-galli*, *Rumex acetosella* L., *Lolium arundinaceum* (Schreb.) Darbysh., *Erigeron bonariensis* L., and *F. myuros*. Ghahremani et al. (2021) found mostly *C. album*, *A. retroflexus*, and *S. arvensis* in Iranian fields. Shem-Tov et al. (2006) observed *S. oleraceus*, *S. media*, *C. album*, *A. retroflexus*, *S. nigrum*, and *S. arvensis* in lettuce fields in USA, while Kruse and Nair (2016) found *C. album*, *S. viridis*, *Lepidium densiflorum*

Schrad., *P. pennsylvanicum*, *Lactuca serriola* L., *C. bursa-pastoris*, and *S. pumila*. In the trial of Kennedy et al. (2020), *U. urens*, and *P. oleracea* were the predominant weeds.

In Europe, *A. theophrasti*, *A. artemisiifolia*, and *X. strumarium* are common weed species in Serbian fields (Umiljendić et al., 2022). In Italy, the second largest lettuce producer in Europe, Virili and Moonen (2022) observed *A. retroflexus*, *C. album*, *C. dactylon*, *Cyperus* spp., *D. sanguinalis*, and *S. nigrum* as the predominant weeds, while in Turkey Isik et al. (2009) found *C. arvensis*, *P. oleracea*, *C. arvensis*, *A. retroflexus*, *E. crus-galli*, and *C. dactylon* as the most predominant weeds.

Table 14. Main weed species in lettuce crops in different Biogeographical areas of the European Union.

LETTUCE			
Family	Main weed species	Biogeographical area	References
Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus retroflexus</i>	MED	Virili and Moonen, 2022
	<i>Chenopodium album</i>	MED	Virili and Moonen, 2022
Asteraceae	<i>Ambrosia artemisiifolia</i>	CONT	Umiljendić et al., 2022
	<i>Xanthium strumarium</i>	CONT	Umiljendić et al., 2022
Cyperaceae	<i>Cyperus</i> spp.	MED	Virili and Moonen, 2022
Malvaceae	<i>Abutilon theophrasti</i>	CONT	Umiljendić et al., 2022
Poaceae	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	MED	Virili and Moonen, 2022
	<i>Digitaria sanguinalis</i>	MED	Virili and Moonen, 2022
Solanaceae	<i>Solanum nigrum</i>	MED	Virili and Moonen, 2022

CONT= Continental; MED= Mediterranean

Melon

Melon (*Cucumis melo* L.) is a crop of economic interest as it is in demand for its organoleptic properties, is a source of vitamins and microelements, as well as having beneficial properties for human health (Vella et al., 2019). In addition, research into the use of melon waste products is being carried out in recent years, such as the skin, which is rich in phenolic compounds and can be used for bioethanol production (Rico et al., 2023).

China, Turkey and India lead the world ranking in melon production, with 14,200,547.42, 1,587,230, and 1,498,000 Mg produced in 2022 (FAOSTAT 2024). Other European countries with a high melon production are Italy with 590,230 Mg, Spain with 524,040 Mg and France with 307,500 Mg in 2022 (FAOSTAT, 2024).

In a trial conducted by Carvalho et al. (2022) in Brazil, they found that the predominant weeds in the working plots were *Trianthema portulacastrum* L., *Amaranthus spinosus* L., *Senna obtusifolia* (L.) H.S.Irwin & Barneby, *Macroptilium lathyroides* (L.) Urb., *Merremia aegyptia* (L.) Urb., *Jacquemontia tamnifolia* Griseb., *Mollugo verticillata* L., *Urochloa plantaginea* (Link) R.D.Webster, *Mimosa pudica* L., *Digitaria horizontalis* Willd., *Waltheria indica* L., and *Ipomoea triloba* L. *E. crus-galli*, *S. nigrum*, *Amaranthus* spp., *Centaurea montana* L., and *C. arvensis* were the main weeds found by Bairambekov et al. (2016) in fields in Russia. In the trial conducted by Kaçan (2019) between 2012 and 2016 in Turkey, he found *A. hybridus*, *Amaranthus albus* L., *A. retroflexus*, *S. halepense*, and *C. arvensis*, among other weeds. Ciaccia et al. (2020) found *L. arvensis*, *C. arvensis*, *P. aviculare*, *R. crispus*, *A. retroflexus*, and *P. oleracea* in a study conducted in Italy in 2014 and 2015. Hunyadi et al. in their 2000 study presume if the fields for melon are well selected then you have to count only the large dicotyledonous weeds like *D. sophia*, *Amaranthus* spp., *Chenopodium* spp., *Datura stramonium* L., *G. parviflora*, the invasive *A. artemisiifolia*, and *H. trionum* in melon fields in Hungary.

Table 15. Main weed species in melon crops in different Biogeographical areas of the European Union.

MELON			
Family	Main weed species	Biogeographical area	References
Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus</i> spp.	BOR, PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000; Bairambekov et al., 2016;
	<i>Amaranthus retroflexus</i>	CONT, MED	Ciaccia et al., 2020; Candido et al., 2008
	<i>Chenopodium</i> spp.	PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000
Asteraceae	<i>Ambrosia artemisiifolia</i>	PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000
	<i>Centaurea montana</i>	BOR	Bairambekov et al., 2016
	<i>Galinsoga parviflora</i>	PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000

Brassicaceae	<i>Descurainia sophia</i>	PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000
Convolvulaceae	<i>Convolvulus arvensis</i>	BOR, CONT	Bairambekov et al., 2016, Ciaccia et al., 2020
Cucurbitaceae	<i>Ecballium elaterium</i>	MED	Maachi et al., 2022
Cyperaceae	<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	MED	Candido et al., 2008
Fabaceae	<i>Vicia sativa</i>	MED	Candido et al., 2008
Malvaceae	<i>Hibiscus trionum</i>	PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000
	<i>Malva sylvestris</i>	MED	Maachi et al., 2022
Poaceae	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	MED	Candido et al., 2008
	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	BOR, MED	Bairambekov et al., 2016; Candido et al., 2008
	<i>Phragmites australis</i>	MED	Candido et al., 2008
Polygonaceae	<i>Polygonum aviculare</i>	CONT	Ciaccia et al., 2020
	<i>Rumex crispus</i>	CONT	Ciaccia et al., 2020
Portulacaceae	<i>Portulaca oleracea</i>	CONT, MED	Ciaccia et al., 2020; Candido et al., 2008
Primulaceae	<i>Lysimachia arvensis</i>	CONT	Ciaccia et al., 2020
Solanaceae	<i>Datura stramonium</i>	PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000
	<i>Solanum nigrum</i>	BOR, MED	Bairambekov et al., 2016; Candido et al., 2008; Maachi et al., 2022

BOR=Boreal; CONT= Continental; MED= Mediterranean; PAN=Pannonian

Tomato

Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) is a widely distributed horticultural product cultivated worldwide. It is very common in the Mediterranean diet, thanks to its taste, freshness and nutritional properties, as it contains a high amount of carbohydrates, proteins, microelements, vitamins, antioxidant compounds, etc. which make it an excellent product beneficial to human health (Ali et al., 2021).

China was the largest tomato producer in 2022, with a production of 68,241,810.69 Mg, followed by India and Turkey with 20,694,000 and 13,000,000 Mg, respectively (FAOSTAT, 2024). In Europe, after Turkey, the largest tomato producer is Italy, with a total of 6,136,380 Mg produced in 2022, followed by Spain in third position, with 3,651,940 Mg, and Russia and Portugal in fourth and fifth position, with 2,645,662 and 1,406,280 Mg, respectively (FAOSTAT, 2024).

Because they are grown in wide rows and grow slowly, tomatoes do not compete well with weeds, which reduces crop quality and yield (Daramola et al., 2021). This competition can lead to yield losses of 48-71% when competing with *D. sanguinalis*, *I. purpurea*, *X. strumarium*, and *D. stramonium* (Mennan et al., 2020b), seriously compromising the crop.

In the United States of America, *Amaranthus palmeri* S.Watson, *C. esculentus*, and *D. sanguinalis* are among the most frequent weeds in tomato fields (Werle et al., 2022). Bhaskar et al. (2020) found *Amaranthus powellii* S. Watson, *sC. bursa-pastoris*, *C. album*, *Galinsoga quadriradiata* Ruiz & Pav., *P. oleracea*, and *Solanum americanum* Mill. as major weeds also in USA tomato fields. In Greece, Cheimona et al. (2016) found *A. retroflexus* as the predominant weed and other species such as *S. nigrum*, *Solanum elaeagnifolium* Cav., *C. arvensis*, *C. rotundus*, *S. halepense*, and *C. album*, among others. Also in Greece, Kati et al. (2021) observed different weed species in winter (*S. oleraceus*, *Helminthotheca echioides* (L.) Holub, *L. serriola*, *C. intybus*, *V. hederifolia*, *S. arvensis*, *P. rhoeas*, *D. carota*, and *C. arvensis*) and summer crops (*C. arvensis*, *H. echioides*, *S. nigrum*, *A. theophrasti*, *Amaranthus* spp., *S. halepense*, *E. crus-galli*, *Digitaria* spp., and *Cyperus* spp.). Campiglia et al. (2018) found different weeds in Italian tomato fields with different cropping systems, and observed *S. viridis*, *E. crus-galli*, *D. sanguinalis*, *A. sterilis* among the most common weeds in conventional treatments, and *C. arvensis*, *C. arvensis*, *Tribulus terrestris* L., *Heliotropium europaeum* L., *P. aviculare*, *S. arvensis*, *Silybum marianum* (L.) Gaertn., *D. stramonium*, and *M. annua* in organic treatments.

The weeds ripening seeds end of the summer like *A. retroflexus*, *A. artemisiifolia*, *C. album*, *H. trionum*, and *P. oleracea* cause the biggest trouble in Hungarian tomato fields. Frequent weeds are the summer seed ripening species, as well as *S. arvensis*, *R. raphanistrum*. Among the perennial species, the cover of *E. crus-galli*, *D. sanguinalis*, and *Setaria* spp. can be large. (Hunyadi et al., 2000)

Table 16. Main weed species in tomato crops in different Biogeographical areas of the European Union.

TOMATO			
Family	Main weed species	Biogeographical area	References
Apiaceae	<i>Daucus carota</i>	MED	Kati et al., 2021
Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus</i> spp.	MED	Kati et al., 2021
	<i>Amaranthus retroflexus</i>	MED, PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000; Cheimona et al., 2016; Lovelli et al., 2017
	<i>Chenopodium album</i>	MED, PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000; Cheimona et al., 2016
Asteraceae	<i>Ambrosia artemisiifolia</i>	PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000
Asteraceae	<i>Cichorium intybus</i>	MED	Kati et al., 2021
	<i>Cirsium arvense</i>	MED	Campiglia et al., 2018
	<i>Helminthotheca echioides</i>	MED	Kati et al., 2021
	<i>Lactuca serriola</i>	MED	Kati et al., 2021
	<i>Silybum marianum</i>	MED	Campiglia et al., 2018
	<i>Sonchus arvensis</i>	MED, PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000; Campiglia et al., 2018
	<i>Sonchus oleraceus</i>	MED	Kati et al., 2021
Brassicaceae	<i>Sinapis arvensis</i>	MED, PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000; Kati et al., 2021
	<i>Raphanus raphanistrum</i>	PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000
Boraginaceae	<i>Heliotropium europaeum</i>	MED	Campiglia et al., 2018
Convolvulaceae	<i>Convolvulus arvensis</i>	MED	Cheimona et al., 2016; Campiglia et al., 2018; Kati et al., 2021

Cyperaceae	<i>Cyperus</i> spp.	MED	Kati et al., 2021
	<i>Cyperus Rotundus</i>	MED	Cheimona et al., 2016
Euphorbiaceae	<i>Mercurialis annua</i>	MED	Campiglia et al., 2018
Malvaceae	<i>Abutilon theophrasti</i>	MED	Kati et al., 2021
	<i>Hibiscus trionum</i>	PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000
Papaveraceae	<i>Papaver rhoeas</i>	MED	Kati et al., 2021
Plantaginaceae	<i>Veronica hederifolia</i>	MED	Kati et al., 2021
Poaceae	<i>Avena sterilis</i>	MED	Campiglia et al., 2018
	<i>Digitaria sanguinalis</i>	MED, PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000; Campiglia et al., 2018; Montull and Torra, 2023
	<i>Digitaria</i> spp.	MED	Kati et al., 2021
	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	MED, PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000; Campiglia et al., 2018; Kati et al., 2021; Montull and Torra, 2023
	<i>Panicum dichotomiflorum</i>	MED	Montull and Torra, 2023
	<i>Setaria</i> spp.	MED, PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000; Montull and Torra, 2023
	<i>Setaria viridis</i>	MED	Campiglia et al., 2018
	<i>Sorghum halepense</i>	MED	Cheimona et al., 2016; Kati et al., 2021
Polygonaceae	<i>Polygonum aviculare</i>	MED	Campiglia et al., 2018
Portulacaceae	<i>Portulaca oleracea</i>	PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000
Solanaceae	<i>Datura stramonium</i>	MED	Campiglia et al., 2018
	<i>Solanum elaeagnifolium</i>	MED	Cheimona et al., 2016

	<i>Solanum nigrum</i>	MED	Cheimona et al., 2016; Kati et al., 2021
Zygophyllaceae	<i>Tribulus terrestris</i>	MED	Campiglia et al., 2018

MED=Mediterranean; PAN=Pannonian

Zucchini

Zucchini (*Cucurbita pepo* L.) is a vegetable that can be consumed fresh or processed, with important nutritional properties, due to its low caloric content and its high content in fiber, proteins, carbohydrates, and microelements, such as potassium and manganese. It also has beneficial properties for human health due to the presence of phytochemicals such as phenolic compounds, carotenoids, anthocyanins, and vitamins that help to prevent diseases (Thanh et al., 2023). In Europe, zucchini production is mainly located in Mediterranean countries, with Spain, Turkey, Italy, France and Greece being the five largest producers with a production in 2022 of 617,000, 590,000, 558,000, 158,000, 53,000 Mg, respectively (EUROSTAT, 2024).

Monks and Schultheis (1998) discovered that after 4, 6, and 10 weeks of substantial crabgrass and watermelon competition, the number of fruits decreased by 25, 66, and 82%, respectively. Marketable watermelons decreased by 35% as a result of season-long interference from a variety of plant species, such as *Amaranthus* spp., *Chenopodium* spp., *A. artemisiifolia*, and *I. hederacea* (Vollmer et al. 2020). In comparison to the hand-weeded check, Peachey et al. (2012) showed a 63% and 86% yield drop in cucumber and summer squash, respectively, due to weed competition.

In the United States, a wide variety of weeds can be found in courgette fields. Walters and Young (2008) found *A. retroflexus* and *Digitaria ischaemum* (Schreb.) Muhl., while Besançon et al. (2020) found *A. hybridus*, *C. album*, *G. quadriradiata*, *S. nigrum*, *M. verticillata*, *S. faberi*, and *D. sanguinalis*. Webber et al. (2014) found *D. ischaemum*, *Physalis angulata* L., *A. spinosus*, and *C. esculentus* in US zucchini fields. Also, Webber et al. (2017) in another trial, found as predominant weeds *D. ischaemum*, *P. angulata*, and *A. spinosus*.

In Europe, other types of weeds can be found. In Poland, Bucki et al. (2021) observed that the predominant weeds were *Galinsoga* sp., *E. crus-galli*, *A. retroflexus*, *C. album*, *C. bursa-pastoris*, and *Thlaspi arvense* L.. In the Mediterranean region, in Italy, Ciaccia et al. (2015) observed in 2010 *Ecballium elaterium* (L.) A.Rich., *C. arvensis*, *P. oleracea*, and *Picris hieracioides* L., *T. officinale*, *E. elaterium*, and *P. oleracea* in 2011 in zucchini fields, while Testani et al. (2019) found *A. retroflexus*, *E. crus-galli*, *Lolium* spp., *Plantago lanceolata* L., *R. crispus*, *S. viridis*, and *S. oleraceus*, among others, between 2014-2015.

Table 17. Main weed species in zucchini crops in different Biogeographical areas of the European Union.

ZUCCHINI			
Family	Main weed species	Biogeographical area	References
Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus retroflexus</i>	CONT, MED	Testani et al., 2019; Bucki et al.,2021
	<i>Chenopodium album</i>	CONT	Bucki et al.,2021
Asteraceae	<i>Galinsoga</i> sp.	CONT	Bucki et al.,2021
	<i>Picris hieracioides</i>	MED	Ciaccia et al., 2015
	<i>Sonchus oleraceus</i>	MED	Testani et al., 2019
	<i>Taraxacum officinale</i>	MED	Ciaccia et al., 2015
Brassicaceae	<i>Capsella bursa-pastoris</i>	CONT	Bucki et al.,2021
	<i>Thlaspi arvense</i>	CONT	Bucki et al.,2021
Convolvulaceae	<i>Convolvulus arvensis</i>	MED	Ciaccia et al., 2015
Cucurbitaceae	<i>Ecballium elaterium</i>	MED	Ciaccia et al., 2015
Plantaginaceae	<i>Plantago lanceolata</i>	MED	Testani et al., 2019
Poaceae	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	CONT, MED	Testani et al., 2019; Bucki et al.,2021
	<i>Lolium</i> spp.	MED	Testani et al., 2019
	<i>Setaria viridis</i>	MED	Testani et al., 2019
Polygonaceae	<i>Rumex crispus</i>	MED	Testani et al., 2019
Portulacaceae	<i>Portulaca oleracea</i>	MED	Ciaccia et al., 2015

CONT=Continental; MED=Mediterranean; PAN=Pannonian

Important weeds in perennial crops

Almond

Almonds (*Prunus dulcis* (Mill.) D.A. Webb) are one of the most consumed tree-nuts worldwide, whose fruit has a variety of uses. Unlike other *Prunus* species, the kernel is the part that is consumed, while the hull and shell are discarded and can be used for energy, bioplastics, livestock feed, etc. (Tomishima et al., 2022). Almonds are relatively low in sugars, but rich in protein, lipids, minerals, vitamins, and antioxidant compounds (Massantini and Frangipane, 2022), and have 30-60% of oil that can be used as bioenergy material (Akubude and Nwaigne, 2016).

The United States of America was the largest producer of almonds in 2022, with a production of 1,858,010 Mg, followed by Australia with 360,328.03 Mg and Spain in third position with 245,990 Mg (FAO, 2024). In Europe, in addition to Spain, Turkey, Italy, Portugal, and Greece are the largest producers of almonds, with 190,000, 74,590, 46,220 and 39,570 Mg, respectively (FAO, 2024).

Shrestha et al. (2012) observed that weed diversity in USA almond orchards between 2009 and 2011 was highest in the summer and winter months, with *P. annua*, *S. oleraceus*, *S. media*, *E. bonariensis*, *L. multiflorum*, *B. diandrus*, and *C. bursa-pastoris* as some of the present weeds. Also in the United States, Haring et al. (2023) found *P. annua*, *A. fatua*, *L. arvensis*, *Phalaris minor* Retz., *P. lanceolata*, *C. dactylon*, *C. arvensis*, *M. polymorpha*, *C. bursa-pastoris*, *S. media*, *Ranunculus parviflorus* L., *R. crispus*, *L. serriola*, *T. officinale*, *E. canadensis*, and *S. oleraceus*, among others. In Europe, De Giorgio and Lamascese (2005) observed *A. fatua*, *T. repens*, *Malva sylvestris* L., *C. bursa-pastoris*, *Calendula arvensis* L., *Diploaxis eruroides* (L.) DC., *L. perenne*, and *C. arvensis* in almond orchards in Italy. Fracchiolla et al. (2016) found *C. arvensis*, *C. dactylon*, *Diploaxis muralis* DC., *H. murinum*, *A. retroflexus*, *Lathyrus* sp., and *H. europaeum* among others in autumn and *H. murinum*, *G. aparine*, *Sherardia arvensis* L., *E. canadensis*, *Fumaria capreolata* L., *L. amplexicaule*, *V. hederifolia*, *C. arvensis*, *D. eruroides*, *L. rigidum*, and *S. vulgaris* among others in spring in experimental almond fields with different soil management techniques in Italy.

Table 18. Main weed species in almond orchards in the Mediterranean Biogeographical area of the European Union.

ALMOND			
Family	Main weed species	Biogeographical area	References
Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus retroflexus</i>	MED	Fracchiolla et al., 2016
Asteraceae	<i>Calendula arvensis</i>	MED	De Giorgio and Lamascese, 2005
	<i>Erigeron canadensis</i>	MED	Fracchiolla et al., 2016

	<i>Senecio vulgaris</i>	MED	Fracchiolla et al., 2016
Brassicaceae	<i>Capsella bursa-pastoris</i>	MED	De Giorgio and Lamascese, 2005
	<i>Diplotaxis eruroides</i>	MED	De Giorgio and Lamascese, 2005; Fracchiolla et al., 2016
	<i>Diplotaxis muralis</i>	MED	Fracchiolla et al., 2016
Boraginaceae	<i>Heliotropium europaeum</i>	MED	Fracchiolla et al., 2016
Convolvulaceae	<i>Convolvulus arvensis</i>	MED	De Giorgio and Lamascese, 2005; Fracchiolla et al., 2016
Fabaceae	<i>Lathyrus sp</i>	MED	Fracchiolla et al., 2016
	<i>Trifolium repens</i>	MED	De Giorgio and Lamascese, 2005
Malvaceae	<i>Malva sylvestris</i>	MED	De Giorgio and Lamascese, 2005
Lamiaceae	<i>Lamium amplexicaule</i>	MED	Fracchiolla et al., 2016
Papaveraceae	<i>Fumaria capreolata</i>	MED	Fracchiolla et al., 2016
Plantaginaceae	<i>Veronica hederifolia</i>	MED	Fracchiolla et al., 2016
Poaceae	<i>Avena fatua</i>	MED	De Giorgio and Lamascese, 2005
	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	MED	Fracchiolla et al., 2016
	<i>Hordeum murinum</i>	MED	Fracchiolla et al., 2016
	<i>Lolium arundinaceum</i>	MED	Peralta y Royuela., 2019
	<i>Lolium perenne</i>	MED	De Giorgio and Lamascese, 2005
	<i>Lolium rigidum</i>	MED	Fracchiolla et al., 2016

Rubiaceae	<i>Galium aparine</i>	MED	Fracchiolla et al., 2016
	<i>Sherardia arvensis</i>	MED	Fracchiolla et al., 2016

MED=Mediterranean

Apple

Apple (*Malus domestica* Borkh.) is one of the most important fruits produced and eaten around the world, representing one of the most nutritional foods in a healthy diet for its content in water, sugars (fructose, glucose, and sucrose), vitamins, minerals, and dietary fibers (Musacchi and Serra, 2018). It also contains a large number of polyphenols (anthocyanins, flavonols, organic acids, etc.), thanks to which the apple has a number of beneficial health effects, such as anti-oxidant, cardiovascular protection, anti-inflammatory, etc. (Bondonno et al., 2017). In addition to the fruit itself, by-products from its processing, such as peel, seeds, pulp etc. (known as pomace) are a source of beneficial nutrients that can be used as a dietary supplement (Skinner et al., 2018), which would support the circular economy by making use of waste products.

China is the world's largest producer of apples, with 47,571,800 Mg produced in 2022, followed far behind by Turkey in second place with 4,817,500 Mg and the United States in third place with 4,429,330 Mg (FAOSTAT, 2024). In Europe, apart from Turkey, the largest apple producers in 2022 were Poland, Russia, Italy, and France, with 4,264,700, 2,379,900, 2,256,240 and 1,785,660 Mg produced, respectively.

Weed pressure, due to inadequate management of weed in apple, can reduce tree growth from 15% to 96%, while yield losses can reach 35-42% because of the adverse impact on fruit quality (Dudic et al., 2020; Hussain et al., 2020c).

In China, Song et al. (2020b) found *Crepidiastrum sonchifolium* (Bunge) Pak & Kawano, *S. viridis*, *Carduus crispus* L., *Chenopodium glaucum* L., and *C. arvensis* in apple orchards. Oliveira et al. (2016) observed that the predominant weeds in a Brazilian apple orchard were *T. repens*, *Trifolium pratense* L., *Paspalum notatum* Flügge, and *Chaptalia nutans* Hemsl.. In Poland, *P. annua*, *S. media*, *E. crus-galli*, and *Draba verna* L. were the predominant weed species observed by Bałuszyńska et al. (2022). Dudic et al. (2020) found in Serbian apple orchards *P. annua*, *H. murinum*, *E. canadensis*, *P. oleracea*, *C. dactylon*, *S. halepense*, *A. retroflexus*, *C. arvensis*, *C. album*, and *S. nigrum*. Mia et al. (2020) observed *T. officinale*, *S. oleraceus*, *V. persica*, *T. repens*, *C. dactylon*, and *L. perenne*, among others, in Italian orchards between 2018 and 2019. In Spain, Juárez-Escario et al. (2017) found *Bromus catharticus* Vahl, *E. colonum*, *Crepis bursifolia* L., and *Setaria adhaerens* (Forssk.) Chiov. in pear and apple orchards, while

Miñarro (2012) found, among others, *E. crus-galli*, *Oxalis latifolia* Kunth, *C. album*, *P. lanceolata*, and *S. vulgaris*, also in Spanish apple orchards. In the Boreal region, weeds distribution and biomass exhibit considerable variation. The growth of weeds, as herbaceous plants, is influenced by soil type, moisture content and the presence of surrounding natural vegetation. In Estonian apple orchards the mowing is performed once or several times per vegetation period therefore the weeds do not comprise competition for the trees and they become part of the grass mulch. The species that have potential to become a weed in Estonian fields are *C. album*, *Lamium album* L., *Urtica dioica* L., *Epilobium angustifolium* L., *Artemisia vulgaris* L., *C. arvense* (Kahu and Luik, 2010).. In Hungary, you can find 45-50 weed species in apple orchards. The most frequent weed species are here the dicotyledon *Amaranthus* spp., *A. artemisiifolia*, *C. album*, *E. canadensis* and *Polygonum* spp.. *E. crus-galli*, *D. sanguinalis*, *C. americanus* and *P. annua* are also commonly found in young orchards (Hunyadi et al., 2000).

Table 19. Main weed species in apple orchards in different Biogeographical areas of the European Union.

APPLE			
Family	Main weed species	Biogeographical area	References
Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus</i> spp.	PAN	Hunyad et al., 2000
	<i>Amaranthus retroflexus</i>	CONT	Dudic et al., 2020
	<i>Chenopodium album</i>	ATL, CONT, MED	Miñarro, 2012; Dudic et al., 2020
Asteraceae	<i>Ambrosia artemisiifolia</i>	PAN	Hunyad et al., 2000
	<i>Artemisia vulgaris</i>	BOR	Kahu and Luik, 2010
	<i>Cirsium arvense</i>	CONT	Dudic et al., 2020
	<i>Crepis bursifolia</i>	MED	Juárez-Escario et al., 2017
	<i>Erigeron canadensis</i>	CONT, PAN	Hunyad et al., 2000; Dudic et al., 2020
	<i>Senecio vulgaris</i>	ATL, MED	Miñarro, 2012
	<i>Sonchus oleraceus</i>	CONT	Mia et al., 2020

	<i>Taraxacum officinale</i>	CONT	Mia et al., 2020
Brassicaceae	<i>Draba verna</i>	CONT	Bałaszzyńska et al., 2022
Caryophyllaceae	<i>Stellaria media</i>	CONT	Bałaszzyńska et al., 2022
Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium repens</i>	CONT	Mia et al., 2020
Lamiaceae	<i>Lamium album</i>	BOR	Kahu and Luik, 2010
Onagraceae	<i>Epilobium angustifolium</i>	BOR	Kahu and Luik, 2010
Oxiladaceae	<i>Oxalis latifolia</i>	ATL, MED	Miñarro, 2012
Plantaginaceae	<i>Plantago lanceolata</i>	ATL, MED	Miñarro, 2012
	<i>Veronica persica</i>	CONT	Mia et al., 2020
Poaceae	<i>Bromus catharticus</i>	MED	Juárez-Escario et al., 2017
	<i>Cenchrus americanus</i>	PAN	
	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	CONT	Dudic et al., 2020; Mia et al., 2020
	<i>Digitaria sanguinalis</i>	PAN	Hunyad et al., 2000
	<i>Echinochloa colonum</i>	MED	Juárez-Escario et al., 2017
	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	ATL, CONT, MED, PAN	Hunyad et al., 2000; Miñarro, 2012; Bałaszzyńska et al., 2022
	<i>Hordeum murinum</i>	CONT	Dudic et al., 2020
	<i>Lolium perenne</i>	BOR	Kahu and Luik, 2010
	<i>Poa annua</i>	CONT, PAN	Hunyad et al., 2000; Dudic et al., 2020; Bałaszzyńska et al., 2022
	<i>Setaria adhaerens</i>	MED	Juárez-Escario et al., 2017
	<i>Sorghum halepense</i>	CONT	Dudic et al., 2020
Polygonaceae	<i>Polygonum spp.</i>	PAN	Hunyad et al., 2000

Portulacaceae	<i>Portulaca oleracea</i>	CONT	Dudic et al., 2020
Solanaceae	<i>Solanum nigrum</i>	CONT	Dudic et al., 2020
Urticaceae	<i>Urtica dioica</i>	BOR	Kahu and Luik, 2010

ATL= Atlantic; BOR=Boreal; CONT=Continental; MED=Mediterranean; PAN=Pannonian

Apricot

Apricot (*Prunus armeniaca* L.) is one of the most important fruits produced in temperate areas. It stands out for its high percentage of water, carbohydrates, minerals (Zn, Ca, Cu, Fe, Mg, Na, Mn, P, and K), and fibre, that is consumed not only for its taste and smell, but also because it contains numerous compounds such as vitamins, β -carotene, phenolic compounds, which make it a functional food (Fратиanni et al., 2018; Karatas, 2022). Different by-products can be obtained from apricots, such as juice or dried apricots, from which waste products are generated that can be used to obtain new products (such as apricot oil obtained from the kernel, or pomace used as a food supplement), thus reducing the amount of waste generated during apricot processing and favouring the circular economy (Fратиanni et al., 2018; Kasapoglu et al., 2020).

The largest producer of apricots in 2022 was Turkey with 803,000 Mg, followed by Uzbekistan and Iran with 451,262.76 and 305,932.21 Mg, respectively (FAOSTAT, 2024). In addition to Turkey, Italy with 230,080 Mg, France with 128,080 Mg, Armenia with 113,572.3 Mg, and Greece with 112,230 Mg were the largest producers of apricots in Europe in 2022 (FAOSTAT, 2024).

Grădilă and Jalobă (2020) found *C. bursa-pastoris*, *C. album*, *F. officinalis*, *L. purpureum*, *M. sylvestris*, *Matricaria* spp., *P. rhoeas*, *F. convolvulus*, *P. oleracea*, *Veronica* spp., *Xanthium* spp., and *Setaria* spp. in Romanian apricot orchards. In Italy, Scavo et al. (2021) found in the seedbank of apricot orchards *Sonchus* sp., *L. arvensis*, *Phalaris paradoxa* L., *Centaurea napifolia* L., *P. oleracea*, *A. retroflexus*, *S. arvensis*, and *Veronica cymbalaria* Bodard, while Ciaccia et al. (2022) observed *C. arvensis*, *C. dactylon*, *R. crispus*, *V. persica*, *T. repens*, *L. multiflorum*, *Avena barbata* Pott ex Link, and *C. intybus*, among others. In an apricot orchard in Turkey, Tursun et al. (2018) observed that the dominant weed species were *A. retroflexus*, *C. arvensis*, *T. terrestris*, *Sisymbrium officinale* (L.) Scop., *S. halepense*, *L. amplexicaule*, *C. album*, *T. arvense*, and *Vaccaria hispanica* (Mill.) Rauschert. Also in Turkey, Karaman et al. (2021) found *A. retroflexus*, *C. arvensis*, *T. terrestris*, *S. officinale*, *S. halepense*, *L. amplexicaule*, *C. album*, *T. arvense*, and *V. hispanica* as the predominant weeds in apricot orchards. Similarly, in Hungary, the alleys and spaces between the trees host a diverse weed flora, including perennial species such as *C. arvense*, *C. arvensis*, *A. syriaca*, *Aristolochia clematitis* L., *Rubus* spp., *C. dactylon*, *E. repens*, and *S.*

halepense, representing both dicotyledon and monocotyledon species. Spring ripening species such as *S. media*, *Lamium* spp., and *C. bursa-pastoris* dominate the interrow (Hunyadi et al., 2000).

Table 20. Main weed species in apricot orchards in different Biogeographical areas of the European Union.

APRICOT			
Family	Main weed species	Biogeographical area	References
Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus retroflexus</i>	MED	Scavo et al., 2021
	<i>Chenopodium album</i>	BS	Grădilă and Jalobă, 2020
Apocynaceae	<i>Asclepias syriaca</i>	PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000
Aristolochiaceae	<i>Aristolochia clematitis</i>	PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000
Asteraceae	<i>Centaurea napifolia</i>	MED	Scavo et al., 2021
	<i>Cichorium intybus</i>	MED	Ciaccia et al., 2022
	<i>Cirsium arvense</i>	PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000
	<i>Matricaria</i> spp.	BS	Grădilă and Jalobă, 2020
	<i>Sonchus</i> sp.	MED	Scavo et al., 2021
	<i>Xanthium</i> spp.	BS	Grădilă and Jalobă, 2020
Brassicaceae	<i>Capsella bursa-pastoris</i>	BS, PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000; Grădilă and Jalobă, 2020
	<i>Sinapis arvensis</i>	MED	Scavo et al., 2021
Caryophyllaceae	<i>Stellaria media</i>	PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000
Convolvulaceae	<i>Convolvulus arvensis</i>	MED, PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000; Ciaccia et al., 2022
Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium repens</i>	MED	Ciaccia et al., 2022
	<i>Malva sylvestris</i>	BS	Grădilă and Jalobă, 2020
Lamiaceae	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	BS	Grădilă and Jalobă, 2020

	<i>Lamium</i> spp.	PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000
Papaveraceae	<i>Fumaria officinalis</i>	BS	Grădilă and Jalobă, 2020
	<i>Papaver rhoeas</i>	BS	Grădilă and Jalobă, 2020
Plantaginaceae	<i>Veronica cymbalaria</i>	MED	Scavo et al., 2021
	<i>Veronica persica</i>	MED	Ciaccia et al., 2022
	<i>Veronica</i> spp.	BS	Grădilă and Jalobă, 2020
Poaceae	<i>Avena barbata</i>	MED	Ciaccia et al., 2022
	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	MED, PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000; Ciaccia et al., 2022
	<i>Elymus repens</i>	PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000
	<i>Lolium multiflorum</i>	MED	Ciaccia et al., 2022
	<i>Phalaris paradoxa</i>	MED	Scavo et al., 2021
	<i>Setaria</i> spp.	BS	Grădilă and Jalobă, 2020
	<i>Sorghum halepense</i>	ANA, MED, PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000, DPPP, 2023
Polygonaceae	<i>Fallopia convolvulus</i>	BS	Grădilă and Jalobă, 2020
	<i>Rumex crispus</i>	MED	Ciaccia et al., 2022
Portulacaceae	<i>Portulaca oleracea</i>	BS, MED	Grădilă and Jalobă, 2020; Scavo et al., 2021
Primulaceae	<i>Lysimachia arvensis</i>	MED	Scavo et al., 2021
Rosaceae	<i>Rubus</i> spp.	PAN	Hunyadi et al., 2000

ANA=Anatolian; BS= Black Sea; MED=Mediterranean; PAN=Pannonian

Hazelnut

Hazelnut (*Corylus avellana* L.) is one of the most important nut crops in the world. The fresh consumption of the total harvest accounts a 10% while the rest goes to the food industry for the

production of other products such as chocolate, ice-cream, etc. (Guiné and Correia, 2020). They are a good source of protein, monosaturated fatty acids, carbohydrates, fibre, minerals, vitamins, and phenolic compounds that provide various benefits to human health (Ferrão et al., 2021). Its use is not only for food, as it is possible to produce biodiesel from the oil that can be extracted from the kernel (Saydut et al., 2016).

The three largest producers of hazelnuts in 2022 were Turkey, Italy and Azerbaijan, with 765,000, 98,670, and 72,104.6 Mg produced according to the FAO (FAOSTAT, 2024). Other hazelnut producing countries in Europe are Georgia (33,400 Mg), France (9,960 Mg), Poland (9,500 Mg), Serbia (9,328 Mg), and Spain (8,040 Mg) (FAOSTAT, 2024).

Inefficient weed management can lead to losses in hazelnut production. Kaya-Altop et al. (2016) observed that a mixed population of *A. vulgaris*, *C. rotundus*, and *U. urens*, with a density of 89 plants per m² caused 12.1% yield loss and when the density increased to 256 plants per m², yield losses increased to 29.7%. Mennan et al. (2020a) developed a predictive model of benefit–cost that, in the case of no glyphosate use, total hazelnut production would decrease by 12% to 21% due to inefficient weed control.

In Turkey, Mennan et al. (2006) observed *Pteridium aquilinum* (L.) Kuh., *A. vulgaris*, *U. urens*, *C. arvensis*, *C. album*, *Lapsana communis* L., *P. annua*, *A. myosuroides*, *C. dactylon*, *L. perenne*, and *S. viridis* as the dominant species in hazelnut orchards. Also in Turkey, Macit and Işık (2023) found that the most important weed in hazelnut orchards were *U. urens*, *P. aquilinum*, *P. lapathifolia*, *C. arvensis*, *Fragaria vesca* L., *L. communis*, *S. viridis*, *P. annua*, *L. perenne*, *E. crus-galli*, and *E. repens*. Yazlik's (2023) study determined that the main weeds faced by hazelnut producers in Turkey are *C. sepium*, *Coronilla varia* L., *Dioscorea communis* (L.) Caddick & Wilkin, *Hedera* spp., *Rubus* spp., among others.

Table 21. The main weed species in hazelnut orchards are in the Black Sea Biogeographical area of the European Union.

HAZELNUT			
Family	Main weed species	Biogeographical area	References
Amaranthaceae	<i>Chenopodium album</i>	BS	Mennan et al., 2006
Araliaceae	<i>Hedera spp</i>	BS	Macit and Işık, 2023

Asteraceae	<i>Artemisia vulgaris</i>	BS	Mennan et al., 2006; Kaya-Alttop et al., 2016;
Asteraceae	<i>Lapsana communis</i>	BS	Mennan et al., 2006, Macit and Işık, 2023
Convolvulaceae	<i>Calystegia sepium</i>	BS	Yazlik's, 2023
	<i>Convolvulus arvensis</i>	BS	Mennan et al., 2006, Macit and Işık, 2023
Cyperaceae	<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	BS	Kaya-Alttop et al., 2016
Dennstaedtiaceae	<i>Pteridium aquilinum</i>	BS	Mennan et al., 2006, Macit and Işık, 2023
Dioscoreaceae	<i>Dioscorea communis</i>	BS	Yazlik's, 2023
Fabaceae	<i>Coronilla varia</i>	BS	Yazlik's, 2023
Poaceae	<i>Alopecurus myosuroides</i>	BS	Mennan et al., 2006
	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	BS	Mennan et al., 2006
	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	BS	Macit and Işık, 2023
	<i>Elymus repens</i>	BS	Macit and Işık, 2023
	<i>Lolium perenne</i>	BS	Mennan et al., 2006
	<i>Poa annua</i>	BS	Mennan et al., 2006
	<i>Setaria viridis</i>	BS	Mennan et al., 2006, Macit and Işık, 2023
Polygonaceae	<i>Persicaria lapathifolia</i>	BS	Macit and Işık, 2023
Rosaceae	<i>Rubus</i> spp.	BS	Yazlik's, 2023
	<i>Fragaria vesca</i>	BS	Macit and Işık, 2023
Urticaceae	<i>Urtica urens</i>	BS	Mennan et al., 2006; Kaya-Alttop et al., 2016; Macit and Işık, 2023

BS=Black Sea

Olive

Olive (*Olea europaea* L.) is an evergreen tree cultivated mainly in Mediterranean countries for the production of olive oil, as well as table olives. Olive oil is made up of 98% triacylglycerols (oleic acid being the main one), but it also contains polyphenols that give it antioxidant properties, making olive oil a functional food that is beneficial to human health and of great interest for its organoleptic properties (Bucciantini et al., 2021; Pedan et al., 2019; Yousefi et al., 2018). Table olives are the most widely consumed fermented food in the Mediterranean countries. Its high nutritional value, the content of bioactive compounds, dietary fibers, fatty acid composition, and antioxidants make table olives a valuable functional food (Campus et al., 2018). As a result of the processing of olives into oil and table olives, many by-products (pomace, mill, seeds, leaves...) are generated, and new applications are being sought for them (Nunes et al., 2016). For example, olive leaves are rich in antioxidant molecules with health-promoting properties that are used in the preparation of teas (Özcan and Matthäus, 2017).

The largest producers of olive trees are Mediterranean countries, led by Spain with 3,940,070 Mg, Turkey in second place with 2,976,000 Mg, Italy in third place with 2,160,400 Mg, Morocco in fourth place with 1,968,110.94 Mg, and Tunisia in fifth place with 1,200,000 Mg (FAOSTAT, 2024). In Europe, in addition to the countries mentioned above, Portugal is another major producer of olive trees with 791,660 Mg produced in 2022 (FAOSTAT, 2024).

In Italy, Terzi et al. (2021) found *L. rigidum*, *Hypochaeris achyrophorus* L., *S. oleraceus*, *Medicago orbicularis* (L.) Bartal., and *Erodium malacoides* (L.) L'Hér. were the most common species in olive orchards. Also in Italy, Assirelli et al. (2022) observed *Porophyllum ruderale subsp. macrocephalum* (DC.) R.R.Johnson, *A. retroflexus*, *P. oleracea*, *F. officinalis*, *L. multiflorum*, *R. raphanistrum*, and *Trifolium arvense* L. among others, while Las Casas et al. (2022) found *A. retroflexus*, *C. dactylon*, *C. rotundus*, *P. aviculare*, *P. oleracea*, *C. arvensis*, and *P. rhoeas* among others. In Spain, Carpio et al. (2020) found *L. arvensis*, *Bromus rubens* L., and *Bromus hordeaceus* L. as dominant aboveground species, while in the case of the seed banks, they encountered *L. arvensis*, *Campanula erinus* L., *Galium murale* (L.) All., *H. europaeum*, *L. amplexicaule*, *Poa infirma* Kunth, and *S. media*. In addition, in Spain, *E. canadensis*, and *Filago pyramidata* L. are two weeds that are causing problems in olive groves as they are resistant to some herbicides (Mora et al., 2019; Palma-Bautista et al., 2023).

Table 22. Main weed species in olive orchards in the Mediterranean Biogeographical area of the European Union.

OLIVE			
Family	Main weed species	Biogeographical area	References
Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus retroflexus</i>	MED	Assirelli et al., 2022; Las Casas et al., 2022
Asteraceae	<i>Erigeron bonariensis</i>	MED	Bastida et al., 2021
	<i>Erigeron canadensis</i>	MED	Mora et al., 2019; Bastida et al., 2021; Palma-Bautista et al., 2023;
	<i>Erigeron sumatrensis</i>	MED	Bastida et al., 2021
	<i>Hypochaeris achyrophorus</i>	MED	Terzi et al., 2021
	<i>Porophyllum ruderale subsp. Macrocephalum</i>	MED	Assirelli et al., 2022
	<i>Sonchus oleraceus</i>	MED	Terzi et al., 2021
Brassicaceae	<i>Raphanus raphanistrum</i>	MED	Assirelli et al., 2022
Boraginaceae	<i>Heliotropium europaeum</i>	MED	Carpio et al., 2020
Campanulaceae	<i>Campanula erinus</i>	MED	Carpio et al., 2020
Caryophyllaceae	<i>Stellaria media</i>	MED	Carpio et al., 2020
Convolvulaceae	<i>Convolvulus arvensis</i>	MED	Las Casas et al., 2022
Cyperaceae	<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	MED	Las Casas et al., 2022
Fabaceae	<i>Medicago orbicularis</i>	MED	Terzi et al., 2021
	<i>Trifolium arvense</i>	MED	Assirelli et al., 2022
Geraniaceae	<i>Erodium malacoides</i>	MED	Terzi et al., 2021
Lamiaceae	<i>Lamium amplexicaule</i>	MED	Carpio et al., 2020

Papaveraceae	<i>Fumaria officinalis</i>	MED	Assirelli et al., 2022
	<i>Papaver rhoeas</i>	MED	Las Casas et al., 2022
Poaceae	<i>Bromus hordeaceus</i>	MED	Carpio et al., 2020
	<i>Bromus rubens</i>	MED	Carpio et al., 2020
	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	MED	Las Casas et al., 2022
	<i>Filago pyramidata</i>	MED	Mora et al., 2019; Palma-Bautista et al., 2023
	<i>Lolium multiflorum</i>	MED	Assirelli et al., 2022
	<i>Lolium rigidum</i>	MED	Terzi et al., 2021
	<i>Poa infirma</i>	MED	Carpio et al., 2020
Polygonaceae	<i>Polygonum aviculare</i>	MED	Las Casas et al., 2022
Portulacaceae	<i>Portulaca oleracea</i>	MED	Assirelli et al., 2022; Las Casas et al., 2022
Primulaceae	<i>Lysimachia arvensis</i>	MED	Carpio et al., 2020
Rubiaceae	<i>Galium murale</i>	MED	Carpio et al., 2020

MED=Mediterranean

Orange

Orange (*Citrus sinensis* (L.) Osbeck) is the most cultivated citrus crop in the world. The Valencia cultivar and its clones are the most produced, due to their high juice content and good taste (Roussos, 2016). These fruits have sucrose, fructose and glucose as main carbohydrates, amino acids, ascorbic acid, phenolic compounds, minerals, carotenoids, etc., which give them nutritional and beneficial properties for human health, such as cardiovascular protection, anti-obesity, anti-osteoporosis, relaxant, etc. (Favela-Hernández et al., 2016; Roussos, 2016). As a result of the processing of these products, numerous waste products of great economic value are generated due to their content of beneficial molecules such as fibre, polyphenols, carotenoids, essential oils, etc. from which other products of interest such as bioethanol can be obtained (Sharma et al., 2017).

The largest producer of oranges in the world is Brazil, with 16,929,631 Mg produced in 2022, followed by India, China and Mexico, with 10,198,000, 7,706,852.63 and 4,850,083.04 Mg, respectively (FAOSTAT, 2024). In Europe, the main producers are Spain with 2,817,400 Mg, Italy with 1,783,110 Mg, Turkey with 1,322,000 Mg and Greece with 873,670 Mg (FAOSTAT, 2024).

Weeds can act directly on the growth of orange trees by competing with them for resources and releasing allelopathic compounds, and indirectly as a host for pests and pathogens, with losses of up to 33% (Martinelli et al., 2017). The period of coexistence between the crop and the weed is also important, for example, Gonçalves et al. (2018) observed that the presence of weeds between October and May causes yield losses of 34%. Singh et al. (2012) found *Urochloa texana* (Buckley) R.D.Webster, *Megathyrus maximus* (Jacq.) B.K.Simon & S.W.L.Jacobs, *C. dactylon*, *A. artemisiifolia*, *Bidens bipinnata* L., *E. canadensis*, and *S. americanum* in orange orchard in USA. In Mexico, the predominant weeds observed by Alcántara-de la Cruz et al. (2019) in orange orchards were *Bidens pilosa* L., *Leptochloa virgata* (L.) P.Beauv., and *E. colonum*, while *Amaranthus viridis* L., *Cynodon nlemfuensis* Vanderyst, *D. sanguinalis*, *Eleusine indica* (L.) Gaertn., and *Parthenium hysterophorus* L. appeared sporadically. Amaral et al. (2023) collected data from surveys of farmers in Brazil, where they suspected that the species *Amaranthus deflexus* L., *A. hybridus*, *B. pilosa*, *Stapfochloa elata* (Desv.) P.M.Peterson, *E. bonariensis*, *Digitaria insularis* (L.) Mez ex Ekman, *S. americanum*, and *Tridax procumbens* L. might be resistant to some herbicides. In Italy, Ciaccia et al. (2019) found *C. bursa-pastoris*, *D. eruroides*, *F. officinalis*, *L. amplixaule*, *S. media*, *U. urens*, *C. rotundus*, *P. oleracea*, and *A. retroflexus* in orange orchards. Morugán-Coronado et al. (2015) observed *Brachypodium retusum* (Pers.) P.Beauv. and *Cistus albidus* L. as the main species in an orange orchard, while Cerdà et al. (2019) found *Parietaria judaica* L., *Erigeron sumatrensis* Retz., *A. hybridus*, and *C. album* also in Spanish orange orchards.

Table 23. Main weed species in orange orchards in the Mediterranean Biogeographical area of the European Union.

ORANGE			
Family	Main weed species	Biogeographical area	References
Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus hybridus</i>	MED	Cerdà et al., 2019
	<i>Amaranthus retroflexus</i>	MED	Ciaccia et al., 2019, Lovelli et al., 2017
	<i>Chenopodium album</i>	MED	Cerdà et al., 2019

Asteraceae	<i>Erigeron bonariensis</i>	MED	Bastida et al., 2021
	<i>Erigeron canadensis</i>	MED	Bastida et al., 2021
	<i>Erigeron sumatrensis</i>	MED	Cerdà et al., 2019
Brassicaceae	<i>Capsella bursa-pastoris</i>	MED	Ciaccia et al., 2019
	<i>Diplotaxis eruroides</i>	MED	Ciaccia et al., 2019
Caryophyllaceae	<i>Stellaria media</i>	MED	Ciaccia et al., 2019
Cyperaceae	<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	MED	Ciaccia et al., 2019
Lamiaceae	<i>Lamium amplexicaule</i>	MED	Ciaccia et al., 2019
Papaveraceae	<i>Fumaria officinalis</i>	MED	Ciaccia et al., 2019
Poaceae	<i>Lolium rigidum</i>	MED	Montull & Torra, 2023
Portulacaceae	<i>Portulaca oleracea</i>	MED	Ciaccia et al., 2019
Urticaceae	<i>Parietaria judaica</i>	MED	Cerdà et al., 2019
	<i>Urtica urens</i>	MED	Ciaccia et al., 2019

MED=Mediterranean

Peach

Peach (*Prunus persica* (L.) Batsch) is a fruit consumed all over the world and has a large number of cultivars. It is composed of carbohydrates (sucrose, fructose, sorbitol and glucose), fibre, fatty acids, amino acids, organic acids (mainly malic and citric acid), minerals, vitamins, etc. (Bento et al., 2020). In addition to these compounds, they contain phytochemical compounds (carotenoids, phenols, flavonoids, anthocyanins, etc.) with antioxidant capacity, and which are considered beneficial to health (Ding et al., 2020). Like many other crops, possible uses for waste products derived from their production are being studied, e.g. waste products from juice production have a high content of fibre and polyphenols that could be used as functional foods (Rodríguez-González et al., 2018).

According to FAO, China is the largest producer of peaches and nectarines in the world with 16,817,068 Mg produced in 2022 (FAOSTAT, 2024). After China, four European countries stand out as major producers of peaches and nectarines worldwide. These are Italy, with 1,151,490 Mg, Turkey with 1,008,185 Mg, Greece with 894,510 Mg, and Spain with 870,720 Mg produced in 2022 (FAOSTAT, 2024).

Proper weed management is very important to minimise yield losses caused by weeds. A critical low weed period from flowering to 12 weeks later can increase crop yield, fruit size and number of fruits per plant (Buckelew et al., 2018). Orchard grass can cause yield losses of 24-37% depending on the peach cultivar (Tworkoski and Glenn, 2001).

In India, Sharma et al. (2024) found *L. arvensis*, *C. rotundus*, *B. pilosa*, and *O. latifolia* among other in peach orchards. Jia et al. (2017) compiled survey data obtained in 2015 in peach orchards, and observed that *E. canadensis*, *Plantago asiatica* L., *T. repens*, *D. ciliaris*, and *Rorippa palustris* Besser were the most common species. Tebeau et al. (2017) found a great diversity of weeds in peach orchards in USA, among which the most important were *C. arvensis*, *L. serriola*, *T. officinale*, *S. viridis*, *Festuca rubra* L. *L. perenne*, and *Trifolium* spp. In Spain, Juárez-Escario et al. (2017) found *B. catharticus*, *E. colonum*, *C. bursifolia*, and *S. adhaerens* in peach and nectarine orchards. Mia et al. (2020) found in Italian peach orchards *T. officinale*, *S. oleraceus*, *V. persica*, *T. repens* L., *C. dactylon*, *L. perenne*, and *E. crus-galli* as predominant weeds. Peach has a similar weed flora to apricot in Hungary.

Table 24. Main weed species in peach orchards in the Mediterranean Biogeographical area of the European Union.

PEACH			
Family	Main weed species	Biogeographical area	References
Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus retroflexus</i>	MED	Lovelli et al., 2017
Asteraceae	<i>Crepis bursifolia</i>	MED	Juárez-Escario et al., 2017
	<i>Erigeron bonariensis</i>	MED	Bastida et al., 2021
	<i>Erigeron canadensis</i>	MED	Bastida et al., 2021
	<i>Erigeron sumatrensis</i>	MED	Bastida et al., 2021
	<i>Sonchus oleraceus</i>	CONT	Mia et al., 2020
	<i>Taraxacum officinale</i>	CONT	Mia et al., 2020
Fabaceae	<i>Trifolium repens</i>	CONT	Mia et al., 2020
Plantaginaceae	<i>Veronica persica</i>	CONT	Mia et al., 2020
Poaceae	<i>Bromus catharticus</i>	MED	Juárez-Escario et al., 2017

<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	CONT	Mia et al., 2020
<i>Echinochloa colonum</i>	MED	Juárez-Escario et al., 2017
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	CONT	Mia et al., 2020
<i>Lolium perenne</i>	CONT	Mia et al., 2020
<i>Lolium rigidum</i>	MED	Montull and Torra, 2023
<i>Setaria adhaerens</i>	MED	Juárez-Escario et al., 2017

CONT=Continental; MED=Mediterranean

Vineyard

Grapevine (*Vitis vinifera* L.) is cultivated mainly for the production of table grapes and for winemaking. Their composition varies greatly between different types of cultivars, some intended for wine production and others for table grapes (Poni et al., 2018). Among the most valued compounds in grapes for consumption are sugars, phenolic compounds, anthocyanins, volatile compounds, carotenes, tocopherols and organic acids (Aubert and Chalot, 2018). Many of these compounds, such as polyphenols or flavonoids, in addition to being valuable for improving the organoleptic properties of the product, are attributed functional properties such as anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, etc. (Magrone et al., 2019). In addition, the waste products obtained as a result of grape processing can be used for other purposes such as the production of biofuel or biofertilisers (Ferjani et al., 2019), providing added value and favoring the circular economy.

China, with 12,672,896.21 Mg produced in 2022, is the world's largest grape producer, followed by three European countries, Italy, France, and Spain with 8,437,970, 6,199,950, and 5,902,040 Mg produced, respectively (FAOSTAT, 2024), positioning Europe as an important area for grape production. Another European country that stands out for grape production is Turkey, with 4,165,000 Mg produced in 2022 (FAOSTAT, 2024).

Weeds can compete with vines for light, water or nutrients and can cause yield losses of up to 37% (Pala et al., 2020b). In Turkey, *A. retroflexus*, *P. oleracea*, *S. nigrum*, *C. arvensis* L., *E. crus-galli*, *C. dactylon*, *L. rigidum*, or *A. sterilis* are some of the weeds found by Pala et al. (2020b). Sportelli et al. (2021) found *Erodium cicutarium* (L.) L'Hér., *M. chamomilla*, *M. sylvestris*, *E. canadensis*, *Aster squamatus* Hieron, *T. officinale*, *P. annua*, *V. persica*, *S. media*, *G. molle*, *L. arundinaceum*, *Bellis perennis* L., *C. bursa-pastoris*, *Euphorbia prostrata* Aiton, *D. sanguinalis*, *C. dactylon*, *P. oleracea*, and *Paspalum*

distichum L. in Italian vineyards. Fried et al. (2019b) determined that the ten most frequent weed species based on surveys conducted in vineyards in France were *C. arvensis*, *C. arvensis*, *S. vulgaris*, *D. eruroides*, *Geranium rotundifolium* L., *E. canadensis*, *T. officinale*, *Crepis sancta* (L.) Babc., *L. serriola*, and *S. oleraceus*, while Bopp et al. (2022) observed *S. media*, *C. arvensis*, *C. sancta*, *T. officinale*, *Cardamine hirsuta* L., *V. persica*, *L. multiflorum*, and *Rubia peregrina* L. among others. Guerra et al. (2022a) found that the predominant weeds in a Spanish vineyard were *Medicago minima* (L.) L., *Bromus madritensis* L., *L. amplexicaule*, *C. arvensis*, and *S. asper*, while they observed on other two vineyards *E. canadensis*, *C. rotundus*, *Lolium arundinaceum* (Schreb.) Darbysh., *E. prostrata*, *C. arvensis*, *B. madritensis*, and *S. asper* as the most abundant species (Guerra et al., 2022b). In the Atlantic bioregion of Spain, Muñoz et al. (2022) found *Oxalis pes-caprae* L., *Sonchus* sp., *C. rotundus*, *Bromus* sp., while in the vineyards of mediterranean bioregion, *C. album*, *D. eruroides*, *P. lanceolata*, *F. officinalis*, *S. arvensis*, *S. oleraceus*, *Bromus arvensis* L. among others. Also, Muñoz et al. (2022) found *T. officinale*, *D. eruroides*, *M. annua*, *C. arvensis*, *L. perenne*, and *C. dactylon* in an Italian vineyard.

The demarcation of the 22 wine regions in Hungary is based on their ecological differences. Since these ecological factors also significantly influence the weed flora, the composition of the weed flora in the plantations can differ significantly. Weed species with deep, intensively growing root systems cause problems in vineyard in Hungary. These represent competition for grapes. The monocotyledon *E. repens*, *C. dactylon*, *S. halepense*, *Poa pratensis* L., *Dactylis glomerata* L., *E. crus-galli*, *D. sanguinalis*, *Setaria* spp., *Bromus* spp. and the dicotyledon *E. canadensis*, *Amaranthus* spp., *Chenopodium* spp., *Atriplex* spp., *S. nigrum*, *L. serriola*, *E. cicutarium*, *G. parviflora*, *Melilotus* spp., *T. officinale*, *C. intybus*, *E. cyparissias*, *Lepidium draba* L., *Reseda lutea* L., *Plantago* spp., *Leontodon* spp., *Falcaria vulgaris* Bernh., *Achillea millefolium* L., *C. arvensis*, *C. arvensis*, *Solidago* spp., *Silene latifolia* subsp. *alba* (Mill.) Greuter & Burdet, *A. vulgaris*, *Trifolium* spp. dominate in Hungarian vineyards (Hunyadi et al., 2000; Knolmajer, 2023).

Table 25. Main weed species in vineyards in different Biogeographical areas of the European Union.

Vineyard			
Family	Main weed species	Biogeographical area	References
Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus</i> spp.	CONT, PAN	Gago et al., 2007; Hunyadi et al., 2000; Knolmajer, 2023

	<i>Chenopodium album</i> L.	CONT, STP, PAN	Gago et al., 2007; Penescu et al., 2017; Hunyadi et al., 2000; Knolmajer, 2023
	<i>Chenopodium murale</i> L.	MAC	SPB, 2023
Asteraceae	<i>Bidens pilosa</i> L.	MAC	SPB, 2023
	<i>Cirsium arvense</i> (L.) Scop.	STP, PAN	Penescu et al., 2017; Knolmajer, 2023
	<i>Erigeron bonariensis</i> L.	MAC	UTAD, 2023
	<i>Erigeron canadensis</i> L.	CONT, MAC, PAN	Gago et al., 2007; PIP, 2023; Knolmajer, 2023
	<i>Galinsoga parviflora</i> Cav.	MAC, PAN	PIP, 2023; Knolmajer, 2023
	<i>Helminthotheca echinoides</i> (L.) Holub	MAC	UTAD, 2023
	<i>Lactuca serriola</i> L.	MAC, PAN	SPB, 2023; Knolmajer, 2023
	<i>Sonchus oleraceus</i> L.	MAC	SPB, 2023
Caryophyllaceae	<i>Cerastium glomeratum</i> Thuill	CONT	Gago et al., 2007
	<i>Stellaria media</i> (L.) Vill.	CONT	Gago et al., 2007
Malvaceae	<i>Malva parviflora</i> L.	MAC	SPB, 2023
Plantaginaceae	<i>Veronica</i> spp.	CONT	Gago et al., 2007
Poaceae	<i>Avena barbata</i> Polt ex Link	MAC	SPB, 2023
	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers.	CONT, STP, PAN	Gago et al., 2007; Penescu et al., 2017; Hunyadi et al., 2000

	<i>Digitaria sanguinalis</i> (L.) Scop.	CONT, PAN	Gago et al., 2007; Knolmajer, 2023
	<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i> (L.) Beauv.	CONT, PAN	Gago et al., 2007 Hunyadi et al., 2000
	<i>Elymus repens</i> (L.) Gould.	STP, PAN	Penescu et al., 2017 Hunyadi et al., 2000
	<i>Poa annua</i> L.	CONT	Gago et al., 2007
Portulacaceae	<i>Portulaca oleracea</i> L.	CONT	Gago et al., 2007
Solanaceae	<i>Solanum nigrum</i> L.	MAC, PAN	SPB, 2023; Knolmajer, 2023

CONT=Continental; PAN=Pannonian; STP= Steppic, MAC=Macaronesian

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Herbicides in Use: Current Status and Perspectives in the Different Biogeographic Regions of Europe

Abstract

This review examines herbicide use in Europe, addressing their development, regulatory landscape, and environmental impacts. Herbicides have boosted agricultural productivity since the 20th century, but long-term use of single-action herbicides has led to resistant weeds. The shift to genetically modified herbicide-tolerant crops has raised environmental risks, affecting soil microbiota and increasing spray drift. The EU's rigorous herbicide approval process aims to protect environmental and human health. Nevertheless, the review assesses the EU's handling of the glyphosate controversy, calling for more transparent and independent research on health effects. The review underscores herbicides' adverse effects on biodiversity, resistant weeds, and non-target species, emphasizing sustainable weed management. Significant disparities in herbicide use across European regions reflect agronomic and regulatory factors, calling for sustainable farming practices. The review advocates reassessing Europe's chemical herbicide dependence, encouraging integrated weed management and policies that balance productivity with environmental protection for a sustainable agricultural future.

1. Introduction

Herbicides play a crucial role in modern agriculture by effectively controlling weeds and enhancing crop yields.¹ Introducing selective herbicides in the late 1940s gave farmers a new tool, allowing them to consider weed control more independently of the crop production system.² In fact, since its commercial introduction in 1974, glyphosate has become the dominant herbicide worldwide.³ However, the prolonged use of herbicides with the same mode of action has led to the selection of resistant weed populations⁴; although this issue is highly dependent on the specific herbicide mode of action, the integration of chemical control within other weed control methods, and the type of crop systems. This issue has been a concern for decades, with scientists predicting the emergence of herbicide-resistant weeds shortly after their introduction.⁵ In European countries, the use of glyphosate is massive in

woody-tree crops such as citrus, grapes, and olives due to its selectivity as it is directly applied to the weeds avoiding the crop canopy⁶. Reports show that fewer herbicides were applied during the first years of introducing herbicide-tolerant crops, with glyphosate replacing other herbicides.⁷ The observed decrease in bacterial and fungal count in soils where herbicides are applied compared to control soils corroborates the impact of prolonged herbicide usage on soil microbiota⁹, together with other agronomic practices like mineral fertilization⁹, or conventional tillage.¹⁰

The history of herbicide use and the main changes in weed management have been reviewed, highlighting the importance of understanding the impact of herbicides on agricultural practices.¹¹ Furthermore, the potential for life-history trade-offs associated with herbicide resistance has been examined across naturally occurring populations, emphasizing the need to understand the fitness of resistant populations.¹² It is also crucial to consider how herbicide resistance traits interact with other life-history traits at the population level to properly understand the fitness of resistant populations.¹³ Some research shows that the advantage of the resistance conferred by a mutation can sometimes be offset by a high fitness-cost penalty¹⁴; however, more research is needed to measure the dominance of the resistance cost in the evolution of resistance¹⁵, as many times such cost may not always express or will just express under certain ecological conditions.¹⁶

The use of herbicides in Europe has been a significant debate and concern, leading to increasingly strict regulations on herbicide use.¹⁷ The European Union has limited or banned several herbicides due to their potential toxicity to aquatic ecosystems.¹⁸ Additionally, there is political consensus in Europe for reducing herbicide use as much as possible.¹⁹ Concerns about the environmental impact of herbicides have led to the prohibition or complication of herbicide application in certain European regions²⁰, although other potential contaminant herbicide molecules are still in use or even re-registered, such as glyphosate. Furthermore, using environmentally friendly systems, such as zero chemical weeding and zero use of synthetic pesticides, is gaining traction in Mediterranean Europe, resulting in benefits for biodiversity and soil conservation.²¹ However, zero chemicals will probably result in a decrease of farmers' revenue. Maybe a reduction of 50% in the use of pesticides would involve deep changes in cultivation systems towards integrated production systems,²² more sustainable with both the environment and farmers' economy.

The impact of herbicide use on plant communities and habitats has been a subject of European research, with studies demonstrating adverse direct impacts on plants and habitats and indirect effects on wildlife.²³ The increased use of agrochemicals (herbicides and fertilizers) and changes in agricultural land use, especially in central and northwestern Europe, has led to the selection of a larger group of weeds adapted to habitats with intermediate fertility.²⁴ Moreover, the use of herbicides has been associated with the development of herbicide-resistant weed populations, which may be attributed to current agricultural practices and the increasing and repeated use of herbicides on a single site.²⁵ However, when farmers rotate both crops and the mode of action of herbicides, the development of herbicide-resistant weed populations is simplified.

In response to global changes and European herbicide policies, farmers are compelled to reduce herbicide use to limit its impact on human health and the environment.^{26,27} This reduction in herbicide use is also influenced by financial and environmental pressures, which limit the availability of alternative herbicides in the European Community Pesticide Review.²⁸ The introduction of genetically modified herbicide-tolerant crops in Europe has sparked considerable debate, with conflicting claims about their ecological consequences.²⁹

1.1. European Union Registration and Approval Process for Herbicides

The European Union (EU) has a stringent and complex registration and approval process for herbicides, which is considered a good model for global harmonisation.³⁰ The EU follows a Tier I risk assessment, revealing higher toxicity reduction for certain insecticides than herbicides and fungicides.³¹ The EU's regulatory system is considered one of the strictest globally, relying on complex but soft laws for pesticide regulation.³² The approval process involves a demanding process, user competency tests, maximum residue limits, and regular post-registration monitoring.³³ Additionally, integrating epidemiological data into pesticide risk assessment is crucial for the peer review of active substances for EU approval.³⁴

The EU's regulatory uncertainty is evident in the glyphosate controversy, leading to an extension of its authorization for another ten years despite opposition from the European Parliament, highlighting the need for independent research on the health effects of herbicides.³⁵ Furthermore, the EU risk assessment process requires studies on chronic and sublethal effects of pesticide-active substances on honeybees, emphasizing the focus on

environmental protection and safety.³⁶ The aforementioned authors reported 10 and 40 $\mu\text{g.kg}^{-1}$ of glyphosate in nectar and pollen collected by bees, respectively, among other 100 active substances, mainly insecticides, which makes reduction of use of synthetic active substances an essential strategy for future more sustainable agricultural fields.

The EU's regulation of biopesticides is also subjected to the same stringent regulations as synthetic active substances, contributing to increased consumer safety.³⁷ The EU also requires guidance to provide applicants and evaluators advice on generating and assessing the required data, reflecting the complexity of the registration process.³⁸ Moreover, the EU's annual report assesses pesticide residue levels in foods on the European market, demonstrating its commitment to food safety.³⁹

Therefore, the EU's registration and approval process for herbicides is stringent and demanding, focusing on environmental protection, safety, and consumer welfare. The process involves a comprehensive risk assessment, competency tests, and regular monitoring, reflecting the EU's commitment to ensuring the safety and efficacy of herbicides in agricultural practices.

In the European Union, this regulation is facilitated through a comprehensive authorization process involving collaborative efforts among three primary stakeholders: the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), the European Commission, and individual Member States (https://food.ec.europa.eu/plants/pesticides/approval-active-substances-safeners-and-synergists_en).⁴⁰

This process is structured into distinct steps, each serving a crucial function in ensuring the safety and efficacy of pesticide usage within the EU. Initially, companies seeking approval to use active substances submit comprehensive applications to the relevant Member State. These applications, encompassing a wealth of scientific data and studies, may pertain to introducing new active substances or the renewal/amendment of previously approved ones.

Following the submission, the Member State thoroughly evaluates the application, scrutinizing its scientific merits and potential risks. Subsequently, EFSA is responsible for conducting a peer review of the Member State's assessment. This review process, performed in collaboration with other Member States, entails a meticulous examination of the assessment report, culminating in providing scientific conclusions to the European

Commission. These conclusions, which may include recommendations for risk management measures, form the basis for decision-making regarding the authorization of the active substance.

Upon receiving EFSA's review, the European Commission, in conjunction with Member States, deliberates on whether to grant authorization for the active substance. This decision-making process involves the Commission's proposal for approval or rejection, followed by a vote by a special committee comprising Member State representatives. Typically, approval for new active substances is granted for ten years, while renewal applications may extend up to fifteen years.

Once an active substance receives authorization, companies can apply for market placement of pesticides containing the approved substance. This application delineates the pesticide's intended uses, including specific crops and application rates. The receiving Member State then evaluates the application, proposing maximum residue levels (MRLs) where necessary.

Should the proposed MRL align with existing legislation, the application should be advanced to the European Commission for consideration. However, if the proposed MRL deviates from established norms, EFSA will conduct a comprehensive assessment and provide its opinion to the Commission. Ultimately, the Commission decides whether to accept the proposed MRL, thereby determining the authorization status of the pesticide.

Upon acceptance, the Member State can authorize the pesticide, adhering to EU regulations which govern pesticide authorization. Notably, the EU operates under three distinct zones for pesticide authorization, facilitating mutual recognition among Member States with similar agricultural and environmental conditions.

After the authorization process, rigorous monitoring mechanisms are employed to ensure compliance with regulatory standards. Member States undertake comprehensive monitoring of pesticide usage, verifying adherence to specified conditions, such as application on designated crops and compliance with dosage limits. Additionally, an EU-wide program is implemented to monitor pesticide residues in food, with EFSA playing a pivotal role in collating and analyzing monitoring results.

EFSA compiles an annual report on pesticide residues in food, which may include proposals for revisions to maximum residue levels. The European Commission and Member States then

deliberate on these proposals, implementing necessary measures to uphold safety standards and mitigate potential risks associated with pesticide usage within the EU.

1.2. Environmental and Safety Considerations on Herbicides in Europe

Using herbicides in Europe has raised significant environmental and safety concerns, prompting regulatory measures and exploring alternative weed management strategies. Strict registration and environmental regulations have led to the loss of some herbicides in Europe, reflecting the region's commitment to environmental protection.⁵ However, the loss of a single herbicide, sometimes means losing the complete mode of action, as it recently happened in Spain, when the HRAC modes of action 22 and 23 were lost by only losing 2 herbicides diquat and chlorpropham respectively, and it can increase the risk of herbicide-resistance evolution. Weedy plant species that have evolved resistance to herbicides due to enhanced metabolic capacity to detoxify herbicides (metabolic resistance), posing threats to herbicide sustainability and global crop production⁴¹, are a major issue. Recent trends in herbicide regulation and registration include providing more detailed information to users to adjust rates according to prevailing environmental conditions and herbicide sensitivity, with the primary regulatory objective of promoting the application of products at minimum effective doses.⁴²

The impact of herbicides on aquatic ecosystems has also been a concern. A review concluded that a reliable herbicide hazard and risk assessment was necessary. An extensive catch-up must be made concerning macrophytes, the marine environment, and sediment as overlooked and understudied environmental compartments.¹⁸ Additionally, the ecological impact assessment of herbicides on aquatic floating vascular plants and freshwater species of phytoplankton has highlighted acute sensitivity and potential risks to these organisms.^{43, 44, 45;}

46

In response to these concerns in Europe, there is a growing interest in environmentally friendly systems, such as less use of synthetic pesticides or even zero chemical weeding, resulting in considerable benefits in terms of biodiversity and soil conservation.²¹ However, such mentioned management practices for weed control could reduce crop yields and increase both, the risk of herbicide-resistant weeds and soil erosion processes as mechanical weeding methods will become more important. The decreasing use of herbicides due to rising

resistance phenomena, the slow advance of the discovery of new modes of action, and more regulatory restrictions have led to the exploration of alternative weed management strategies⁴⁷, such as the use of different new mulch materials (paper, plastic, hydromulch, etc)⁴⁸, new thermal methods (laser diodes, micro-flames and capacity coupling of electric fields)⁴⁹, sensor-based mechanical methods (image analysis with camera, global navigation satellite systems, laser and ultrasonic systems, all combined with mechanical systems)⁵⁰, and the use of bioherbicides (natural compounds such as carvacrol, thymol, eugenol, p-cymene, citral, etc...)⁵¹.

2. Aim of work

This work aims to outline the present status of herbicides registered on the EU market and the consumption of herbicides in the years 2016-2021 in the selected European countries representing the eleven biogeographical regions of Europe (European Environment Agency, 2016, <https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/climate-change-impacts-and-vulnerability-2016>)⁵². Biogeographical regions of Europe are the hierarchical system in which geographical areas are categorized based on their biotas.⁵³ Europe is divided into eleven distinct biogeographical regions, i.e., Arctic, Boreal, Alpine, Continental, Atlantic, Pannonian, Steppic, Anatolian, Black Sea, Mediterranean, and Macaronesian. Biogeographical regionalization is needed to provide reference areas for large-scale ecological analyses and conservation and management practices.^{54, 55} In this regard, it is interesting to analyze differences in herbicide use, which can differ depending on the country's location, e.g., north to south, east to west. These differences correlate with the role and type of agricultural production and are also, among others, related to the environmental conditions.

3. Methods

The database of active substances, encompassing herbicides, insecticides, and fungicides authorized for being used within the European Union, was extracted from the EU pesticide database website (<https://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/pesticides/eu-pesticides-database/start/screen/active-substances>).⁵⁵ This resource details each chemical compound, including approval and expiration dates and human and environmental toxicity profiles. It also

indicates the EU member state/s where these substances are allowed. An initial screening aimed to distinguish herbicides from other pesticide categories within the vast inventory of 1,485 chemicals. This led to the exclusion of substances no longer approved for use, narrowing down to a refined selection. The selected approved herbicidal substances were catalogued with specific information, such as molecular formulas, harmonized chemical classifications according to EUROSTAT (Table 1 – The complete dataset detailing the herbicides is presented in Supplementary Table S1), HRAC/WSSA modes of action (<https://hracglobal.com>)⁵⁶, the state of herbicide resistance⁵⁷, and World Health Organization (WHO) hazard classes of herbicides.⁵⁸

Herbicide consumption data (in tons of active ingredients per country) and the total area of cropland (in hectares) for the period 2016 to 2021 were collected for a set of countries representing various European biogeographical regions, including Slovakia (Alpine), Poland (Continental), Italy (Mediterranean), Hungary (Pannonian), Belgium (Atlantic), Türkiye (Anatolian & Black-Sea), Romania (Steppic), Estonia (Boreal), and Iceland (Arctic). This information was sourced from FAOSTAT (<https://www.fao.org>)⁵⁹ and Eurostat (<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/data/database>)⁶⁰ (when FAOSTAT did not provide a complete dataset). A brief description of the agricultural characteristics of each of the countries, based on statistical data, is presented in Table 1. Additionally, herbicide consumption data were compiled for different chemical families as outlined by EUROSTAT (Table 2 - The complete dataset detailing the herbicides is presented in Supplementary Table S1), which enabled the calculation of each country's herbicide used per hectare of cropland. According to the FAO, cropland is defined as land allocated for the cultivation of crops, including arable land and permanent crops. By comparing this data with the information on the European Commission's "Pesticide Database – Active Substance" website (<https://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/pesticides/eu-pesticides-database/start/screen/active-substances>)⁵⁵, an analysis was conducted to ascertain the usage patterns of different chemical groups of herbicides in European bioregions.

Table 1. Characteristics of agriculture in the countries representing the biogeographical regions.

Country/Bioregion	Utilized agricultural area (ha)*	Arable (ha)*	Share of arable area in the utilized agricultural area (%)	Orchards (ha)**	Share of orchards in the utilized agricultural area (%)	Average farm area (ha)*	Main crops
Belgium/Atlantic	1 368 120	869 280	63.54	14 730	1.08	38.00	Sugar beets, chicory, flax, cereal grains and potatoes
Estonia/Boreal	975 320	692 860	71.04	5141	0.52	85.78	Winter wheat, spring barley, spring wheat, oilseed rape, oat
Hungary/Pannonian	4 921 740	4 027 970	81.84	36 292.48	0.74	21.21	Wheat, maize, sunflower, rape, vineyards, fruit trees and berries

Iceland/Arctic***	91 531	12 902	0.14	0	0	--	Forage crops, grass, barley, potatoes, turnips, carrots	
Italy/Mediterranean	12 041 230	7 197 650	59.78	1	389 829.43	11.54	14.5	Cereal grains, vine, olive, citrus fruits, fruit trees, vegetables, permanent meadows and pastures
Poland/Continental	14 749 240	11 147 160	75,58	167 314,99	1,13%	11,33	Winter wheat, oilseed rape, maize, apples	
Romania/Steppic	12 762 830	8 570 730	67,15	67 840,29	0,53	4,42	Winter wheat, oilseed rape, sunflower, maize, barley, soybean, apple, pear	
Slovakia/Alpine	1 862 650	1 325 330	71,15	2 321,44	0,12	94,89	Wheat, barley, maize, oil crops, potatoes, sugar beet, vineyards, fruit trees	

Turkey/Anatolian & Black Sea	38 089 000* ***	19 881 000*** *	52,20	3 694 255.7	15.43	6,1	Wheat, sugar beet, cotton, vegetables and fruit
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* EUROSTAT ⁶⁰

** This category consist of Dessert apple trees, Apple trees plantation for industrial processing, Dessert pear trees, Pear trees for industrial processing, Dessert peach and nectarine trees, Peach and nectarine trees for industrial processing (including group of Pavie), Apricot trees, Orange trees, Small citrus fruit trees, Lemon trees, Olive trees, Table grape vines

*** RML (2024). ¹⁰⁵ Data for year 2020.

**** FAOSTAT ⁵⁹

Table 2: Table of the herbicides allowed in Europe according to the EU pesticide database (<https://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/pesticides/eu-pesticides-database/start/screen/active-substances>⁵⁵). The table reports the active principle (herbicide), the Mode of Action [MoA – according to the Herbicide Resistance Action Committee (HRAC) and the Weed Science Society of America (WSSA)], the harmonised FAO classification, the main herbicide resistance cases reported till 2024, and the expiration approval (Exp. Approval). The complete dataset detailing the herbicides (i.e., European nations in which they are allowed, WHO hazard class, etc.) is presented in Supplementary Table S1.

Herbicide	MoA	Harmonised FAO classification	Herbicide resistance cases [Heap 2024⁵⁸]	Exp. approval
Clethodim		Cyclohexanedione herbicides	34 cases, 12 countries, 16 species	31/08/2026
Clodinafop		Aryloxyphenoxy-propionic herbicides	78 cases, 25 countries, 13 species	15/12/2025
Cycloxydim		Cyclohexanedione herbicides	26 cases, 10 countries, 9 species	31/08/2026
Cyhalofop-butyl	HRAC/WSSA 1	Aryloxyphenoxy-propionic herbicides	25 cases, 13 countries, 9 species	30/06/2032
Diclofop		Aryloxyphenoxy-propionic herbicides	87 cases, 20 countries, 13 species	31/08/2026
Fenoxaprop-P-ethyl		Aryloxyphenoxy-propionic herbicides	122 cases, 35 countries, 26 species	15/08/2025
Fluazifop-P-butyl		Aryloxyphenoxy-propionic herbicides	55 cases, 16 countries, 23 species	31/05/2026

Pinoxaden		Phenylpyrazole herbicides	60 cases, 18 countries, 16 species	30/06/2026
Propaquizafop		Aryloxyphenoxy-propionic herbicides	13 cases, 9 countries, 10 species	28/02/2027
Quizalofop-P-ethyl		Aryloxyphenoxy-propionic herbicides	40 cases, 15 countries, 20 species	28/02/2027
Amidosulfuron		Sulfonylurea herbicides	5 cases, 5 countries, 5 species	15/08/2025
Bensulfuron		Sulfonylurea herbicides	58 cases, 13 countries, 31 species	15/08/2026
Flazasulfuron		Sulfonylurea herbicides	5 cases, 3 countries, 4 species	31/07/2032
Florasulam		Anilide herbicides	36 cases, 17 countries, 23 species	31/12/2030
Foramsulfuron	HRAC/WSSA 2	Sulfonylurea herbicides	27 cases, 11 countries, 16 species	31/05/2035
Halosulfuron - methyl		Sulfonylurea herbicides	25 cases, 5 countries, 20 species	05/08/2025
Imazamox		Imidazolinone herbicides	74 cases, 18 countries, 43 species	31/01/2025
Iodosulfuron-methyl		Sulfonylurea herbicides	118 cases, 31 countries, 40 species	31/03/2032

Mesosulfuron-methyl	Sulfonylurea herbicides	89 cases, 24 countries, 26 species	30/06/2032
Metsulfuron-methyl	Sulfonylurea herbicides	84 cases, 18 countries, 40 species	31/03/2024
Nicosulfuron	Sulfonylurea herbicides	59 cases, 18 countries, 27 species	31/03/2027
Penoxsulam	Amide herbicides	29 cases, 13 countries, 14 species	15/05/2026
Propoxycarbazone	Triazolone herbicides	18 cases, 10 countries, 12 species	31/08/2032
Prosulfuron	Sulfonylurea herbicides	8 cases, 4 countries, 7 species	31/07/2024
Pyroxsulam	Amide herbicides	56 cases, 19 countries, 27 species	30/04/2025
Rimsulfuron (aka renriduron)	Sulfonylurea herbicides	17 cases, 9 countries, 12 species	15/08/2025
Sulfosulfuron	Sulfonylurea herbicides	22 cases, 12 countries, 14 species	31/12/2030
Thiencarbazone-methyl	Triazolone herbicides	6 cases, 4 countries, 5 species	30/09/2024
Thifensulfuron-methyl	Sulfonylurea herbicides	93 cases, 13 countries, 31 species	31/10/2031

Tribenuron metometuron)	(aka	Sulfonylurea herbicides	105 cases, 23 countries, 48 species	30/01/2034
Tritosulfuron		Sulfonylurea herbicides	1 case, 1 country, 1 species	15/07/2025
Pendimethalin		Dinitroaniline herbicides	11 cases, 5 countries, 6 species	30/11/2024
	HRAC/WSSA 3			
Propyzamide		Amide herbicides	6 cases, 2 countries, 2 species	30/06/2025
2,4-D		Phenoxy herbicides	47 cases, 16 countries, 25 species	31/12/2030
2,4-DB		Phenoxy herbicides	<i>Not available</i>	31/10/2032
Aminopyralid		Pyridinecarboxylic-acid herbicides	4 cases, 3 countries, 3 species	31/12/2024
Clopyralid		Pyridinecarboxylic-acid herbicides	4 case, 3 countries, 4 species	30/09/2036
	HRAC/WSSA 4			
Dicamba		Benzoic-acid herbicides	21 cases, 7 countries, 10 species	31/03/2027
Dichlorprop-P		Phenoxy herbicides	2 case, 1 country, 2 species	15/03/2025
Florpyrauxifen-benzyl		Pyridinecarboxylic-acid herbicides	2 cases, 2 species, 1 country	24/07/2029
Fluroxypyr		Pyridyloxyacetic-acid herbicides	6 cases, 3 countries, 4 species	31/12/2024

Halauxifen-methyl		Pyridinecarboxylic-acid herbicides	<i>Not available</i>	05/08/2025
MCPA		Phenoxy herbicides	17 cases, 9 countries, 13 species	15/08/2026
MCPB		Phenoxy herbicides	1 case, 1 country, 1 species	15/08/2026
Mecoprop-P		Phenoxy herbicides	3 case, 2 countries, 3 species	31/01/2024
Picloram		Pyridinecarboxylic-acid herbicides	5 cases, 3 countries, 5 species	15/02/2028
Quinmerac		Quinoline herbicides	<i>Not available</i>	31/07/2024
Triclopyr		Pyridyloxyacetic-acid herbicides	1 case, 1 country, 1 species	15/12/2024
Phenmedipham		Bis-carbamate herbicides	1 case, 1 country, 1 species	15/02/2025
Chlorotoluron		Urea herbicides	16 cases, 7 countries, 6 species	15/08/2026
Fluometuron	HRAC/WSSA 5	Urea herbicides	<i>Not available</i>	31/08/2024
Lenacil		Uracil herbicides	6 cases, 2 countries, 5 species	15/08/2025
Metobromuron		Urea herbicides	<i>Not available</i>	31/12/2024

Metribuzin		Triazinone herbicides	30 cases, 11 countries, 16 species	15/02/2025
Terbuthylazine		Triazine herbicides	6 cases, 3 countries, 5 species	31/12/2024
Bentazon		Thiadiazine herbicides	3 cases, 2 countries, 3 species	31/05/2025
	HRAC/WSSA 6			
Pyridate		Diazine herbicides	<i>Not available</i>	31/12/2030
Glyphosate	HRAC/WSSA 9	Organophosphorus herbicides	361 cases, 31 countries, 57 species	15/12/2033
Beflubutamid		Amide herbicides	<i>Not available</i>	31/10/2026
Diflufenican		Anilide herbicides	7 cases, 2 countries, 4 species	15/01/2026
	HRAC/WSSA 12			
Picolinafen		Pyridinecarboxamide herbicides	<i>Not available</i>	30/06/2031
Flurochloridone		//	<i>Not available</i>	15/03/2026
Clomazone	HRAC/WSSA 13	Unclassified herbicides	3 cases, 2 countries, 3 species	15/06/2025
Flumioxazin		Dicarboximide herbicides	2 cases, 1 country, 2 species	28/02/2037
	HRAC/WSSA 14			
Oxyfluorfen		Diphenyl ether herbicides	3 cases, 3 countries, 3 species	31/12/2024

Bifenox		Diphenyl ether herbicides	<i>Not available</i>	31/03/2027
Carfentrazone-ethyl		Triazolinone herbicides	5 cases, 4 countries, 4 species	31/07/2033
Pyraflufen-ethyl		Phenylpyrazole herbicides	2 cases, 1 country, 2 species	31/03/2031
Dimethenamid-P		Amide herbicides	1 case 1 country, 1 species	31/08/2034
Dimethachlor		Chloroacetanilide herbicides	<i>Not available</i>	15/10/2026
Ethofumesate		Benzofurane herbicides	1 case, 1 country, 1 species	31/10/2031
Flufenacet		Anilide herbicides	6 cases, 4 countries, 2 species	15/06/2025
Metazachlor	HRAC/WSSA 15	Anilide herbicides	<i>Not available</i>	31/10/2026
Napropamide		Amide herbicides	<i>Not available</i>	31/03/2027
Pethoxamid		Amide herbicides	<i>Not available</i>	30/11/2033
Prosulfocarb		Thiocarbamate herbicides	1 case, 1 country, 1 species	31/01/2027
Tri-allate		Thiocarbamate herbicides	12 cases, 3 countries, 2 species	31/03/2027

Isoxaflutole		Isoxazole herbicides	2 cases, 2 countries, 2 species	31/07/2034
Mesotrione	HRAC/WSSA 27	Triketone herbicides	16 cases, 3 countries, 4 species	31/05/2032
Sulcotrione		Triketone herbicides	<i>Not available</i>	30/11/2026
Tembotrione		Triketone herbicides	10 cases, 2 countries, 3 species	31/07/2024
Aclonifen	HRAC/WSSA 32	Diphenyl ether herbicides	<i>Not available</i>	31/10/2026

4. Overview of herbicides currently registered in the EU

As of February 2024, the registry of authorized herbicides includes 82 active substances (Table 2 and Supplementary Table S1). This inventory, organized according to a harmonized classification of pesticides (Table 2 and Supplementary Table S1), reveals a diverse composition; e.g., phenoxy hormone products account for 7.3%, triazines for 2.4%, and carbamates, uracil, and dinitroaniline derivatives represent 1.2% each (with one active substance per category). Furthermore, urea derivatives comprise 3.7% of the list, while sulfonylureas, notable for their significant representation, constitute 18.3%. A broad category labeled 'other herbicides' encompasses a heterogeneous collection of substances, making up 48.8% of the registry. These herbicides, according to acute risk to human health, are classified into three World Health Organization (WHO) hazard classes: 29% fall into class II, indicating moderate hazard; 31% into class III, denoting slight hazard; and a substantial 41% into class U, suggesting they are unlikely to pose an acute hazard under typical conditions of use.

4.1. Review of the mode of action (MoA) and herbicide resistance status

Under the updated HRAC/WSSA classification, twenty-six distinct modes of action groups encompass 359 herbicides (Table 3). In the 2024 compilation of herbicides authorized within the European Union, merely thirteen HRAC/WSSA groups are represented. Table 3 delineates the comprehensive inventory of herbicides, itemizing the total count alongside the subset registered within each HRAC/WSSA group. Additionally, it specifies the proportion of herbicides within each group accessible on the market in 2024, offering a clear overview of the current landscape in herbicide availability (Table 3).

The predominant category of herbicides documented comprises inhibitors of acetolactate synthase (ALS), categorized under the HRAC 2 group. This group consists of various chemical families, including sulfonylureas (15 herbicides), imidazolinones (1 herbicide), triazolinones (2 herbicides), and triazolopyrimidines (3 herbicides), collectively accounting for 26% of the active substances listed. ALS inhibitors are crucial for the biosynthesis of branched-chain amino acids such as valine, leucine, and isoleucine, impacting a wide range of plant species by impairing seedling growth. In mature plants, exposure may lead to various symptoms, including malformation, stunting, and diminished seed production. Remarkably, these herbicides exhibit such potency that they impact plant growth at levels below detectable standards of chemical analysis. The rapid emergence of resistance among weed species to ALS inhibitors is attributed to these compounds' singular mode of action and extended residual activity.⁶¹ Notably, all 21 active substances within the HRAC 2 group have been associated with the selection of herbicide-resistant weeds.⁵⁷ Resistance has developed across all substances listed, with iodosulfuron-methyl identified as the herbicide selected for resistance in the highest number of weed species—40 across 31 countries. Conversely, tritosulfuron has been linked to resistance in only one biotype of *Stellaria media* in Germany, despite its introduction in 2003 for post-emergence application against dicotyledonous weeds in cereals and maize.^{62,63} Obviously, within each HRAC mode of action group, the fact that an herbicide has been more times linked to weed resistance cases or a specific weed has evolved more times resistance to herbicides, depends on the use of this specific herbicide and the target weed, respectively. Perhaps, sulfonylureas herbicides and in particular iodosulfuron-methyl⁶⁴ are, after glyphosate, the most used herbicides in Europe, especially in cereals, as they can control a wide range of weeds⁶⁵ and takes part of numerous commercial herbicide mixtures. Therefore, the chance to find resistant weed species to iodosulfuron-methyl is higher than to other sulfonylurea herbicides.

The HRAC 4 group of herbicides, comprising 15 active substances and accounting for 18% of the list, is the second most prevalent category. This group is chemically diverse, including phenoxy-carboxylic acids (with six herbicides) and pyridine carboxylic acids

(with six herbicides as well), alongside three additional herbicides from varied chemical families: arylpicolinate (florpyrauxifen-benzyl), benzoic acids (dicamba), and quinoline carboxylic acids (quinmerac). Notably, this group spans several decades of herbicidal innovation. For instance, 2,4-D (2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid) emerged as the inaugural member of this group, marking its global commercial release in 1945. Conversely, florpyrauxifen-benzyl represents a modern addition, securing EU approval in 2019. Renowned for its efficacy in post-emergence applications, it effectively manages grasses, sedges, and broadleaf weeds in rice crops.⁶⁶ Another recent development within this group is halauxifen-methyl (Arylex™), formulated by Dow (Corteva Agriscience). This pyridine-type auxin-mimicking herbicide is remarkably potent against a spectrum of major broadleaf weeds, such as pigweed (*Amaranthus* sp.), henbit (*Lamium amplexicaule* L.), corn poppy (*Papaver rhoeas* L.), flixweed [*Descurainia sophia* (L.) Webb], and chickweed [*Stellaria media* (L.) Vill.], at extremely low dosages of 5–10 g ha⁻¹, and is versatile across multiple crops, notably winter wheat.⁶⁶ Despite the longstanding presence of auxin mimic herbicides on the market—nearly 70 years—global resistance cases are a total of 113, affecting 42 species. Of these, 25 species have demonstrated resistance to 2,4-D, indicating a relatively modest incidence of resistance across the globe.⁵⁷

Within the list, ten graminicides, constituting 12% of the total, are categorized under the HRAC 1 group as ACC-ase inhibitors. This group includes seven substances from the aryloxyphenoxypropionates chemical family (commonly referred to as FOPs), two from cyclohexanediones (DIMs), and one phenylpyrazole (DEN) - specifically, pinoxaden. Graminicides serve the purpose of controlling grassy weeds by inhibiting the activity of acetyl-CoA carboxylase (ACCase), a crucial enzyme in fatty acid biosynthesis. This blockage prevents the synthesis of lipids and secondary metabolites in susceptible plants, leading to compromised cell membrane integrity, leakage of metabolites, and eventual cell death. Notably, FOPs and DIMs were introduced to the agricultural market over four decades ago, while DEN entered the market more recently in 2006⁶⁷. Across all continents, each active substance within the HRAC 1 group has been associated with the development of resistant weed species, with fenoxaprop-P-ethyl identified as the

most prone herbicide to resistance selection.⁵⁷ However, not all HRAC group 1 herbicides induce the same mechanism of resistance to weeds. Some weed populations show metabolic resistance to some herbicides of this group, while they are sensitive to another active ingredients of the same group, and the same happens when target-site resistance is induced instead of metabolic resistance. This phenomenon is not exclusive of the HRAC group 1 herbicides, it can also happen for HRAC group 2, being the real problem when some weed populations show both types of resistance, target-site and metabolic.⁶⁸

The fourth most prevalent category in the list pertains to the HRAC/WSSA group 15, which comprises nine active substances accounting for 11% of the total. These substances function by inhibiting very-long-chain fatty acid (VLCFA) elongases and have been employed for over sixty years for the residual control of weeds in a variety of crops including maize, barley, oat, sorghum, soybean, sugarcane, wheat, and certain vegetable crops. Their primary mechanism of action is the inhibition of shoot development in susceptible weed species, thereby preventing their emergence and growth.⁶⁹ Three herbicides—dimetachlor, metazachlor, and pethoxamid—that have not been implicated in selecting resistant weed species are of special interest within this group. Pethoxamid is a relatively recent addition to the pesticide market, introduced in 2002. It is characterized as a pre- and early post-emergence chloroacetamide herbicide targeting certain grasses and broad-leaved weeds in crops such as maize, soybeans, and sunflower. As a systemic herbicide, pethoxamid is absorbed by plants' roots and young shoots.⁷⁰ Meanwhile, other herbicides in this group, such as ethofumesate (1994) and prosulfocarb (2011), have been linked to a limited number of resistant weed cases, with flufenacet and tri-allate presenting more significant resistance challenges. These herbicides mostly target grass weeds, which have a greater ability to evolve herbicide detoxification mechanisms mediated by enhanced metabolic activity, and very few cases of cross-resistance.⁷¹

Seven herbicides are classified under the HRAC/WSSA 5 group and two under HRAC/WSSA 6, both encompassing photosynthesis inhibitors at photosystem II (PSII)—specifically, the serine 264 binders in group 5, and the histidine 215 binders in group 6.

Historically, these groups were amalgamated under the HRAC classifications C1, C2, and C3, as general photosynthesis inhibitors at PSII. They have been delineated into groups 5 (comprising the former C1 and C2) and 6 (previously C3) due to the absence of demonstrated target site cross-resistance between these categories (HRAC Global, 2024). This distinction underscores the indiscriminate nature of PSII targeting by these herbicides.⁷² Within HRAC/WSSA 5, the listed herbicides span several chemical classes including ureas (chlorotoluron, fluometuron, metobromuron), uracils (lenacil), triazines (terbutylazine), triazinones (metribuzin), and phenyl-carbamates (phenmedipham). Meanwhile, HRAC/WSSA 6 features phenyl-pyridazines (pyridate) and benzothiadiazinones (bentazone). Both groups are selective, sparing crops while controlling weeds, and can be applied to either soil or foliage. Due to the abundance of binding sites in photosynthetic tissues, these herbicides can be used at higher rates. Upon exposure to full sunlight, treated plant leaves exhibit rapid wilting and death within days.⁷² Notably, fluometuron, metobromuron, and pyridate from these groups have not been linked to any weed resistance phenomena. Resistance is generally rare among these herbicides, with metribuzin and chlorotoluron recording the highest incidences of resistance cases, 30 and 16 respectively.

Group HRAC/WSSA 14 consists of five herbicides: carfentrazone-ethyl (N-phenyl triazolinones), flumioxazin (N-phenylphthalimides), pyraflufen ethyl (phenylpyrazoles), oxyfluorfen, and bifenox (diphenylethers), which act by inhibiting protoporphyrinogen IX oxidase (Protox). This enzyme is crucial for converting protoporphyrinogen IX to protoporphyrin IX (Proto), with inhibition leading to uncontrolled substrate autooxidation and Proto accumulation. The resultant blockage of the porphyrin pathway halts chlorophyll synthesis, causing light-dependent damage (photo-bleaching) directly tied to Proto accumulation levels.⁷³ These herbicides are approved for pre-emergence use to manage broadleaf weeds across various agricultural and horticultural settings. Among them, resistance occurrences are rare, with bifenox—introduced in the early 1970s—noting no confirmed resistance instances.⁵⁷ Most of the herbicides in this group are contact herbicides. Oxyfluorfen is soil applied, and weeds die when trespassing on the soil surface when they try to emerge. On the contrary, carfentrazone and pyraflufen

ethyl are foliar applied against dicot weeds, and they can also be used to desiccate potato leaves just after harvesting time.

In the classification of herbicides, HRAC/WSSA 12 designates phytoene desaturase inhibitors, represented by four herbicides: diflufenican and picolinafen (pyridinecarboxamides), beflubutamid (phenyl ethers), and fluorochloridone (pyrrolidine). These herbicides disrupt carotenoid biosynthesis in plants, leading to plant bleaching. Introduced commercially in the early 1970s, phytoene desaturase inhibitors comprise only a small fraction of the herbicides used in crop production.⁷⁴ Beflubutamid, a newer addition to this class, was introduced in 2018.⁷⁵ The resistance profile for these four herbicides is notable, with no resistance cases reported for picolinafen, fluorochloridone, and beflubutamid.⁵⁷ Diflufenican, however, has been linked to seven cases of weed resistance.^{76, 77, 78}

Following in sequence, HRAC/WSSA 27 encompasses inhibitors of *p*-hydroxyphenyl pyruvate dioxygenase (HPPD inhibitors), a group discovered through serendipitous observations of weed growth.⁷⁹ HPPD inhibitors block the formation of homogentisic acid, an essential precursor for plastoquinone and vitamin E, making them highly effective for selective pre-emergence and, in certain cases, post-emergence control of a broad spectrum of broadleaf and grass weeds in maize and rice. This efficacy has sparked interest in developing transgenic crops resistant to these herbicides.⁸⁰ The group includes three triketones—mesotrione, sulcotrione, and tembotrione—and one isoxazole, isoxaflutole, with a relatively low incidence of weed resistance reported.⁵⁷

In the group HRAC/WSSA 3, there are only two registered herbicides: propyzamide (chemical family benzamides) and pendimethalin (chemical family dinitroanilines). The HRAC/WSSA group 3 comprises herbicides that inhibit microtubule assembly by targeting tubulin proteins in plants and protists, and are called anti-cytoskeletal herbicides.⁸¹ They are used as pre-emergence herbicides to control various weed species. Both propyzamide and pendimethalin have been present on the pesticide market for decades; however, up-to-date, there are only 11 cases of herbicide resistance to pendimethalin and only six cases (2 countries and 2 species) to propyzamide.^{57, 82}

Glyphosate represents HRAC/WSSA group 9, inhibitors of enolpyruvyl shikimate phosphate synthase (EPSPS), an enzyme in the shikimate pathway that is essential for the biosynthesis of aromatic amino acids (phenylalanine, tryptophan, and tyrosine) in plants, fungi, microorganisms, and parasites.⁸³ Glyphosate, a superior herbicide, was firstly commercialized in 1974, and became a highly successful non-selective herbicide before the introduction of glyphosate-tolerant crops.^{84,85,86} Since then, the use of glyphosate significantly increased, resulting in recent environmental, health, and safety risks.^{87, 87} Until now, fifty-seven weed species in 31 countries have evolved resistance to this herbicide, with 361 cases of resistance.⁵⁷ Due to a massive use, glyphosate, endangers many nontarget organisms in the natural environment, comprising both soil and water.⁸⁹ However, the glyphosate market aims for a positive forecast until 2035⁸⁹ because it is a very effective herbicide, easy to manage, and unexpensive.

Clomazone, from the chemical family isoxazolidinones, is the only representative of HRAC/WSSA group 13, inhibitors of deoxy-d-xylulose phosphate synthase (DOXP). The DOXP is the first rate-limiting enzyme involved in the 2-C-methyl-D-erythritol 4-phosphate (MEP) pathway for terpenoid biosynthesis.⁹⁰ Clomazone was developed in the early 1980s, a soil-applied, pre-emergence herbicide. It is used against broadleaf and grassy weeds. It is widely used for weed control in canopies of soybean, cotton, sugar cane, corn, rice, tobacco, and various vegetable crops. It is generally accepted that clomazone prevents the accumulation of chloroplast pigments and plastidic isoprene evolution.^{91,92} Despite a long clomazone's presence on the market, it has only three cases of selected resistant weeds, one from Australia (1982) and two recent - 2008 and 2020 from the USA.⁵⁷

Aclonifen is a unique diphenyl ether herbicide authorized for agronomic use in Europe in 1983. It is the only representative in the new group of solanesyl diphosphate synthase inhibitors HRAC/WSSA 32. Aclonifen is categorized as an inhibitor of pigment biosynthesis with an unknown target and is used agronomically for pre-emergence control of monocot and dicot weeds in potato, sunflower lentils, and chickpea cultivation.⁹³ Presently, there are no records for weed resistance to aclonifen.⁵⁷

Table 3. Number of herbicides in total and registered in 2024 for each HRAC/WSSA group.

Mode of action	Group number	Total	Registered 2024	in %
Inhibition of acetyl CoA carboxylase	1	21	10	47.6
Inhibition of acetolactate synthase	2	58	21	36.2
Inhibition of microtubule assembly	3	18	2	11.1
Auxin mimics	4	24	15	62.5
Inhibition of photosynthesis at PSII - serine 264 binders	5	75	7	9.3
Inhibition of enolpyruvyl shikimate phosphate synthase	9	1	1	100
Inhibition of glutamine synthetase	10	2	//	//
Inhibition of phytoene desaturase	12	7	4	57.1
Inhibition of deoxy-d-xylulose phosphate synthase	13	2	1	50
Inhibition of protoporphyrinogen oxidase	14	30	5	16.7
Inhibition of very long-chain fatty acid synthesis	15	43	9	20.9

Inhibition of dihydropteroate synthase	18	1	//	//
Auxin transport inhibitor	19	2	//	//
PS I electron diversion	22	4	//	//
Inhibition of microtubule organisation	23	6	//	//
Uncouplers	24	6	//	//
Inhibition of hydroxyphenyl pyruvate dioxygenase	27	14	4	28.6
Inhibition of dihydroorotate dehydrogenase	28	1	//	//
Inhibition of cellulose synthesis	29	6	//	//
Inhibition of fatty acid thioesterase	30	2	//	//
Inhibition of serine-threonine protein phosphatase	31	1	//	//
Inhibition of solanesyl diphosphate synthase	32	1	//	//
Inhibition of homogentisate solanesyltransferase	33	1	//	//
Inhibition of lycopene cyclase	34	1	1	100

Auxin mimics/inhibition of cellulose synthesis	4/29	1	//	//
Inhibition of photosynthesis at PSII - histidine 215 binders/uncouplers	6/24	3	2	66.7
Unknown	//	28	//	//
In total		359	82	22.8

5. Herbicides' Use in Countries Representing European Biogeographic Regions.

Agricultural production across European biogeographic regions directly correlates with pedoclimatic and agroeconomic conditions, significantly influencing herbicide usage patterns, including consumption rates from various FAO groups (<https://www.fao.org>).⁵⁹ Table 4 delineates these relationships, presenting the average herbicide usage per hectare of cropland. Notably, between 2016 and 2021, the Arctic bioregion reported the lowest herbicide application rates (Table 4). In contrast, the Atlantic bioregion experienced the highest levels of herbicide usage, closely followed by the Continental bioregion (Table 4). This variance underscores the impact of regional agricultural practices and environmental conditions on herbicide consumption trends.

Table 4. Agricultural use of herbicides in kg per hectare of cropland in 2016-2021 for European bioregions represented by selected countries.

Bioregions/Country	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	Mean
Atlantic/Belgium	2.588	2.717	3.028	2.651	2.195	2.761	2.657
Boreal/Estonia	0.864	0.674	0.621	0.733	0.484	0.861	0.706

Pannonian/Hungary	1.018	0.949	0.850	0.870	1.019	1.016	0.954
Arctic/Iceland	0.23	0.15	0.15	0.06	0.04	0.05	0.113
Mediterranean/Italy	0.792	0.746	0.751	0.914	1.040	0.587	0.805
Continental/Poland	1.133	1.209	1.001	1.025	1.111	1.253	1.122
Steppic/Romania	0.556	0.612	0.568	0.428	0.464	0.428	0.510
Alpine/Slovakia	0.612	0.646	0.665	0.674	0.674	0.644	0.653
Anatolian & Black Sea/Turkey	0.148	0.507	0.644	0.310	0.572	0.566	0.458

Source: own elaboration based on data from FAOSTAT⁵⁹ and EUROSTAT⁶⁰

Table 5 illustrates trends in herbicide usage, which have shifted notably in recent years, displaying varying patterns across different countries that represent distinct biogeographical regions. This variability can be attributed to modifications in the European Union's roster of registered herbicides, which has been progressively decreasing. Throughout the six years under review, each bioregion—denoted here as bioregion=country—experienced a reduction in herbicide use compared to the previous year on at least one occasion (Table 5). The Pannonian and Alpine regions demonstrated a relatively stable pattern of herbicide application, with fluctuations of approximately 10% during the period analysed. Conversely, other bioregions exhibited more pronounced variability in herbicide consumption. Particularly noteworthy is the Anatolian and Black Sea bioregion, which saw a remarkable 236% increase in herbicide use in 2017 (Table 5). It is essential to acknowledge that variations in herbicide consumption are significantly influenced by the weather conditions prevailing during specific growing seasons and the inherent characteristics of agricultural production within each bioregion.

Table 5. Year-to-year change (%) in total herbicide use for agricultural purposes in 2016-2021 for European bioregions represented by selected countries (previous year = 100%).

Source: own elaboration based on data from FAOSTAT⁵⁹ and EUROSTAT⁶⁰

Bioregion/Country:	Change in herbicides use (%). previous year = 100%					
	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Atlantic/Belgium	X	3.38	13.37	-11.75	-16.48	25.92
Boreal/Estonia	X	-23.40	-7.44	19.28	-33.76	79.50
Pannonian/Hungary	X	-6.78	-10.44	2.13	9.19	2.19
Arctic/Iceland	X	-33.33	0.00	-62.50	-40.00	31.11
Mediterranean/Italy	X	-4.98	-0.03	23.93	14.46	-43.73
Continental/Poland	X	7.59	-16.73	2.76	9.62	12.06
Steppic/Romania	X	9.59	-5.44	-22.65	2.81	-6.64
Alpine/Slovakia	X	5.27	3.30	1.43	-0.11	-5.87
Anatolian & Black Sea/Turkey	X	236.05	26.23	-52.04	85.09	0.18

Figures 1-10 offer an in-depth examination of the variation in herbicide application rates (expressed in kg per hectare of cropland) across various European bioregions and countries from 2016 to 2021. These analyses draw on data from FAOSTAT and employ the harmonized classification of herbicides, as detailed in Table 2, for those herbicides approved for use in 2024.

Phenoxy hormone herbicides, known for their complex action mechanisms similar to auxins (plant growth hormones), influence cellular division, enhance phosphate metabolism, and alter nucleic acid metabolism. Their primary application is controlling broadleaf weeds across various crops, including wheat, corn, and rice⁹⁴. Functioning as hormone mimics, these herbicides elevate the weed's hormone levels beyond typical growth thresholds, thereby inhibiting weed growth and development, particularly in dicotyledonous species.⁹⁵ From 2016 to 2021, the Continental and Atlantic bioregions reported the highest usage rates of phenoxy hormone herbicides, averaging 0.13 and 0.16 kg per hectare, respectively (Figure 1). Notably, their importance has declined in the Anatolian, Black Sea, and Steppic regions since 2019. Conversely, their application has remained relatively stable across other bioregions, with a notable increase of approximately 12% observed in the Continental region since 2019 (Figure 1).

As of 2024, the registry of approved herbicides lists only six phenoxy hormone herbicides, all categorized under the HRAC/WSSA group 4. Among these, one herbicide is set to expire by the end of January 2024, while the others are approved until 2026, 2030, or 2032 (Table 2 and Supplementary Table S1).

Figure 1. The use of phenoxy hormone herbicides, measured in kilograms per hectare of cropland from 2016 to 2021 across countries representing selected biogeographical regions of Europe. Notably, data for the Anatolian and Black Sea regions for 2016 and for the Boreal region for 2016 and 2017 are absent. This analysis is based on data meticulously compiled from FAOSTAT (<https://www.fao.org>)⁵⁹ and Eurostat (<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/data/database>)⁶⁰, representing a novel contribution by the authors. The bioregions under consideration are delineated by the following countries: Atlantic (Belgium), Boreal (Estonia), Pannonian (Hungary), Arctic (Iceland), Mediterranean (Italy), Continental (Poland), Steppic (Romania), Alpine (Slovakia), and Anatolian & Black Sea (Turkey). This geographic categorization allows for a

comprehensive analysis of phenoxy hormone herbicide usage trends across diverse European agricultural landscapes.

According to the Food and Agriculture Organization's classification (WHO, 2022)⁵⁹, triazines are defined by their structural composition of six-membered rings containing three nitrogen atoms. This structural feature, indicated by the prefix "tri-" for three and "azine" for a nitrogen-containing ring, characterises the heterocyclic nature of triazines. As potent inhibitors of photosynthetic electron transport, triazine herbicides effectively restrict the oxidation of the quinone acceptor (QA), thereby impeding electron flow from photosystem II (PSII) to photosystem I (PSI) and ultimately inhibiting photosynthesis. This action results in a reduced maximum quantum yield, denoted as the F_v/F_m ratio.^{96, 97, 98} Furthermore, triazines compromise the turnover and stability of the D1 protein, essential for photosystem II's repair mechanism, necessitating its replacement.⁹⁹

Between 2016 and 2021, triazine herbicides were predominant in the Atlantic bioregion, with an average usage rate of 0.26 kg per hectare of cropland (Figure 2). Conversely, in other bioregions such as the Alpine, Mediterranean, and Steppic, their usage averaged below 0.05 kg per hectare. Notably, the Continental and Pannonian bioregions have observed an uptick in triazine usage since 2020, with rates approximately 70% lower than those in the Atlantic bioregion, averaging only 0.08 and 0.07 kg per hectare. In contrast, the Anatolian and Black Sea, Boreal, and Arctic bioregions have employed triazines only sparingly, with usage rates less than 0.004 kg per hectare or not at all (Figure 2). As of the 2024 registry, only two triazine herbicides, terbuthylazine and metribuzin, classified under HRAC/WSSA 5, remain authorized, with their approvals set to expire in December 2024 and February 2025, respectively (Table 2 and Supplementary Table S1).

Figure 2. The use of phenoxy triazines, measured in kilograms per hectare of cropland from 2016 to 2021 across countries representing selected biogeographical regions of Europe. No data are available for Anatolian and Black Sea 2016 and Boreal 2016. Source and bioregions: As shown in Figure 1.

According to the Food and Agriculture Organization (<https://www.fao.org>)⁵⁹, amide herbicides exhibit many biological properties. Similar to triazine herbicides, those belonging to the amide group were notably more popular in the Atlantic bioregion than others. From 2016 to 2021, their average application rate in the Atlantic was 0.37 kg per hectare (Figure 3). This use significantly outpaced the Alpine and Continental bioregions,

where amide herbicide application was approximately half of the Atlantic bioregion application. Moreover, it was roughly five to six times greater than in the Mediterranean and Pannonian bioregions. Notably, these herbicides saw scant use over the six years analysed in the Anatolian, Black Sea, and Arctic bioregions (Figure 3). The 2024 registry of herbicides lists 12 substances categorized under amides and anilides, scheduled for approval expirations between 2025 and 2027 (Table 2 and Supplementary Table S1).

Figure 3. Use of amides, measured in kilograms per hectare of cropland, from 2016 to 2021 across countries representing selected biogeographical regions of Europe. No data

is available for Anatolian & Black Sea 2016, Arctic 2017, Boreal 2016, and Pannonian 2018. Source and bioregions: like in Figure 1.

Carbamates, defined as carbamic acid esters¹⁰⁰, exhibited distinct use patterns across various European bioregions. In the Atlantic bioregion, carbamates were applied at the highest average rate of 0.13 kg per hectare of cropland, although this trend declined in the last years (Figure 4). Conversely, there was an uptick in the use of carbamates in the Continental bioregion, contrasting with the Alpine bioregion, where their use noticeably decreased in 2021 (Figure 4). Between 2016 and 2021, the Alpine and Continental bioregions reported low average carbamate applications of 0.02 kg and 0.05 kg per hectare of cropland, respectively (Figure 4). Meanwhile, the Mediterranean region witnessed only marginal use of these herbicides, averaging 0.005 kg per hectare (Figure 4). As of the 2024 registry, carbamates in the list of authorized herbicides are solely represented by phenmedipham (classified under HRAC/WSSA group 5), which is set to expire in 2025 (Table 2 and Supplementary Table S1).

Figure 4. Use of carbamates, measured in kilograms per hectare of cropland, from 2016 to 2021 across countries representing selected biogeographical regions of Europe. No data is available for Anatolian & Black Sea 2016, 2018, 2021, Arctic 2016, 2017, 2018, Boreal 2016, and Pannonian 2016—source and bioregions, like in Figure 1.

Dinitroanilines, a chemical class originating from both aniline and dinitrobenzenes, function as antimetabolic agents by disrupting microtubule polymerization and stability through their interaction with tubulin heterodimers.¹⁰¹ In European agriculture, spanning the biogeographical regions from 2016 to 2021, herbicides belonging to the dinitroaniline category were deployed in relatively modest quantities (Figure 5). Notably, the Atlantic bioregion reported the highest use, averaging 0.096 kg per hectare of cropland (Figure 5).

A significant observation was made in 2017, where all bioregions, except the Mediterranean and Alpine regions, experienced a marked reduction in dinitroaniline application rates (Figure 5). However, after this decline, the use of these herbicides began to increase, eventually stabilising through to 2021 (Figure 5). The currently authorized herbicide registry lists pendimethalin as the sole dinitroaniline, slated for approval by the end of November 2024 (Table 2 and Supplementary Table S1). This trend underscores a cautious approach to dinitroaniline utilisation across Europe, reflecting an adaptive management strategy in response to evolving agricultural and regulatory landscapes.

Figure 5. Use of dinitroanilines, measured in kilograms per hectare of cropland, over the years 2016 to 2021 across countries representing selected biogeographical regions of Europe. No data for Anatolian and Black Sea 2016, Arctic 2016, 2017, 2018, and Pannonian 2020, 2021 is available—source and bioregions, like in Figure 1.

Urea derivatives experienced higher use within two specific bioregions - Atlantic and Continental - with discernible trends observed from 2016 to 2021 (Figure 6). In the Continental bioregion, use remained stable, averaging 0.09 kg per hectare of cropland. Conversely, the Atlantic bioregion witnessed a fluctuating pattern; after experiencing a decrease from 2017 to 2020, there was a notable resurgence of their use in 2021 (Figure

6). The average application rate of these herbicides in the Atlantic region over the six-year period was 0.12 kg per hectare of cropland (Figure 6). In comparison, use in other bioregions was relatively minimal, ranging from 0.001 to 0.02 kg per hectare of cropland (Figure 6). As of 2024, urea derivatives listed in the registry of herbicides are embodied by three specific compounds: chlorotoluron (expiration year: 2026), fluometuron (expiration year: 2024), and metobromuron (expiration year: 2024) (Table 2 and Supplementary Table S1). Chlortoluron (3-(3-chloro-p-tolyl)-1,1-dimethyl urea), developed by Ciba Geigy in 1969, is widely used in to control grass weed in cereal, cotton, poppy and fruit crops.¹⁰² Fluometuron was introduced as a commercial chemical in 1960 by Ciba-Geigy AG under the trademark Cotoran; it has been widely used to control broadleaf weeds and grasses on agricultural crops e.g., cotton and sugarcane.¹⁰³

Figure 6. Use of urea derivatives, measured in kilograms per hectare of cropland, from 2016 to 2021 across countries representing selected biogeographical regions of Europe.

No data for Anatolian & Black Sea 2016, Boreal 2017, 2018, and Pannonian 2018, 2019 is available—source and bioregions, like in Figure 1.

Sulfonylurea herbicides, known as meristematic inhibitors with foliar and soil activity, control broadleaf weeds more efficiently than grasses. They achieve this by disrupting the biosynthesis of the amino acids valine, isoleucine, and leucine, pivotal components in plant growth.¹⁰⁴ Over the period from 2016 to 2021, sulfonylureas demonstrated a marked increase in significance within the Steppic bioregion, where their application averaged 0.022 kg per hectare of cropland (Figure 7). In contrast, their utilisation across the Alpine, Continental, Mediterranean, and Atlantic bioregions maintained a consistent average, ranging from 0.006 to 0.013 kg per hectare during the same period (Figure 7). The FAOSTAT database indicates that the application of sulfonylurea herbicides was considerably less prevalent in the Arctic and Boreal bioregions, with uses ranging between 0.0001 and 0.002 kg per hectare of cropland (Figure 7).

The 2024 herbicide registry lists 15 sulfonylurea compounds. Notably, two of these, metsulfuron-methyl and prosulfuron, are registered until 2024 (Table 2 and supplementary Table S1). The remaining compounds, including amidosulfuron, halosulfuron-methyl, and rimsulfuron, have expiration dates extending into 2025 and beyond, indicating a sustained reliance on and regulatory approval for using sulfonylurea herbicides in agricultural practices (Table 2 and Supplementary Table S1).

Figure 7. The use of sulfonylureas, measured in kilograms per hectare of cropland from 2016 to 2021 across countries representing selected biogeographical regions of Europe. No data is available for Anatolian & Black Sea 2016 and Boreal 2016, 2018 - source and bioregions, like in Figure 1.

Bipyridyls constitute a family of chemical compounds characterized by two pyridyl rings. Pyridine, an aromatic nitrogen-containing heterocycle, can form complexes with most transition metals. These herbicides' action mechanism involves positive ions, which are naturally dissociated and then reduced by photosynthesis to form stable free radicals. Subsequently, these free radicals are oxidised to regenerate the original ion and produce

hydrogen peroxide, destroying plant tissue. The application of bipyridyls has been notably significant in the Atlantic and Pannonian bioregions; however, there has been a marked decline since 2019 (Figure 8). Specifically, the average application rates of these herbicides were recorded at 0.05 and 0.03 kg per hectare of cropland in the Atlantic and Pannonian regions, respectively (Figure 8). As of 2024, no bipyridyl herbicides are registered for use (Table 2 and Supplementary Table S1).

Figure 8. Bipyridyls, measured in kilograms per hectare of cropland, were used from 2016 to 2021 across countries representing selected biogeographical regions of Europe. No data is available for Anatolian & Black Sea 2016 and Pannonian 2021—source and bioregions, like in Figure 1.

Uracil herbicides decrease photosynthesis by inhibiting the Hill reaction, similarly to ureas and triazines. Typically applied to soil, they are absorbed and transported within

plants via the transpiration stream. Notably, the Atlantic bioregion experienced a significant surge in the use of uracil herbicides, with a recorded increase of approximately 220% per hectare of cropland in 2021 compared to 2016 (Figure 9). The average application rates in the Alpine and Continental bioregions were 0.002 kg and 0.004 kg per hectare of cropland, respectively (Figure 9). Conversely, in the Mediterranean, Anatolian, Black Sea, and Steppic bioregions, the use of uracil herbicides was comparatively lower, averaging around 0.001 kg per hectare of cropland (Figure 9). Data on the use of this group of herbicides were largely unavailable for the Pannonian and Arctic bioregions for most of the years studied (Figure 9). As of 2024, lenacil stands as the sole uracil herbicide registered, with its approval set to expire in August 2025 (Table 2 and Supplementary Table S1).

Figure 9. The use of uracil herbicides, measured in kilograms per hectare of cropland from 2016 to 2021 across countries representing selected biogeographical regions of Europe. No data is available for Anatolian & Black Sea 2016, Arctic 2016, 2017, 2018,

Boreal 2016, and Pannonian 2016, 2017, 2018, and 2019—source and bioregions, like in Figure 1.

Within the FAO classification (<https://www.fao.org>)⁵⁹, the "other herbicides" category encompasses diverse chemical classes, among which glyphosate's significant contribution to agricultural productivity stands out. According to FAOSTAT data, this group's herbicides have been deployed across all bioregions, with the Atlantic bioregion witnessing the most substantial use, averaging 1.46 kg per hectare of cropland—more than double of the rate observed in other regions (Figure 10). From 2016 to 2021, the application of these herbicides remained relatively consistent, except in the Mediterranean bioregion, where a noticeable decline in their use was recorded in 2021 (Figure 10). The average application rates in other bioregions ranged from 0.33 to 0.59 kg per hectare, while the Arctic bioregion experienced minimal usage, marked by an application rate of merely 0.006 kg per hectare (Figure 10). Notably, the 2024 registry of authorized herbicides identifies nearly half of the entries - 40 in total - as belonging to this "other" classification (Table 2 and Supplementary Table S1).

Figure 10. Other herbicides in kilograms per hectare of cropland used from 2016 to 2021 across countries representing selected biogeographical regions of Europe. Anatolian & Black Sea 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021, Boreal 2016, Pannonian 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021 and Steppic 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021 - no data available. Source and bioregions: like in Figure 1.

Consolidating the data on herbicide use across various European bioregions, as represented by selected countries from 2016 to 2021, the consumption patterns of herbicides, as measured in kilograms per hectare of cropland, reveal a predominant use within the Atlantic region across nearly all groups. The sole exception is observed with

Sulfonylureas, where the average use per hectare of cropland surpassed that of the Atlantic region in the Steppic, Anatolian, Black Sea, and Pannonian bioregions.

Conversely, the Arctic bioregion exhibited markedly low or negligible herbicide usage, with instances where such data were absent from the FAOSTAT database for 2016-2021. Following the Atlantic, the Continental bioregion reported the next highest herbicide usage, succeeded by the Mediterranean region.

An annual summation of herbicide use per country from 2016 to 2021 also underwent analysis and ranking in Table 6. This assessment indicated a shift in use proportions. Despite Poland's cropland area, representing the Continental bioregion, being substantially smaller than Turkey's (which represents the Anatolian and Black Sea bioregion), Poland emerged as the most prolific consumer of herbicides among the examined countries (Table 6). Romania, aligning with the Steppic bioregion, presents an intriguing case, with herbicide consumption nearly half that of Italy, despite both countries having comparable cropland areas (Table 6). Remarkably, Romania's herbicide use aligns closely with Hungary's, even though Hungary's cropland area is half that of Romania's (Table 6).

Table 6. Rank of countries according to the yearly herbicide use in tons (average for years 2016-2021)

Country	Yearly herbicides used in tons	Cropland area (ha)	Rank
Poland	12 761 333	11 372 626	1
Turkey	10 659 205	23 325 833	2
Italy	7 462 666	9 267 057	3
Romania	4 611 728	9 056 166	4
Hungary	4 200 440	4 409 389	5

Belgium	2 330 013	877 373	6
Portugal	2 119 923	1 793 080	7
Slovakia	888 166	1 361 000	8
Estonia	491 881	696 000	9
Island	1 465	12 902	10

Source: own elaboration based on data from FAOSTAT⁵⁹ and EUROSTAT⁶⁰⁵

5. Prospective, Challenges and Opportunities

The in-depth review of herbicide use across Europe's diverse agricultural landscapes uncovers a multifaceted scenario marked by the historical evolution of weed control methods, the progression toward herbicide-resistant crops, and the ensuing ecological and regulatory challenges.

This narrative illustrates the critical juncture at which modern agriculture finds itself, grappling with the dual imperatives of enhancing crop yields while preserving environmental integrity. The historical reliance on chemical herbicides, notably exemplified by the widespread adoption of herbicide-tolerant genetically modified crops (not in Europe), has precipitated a notable reduction in herbicide diversity. This shift has inadvertently escalated the risks associated with herbicide resistance, with profound implications for biodiversity and the health of soil microbiota. Such developments underscore the inherent complexities within the European Union's regulatory framework, which, despite its rigorous approach to herbicide approval and monitoring, has encountered significant controversies, most notably surrounding the use and regulation of glyphosate, still re-registered. These controversies highlight an acute need for independent, robust research to inform regulatory frameworks, ensuring they are grounded in comprehensive risk assessments and the latest scientific findings.

Moreover, the ecological impact of sustained herbicide use, manifested in the decline of biodiversity and the rise of herbicide-resistant weed species, brings to the forefront the urgent necessity for sustainable weed management strategies. These strategies, which include reducing reliance on chemical herbicides in favour of crop rotation, biological control methods, and mechanical weeding, offer a pathway to mitigate the adverse impacts on ecosystems and human health. Such a shift necessitates reevaluating current regulatory policies and adopting policies that incentivise and support the transition toward more sustainable agricultural practices.

In response to these challenges, this analysis proposes a multi-faceted approach aligned with the European Green Deal's objectives. This approach calls for enhanced research into the long-term ecological impacts of herbicides, focusing on their effects on soil health, non-target species, and overall biodiversity. It advocates for the evolution of policy frameworks to be dynamic and reflective of the latest scientific insights, technological advancements, and the principles of the Green Deal. Specifically, policies should support developing and adopting innovative weed management technologies and practices, facilitating a transition towards more sustainable agriculture. In this sense, reducing the active dose of herbicide per unit area and sectorizing the application of herbicides could be helpful measures.

Moreover, there is a pronounced need for educational programs and technical support for farmers and agricultural stakeholders, guiding them through the transition to sustainable weed management practices. These initiatives should promote the adoption of precision agriculture techniques to minimise herbicide use and maximise efficiency, thereby aligning agricultural productivity with environmental stewardship.

The European Community can significantly advance towards the sustainability goals outlined in the Green Deal by embracing integrated weed management practices, committing to ongoing research, and implementing forward-thinking policies. This comprehensive strategy addresses the immediate challenges of herbicide resistance and ecological degradation. It sets the stage for a more sustainable, resilient agricultural

future, harmonising the dual objectives of enhancing food security and preserving the natural environment.

Finally, glyphosate—a widely used and highly effective herbicide—faces significant controversies due to its environmental and health risks. While its effectiveness and low cost have made it popular, the herbicide's extensive use has led to widespread resistance in weeds (57 resistant species across 31 countries) and adverse impacts on non-target organisms, including those in soil and aquatic ecosystems. In light of these issues, efforts are increasingly turning towards reducing glyphosate use by integrating agroecological practices. By combining strategies such as crop rotation, sectorized weed management, and the application of modern technologies like drones, robots, satellites, and artificial intelligence, it is possible to mitigate the negative effects associated with glyphosate while still maintaining effective weed control. Although the herbicide remains authorised and widely used in Europe due to its practicality, the environmental and safety concerns underscore the urgent need for independent, robust research to understand its long-term impacts better. As a result, sustainable alternatives and a more judicious approach to herbicide application are strongly advocated to ensure both agricultural productivity and environmental protection.

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Supplementary Table S1. Complete dataset detailing the herbicides (i.e., European nations in which they are allowed, WHO hazard class, etc.). Herbicides allowed in Europe according to the EU pesticide database (<https://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/pesticides/eu-pesticides-database/start/screen/active-substances>).

Herbicide	Harmonized FAO classification	Harmonized FAO classification	Molecular formula	MoA	Herbicide resistance cases [Heap 2024]	WHO hazard class	date of approval	expiration of approval	Authorised countries
Fenoxaprop-P-ethyl	other	Aryloxyphenoxy-propionic herbicides	C16H12ClNO5	HRAC/WSSA 1	122 cases, 35 countries, 26 species	III	01/01/2009	15/08/2025	AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, DK, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, LT, LU, LV, NL, PL, PT, RO, SE, SK, UK
Fluazifop-P-butyl	other	Aryloxyphenoxy-propionic herbicides	C15H12F3NO4	HRAC/WSSA 1	55 cases, 16 countries, 23 species	III	01/01/2012	31/05/2026	AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, IT, LT, LU, LV, NL, PL, PT, RO, SE, SI, SK, UK
Propaquizafop	other	Aryloxyphenoxy-propionic herbicides	C22H22ClN3O5	HRAC/WSSA 1	13 cases, 9 countries, 10 species	U	01/12/2009	28/02/2027	AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, DK, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, LT, LU, LV, PL, PT, RO, SE, SI, SK, UK
Quizalofop-P-ethyl	other	Aryloxyphenoxy-propionic herbicides	C19H17ClN2O4	HRAC/WSSA 1	40 cases, 15 countries, 20 species	II	01/12/2009	28/02/2027	AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, LT, LU, LV, MT, NL, PL, PT, RO, SE, SI, SK, UK
Clodinafop	other	Aryloxyphenoxy-propionic herbicides	C14H11ClFNO4	HRAC/WSSA 1	78 cases, 25 countries, 13 species		01/02/2007	15/12/2025	BG, CY, DE, DK, EL, ES, FR, FR, FR, HR, IE, NL, PL, PT, RO, UK
Cyhalofop-butyl	other	Aryloxyphenoxy-propionic herbicides	C20H20FNO4	HRAC/WSSA 1	25 cases, 13 countries, 9 species	U	01/07/2017	30/06/2032	BG, EL, ES, FR, FR, FR, PT
Diclofop	other	Aryloxyphenoxy-propionic herbicides	C15H12Cl2O4	HRAC/WSSA 1	87 cases, 20 countries, 13 species	II	01/06/2011	31/08/2026	EL, ES, PT
Clethodim	other	Cyclohexanedione herbicides	C17H26ClNO3S	HRAC/WSSA 1	34 cases, 12 countries, 16 species		01/06/2011	31/08/2026	AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, IT, LT, LU, LV, NL, PL, PT, RO, SE, SI, SK, UK
Cycloxydim	other	Cyclohexanedione herbicides	C17H27NO3S	HRAC/WSSA 1	26 cases, 10 countries, 9 species	III	01/06/2011	31/08/2026	AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, DK, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, LT, LU, LV, NL, PL, PT, RO, SE, SI, SK, UK

Pinoxaden	other	Phenylpyrazole herbicides	C23H32N2O4	HRAC/WSSA 1	60 cases, 18 countries, 16 species	III	01/07/2016	30/06/2026	AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, IT, LT, LU, LV, NL, PL, PT, RO, SE, SI, SK, UK
Florasulam	amides and anilides	Anilide herbicides	C12H8F3N5O3S	HRAC/WSSA 2	36 cases, 17 countries, 23 species	U	01/01/2016	31/12/2030	AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, DK, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, IT, LT, LU, LV, MT, NL, PL, PT, RO, SE, SI, SK, UK
Penoxsulam	amides and anilides	Amide herbicides	C16H14F5N5O5S	HRAC/WSSA 2	29 cases, 13 countries, 14 species	U	01/08/2010	15/05/2026	AT, BE, CY, CZ, DE, EL, ES, FR, FR, FR, HU, LU, PT, RO, SI, SK
Pyroxsulam	amides and anilides	Amide herbicides	C14H13F3N6O5S	HRAC/WSSA 2	56 cases, 19 countries, 27 species	III	01/05/2014	30/04/2025	AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, DK, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, LT, LU, LV, NL, PL, PT, RO, SE, SI, SK, UK
Imazamox	other	Imidazolinone herbicides	C15H19N3O4	HRAC/WSSA 2	74 cases, 18 countries, 43 species	III	01/11/2017	31/01/2025	AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, LT, LV, MT, NL, PL, PT, RO, SE, SI, SK, UK
Propoxycarbazone	other	Triazolone herbicides	C15H18N4O7S	HRAC/WSSA 2	18 cases, 10 countries, 12 species		01/09/2017	31/08/2032	BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, IE, LU, LV, PL, PT, RO, SE, SK, UK
Thiencarbazone-methyl	other	Triazolone herbicides	C12H14N4O7S2	HRAC/WSSA 2	6 cases, 4 countries, 5 species		01/07/2014	30/09/2024	AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, DK, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, LT, LU, LV, NL, PL, PT, RO, SE, SI, SK, UK
Amidosulfuron	sulfonylurea herbicides	Sulfonylurea herbicides	C9H15N5O7S2	HRAC/WSSA 2	5 cases, 5 countries, 5 species		01/01/2009	15/08/2025	AT, BE, BG, CZ, DE, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, IT, LT, LU, LV, NL, PL, PT, RO, SE, SI, SK, UK
Bensulfuron	sulfonylurea herbicides	Sulfonylurea herbicides	C15H16N4O7S	HRAC/WSSA 2	58 cases, 13 countries, 31 species	U		15/08/2026	AT, BG, CY, EL, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IT, MT, NL, PL, PT, RO, SI
Flazasulfuron	sulfonylurea herbicides	Sulfonylurea herbicides	C13H12F3N5O5S	HRAC/WSSA 2	5 cases, 3 countries, 4 species	III	01/08/2017	31/07/2032	AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, EL, ES, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, LU, MT, PL, PT, RO, SK, UK
Foramsulfuron	sulfonylurea herbicides	Sulfonylurea herbicides	C17H20N6O7S	HRAC/WSSA 2	27 cases, 11 countries, 16 species		01/06/2020	31/05/2035	AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, DK, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, IT, LT, LU, LV, NL, PL, PT, RO, SE, SI, SK, UK
Halosulfuron - methyl	sulfonylurea herbicides	Sulfonylurea herbicides	C13H15CIN6O7S	HRAC/WSSA 2	25 cases, 5 countries, 20 species			05/08/2025	BG, EL, FR, FR, FR, HU, PT

Iodosulfuron-methyl	sulfonylurea herbicides	Sulfonylurea herbicides	C14H14IN5O6S	HRAC/WSSA 2	118 cases, 31 countries, 40 species		31/03/2032	AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, DK, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, LT, LU, LV, NL, PL, PT, RO, SE, SI, SK, UK
Mesosulfuron-methyl	sulfonylurea herbicides	Sulfonylurea herbicides	C17H21N5O9S2	HRAC/WSSA 2	89 cases, 24 countries, 26 species		30/06/2032	AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, DK, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, IT, LT, LU, LV, NL, PL, PT, RO, SE, SI, SK, UK
Metsulfuron-methyl	sulfonylurea herbicides	Sulfonylurea herbicides	C14H15N5O6S	HRAC/WSSA 2	84 cases, 18 countries, 40 species	U	01/04/2016	31/03/2024 AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, DK, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, LT, LU, LV, MT, NL, PL, PT, RO, SE, SI, SK, UK
Nicosulfuron	sulfonylurea herbicides	Sulfonylurea herbicides	C15H18N6O6S	HRAC/WSSA 2	59 cases, 18 countries, 27 species	U	01/01/2009	31/03/2027 AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, EE, EL, ES, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, LT, LU, LV, MT, NL, PL, PT, RO, SI, SK, UK
Prosulfuron	sulfonylurea herbicides	Sulfonylurea herbicides	C15H16F3N5O4S	HRAC/WSSA 2	8 cases, 4 countries, 7 species		01/05/2017	31/07/2024 AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, LT, LU, LV, MT, NL, PL, PT, RO, SI, SK, UK
Rimsulfuron (aka renriduron)	sulfonylurea herbicides	Sulfonylurea herbicides	C14H17N5O7S2	HRAC/WSSA 2	17 cases, 9 countries, 12 species	U	01/02/2007	15/08/2025 AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, LT, LU, LV, MT, NL, PL, PT, RO, SE, SI, SK, UK
Sulfosulfuron	sulfonylurea herbicides	Sulfonylurea herbicides	C16H18N6O7S2	HRAC/WSSA 2	22 cases, 12 countries, 14 species		01/01/2016	31/12/2030 BE, CZ, EE, FI, FR, FR, FR, HU, IE, IT, LV, SK, UK
Thifensulfuron-methyl	sulfonylurea herbicides	Sulfonylurea herbicides	C12H13N5O6S2	HRAC/WSSA 2	93 cases, 13 countries, 31 species	U	01/11/2016	31/10/2031 AT, BE, BG, CZ, DE, DK, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, LT, LU, LV, NL, PL, PT, RO, SE, SI, SK, UK
Tribenuron (aka metometuron)	sulfonylurea herbicides	Sulfonylurea herbicides	C14H15N5O6S	HRAC/WSSA 2	105 cases, 23 countries, 48 species	U		30/01/2034 AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, DK, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, LU, LV, MT, NL, PL, PT, RO, SE, SI, SK, UK
Tritosulfuron	sulfonylurea herbicides	Sulfonylurea herbicides	C13H9F6N5O4S	HRAC/WSSA 2	1 case, 1 country, 1 species		01/12/2008	15/07/2025 AT, BE, CZ, DE, DK, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, NL, PL, RO, SE, SK, UK
Propyzamide	amides and anilides	Amide herbicides	C12H11Cl2NO	HRAC/WSSA 3	6 cases, 2 countries, 2 species	U	01/07/2018	30/06/2025 AT, BE, CY, CZ, DE, DK, EL, FR, FR, FR, HU, IE, IT, LU, MT, NL, PL, PT, SE, UK
Pendimethalin	dinitroaniline derivatives	Dinitroaniline herbicides	C13H19N3O4	HRAC/WSSA 3	11 cases, 5 countries, 6 species	II	01/09/2017	30/11/2024 AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, DK, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, LT, LU, LV, MT, NL, PL, PT, RO, SI, SK, UK

Florpyrauxifen-benzyl	other	Pyridinecarboxylic-acid herbicides	C20H14Cl2F2N2O3	HRAC/WSSA 4	2 cases, 2 species, 1 country		24/07/2019	24/07/2029	BG, EL, ES, FR, FR, FR
Dicamba	other	Benzoic-acid herbicides	C8H6Cl2O3	HRAC/WSSA 4	21 cases, 7 countries, 10 species	II	01/01/2009	31/03/2027	AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, DK, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, LT, LU, LV, MT, NL, PL, PT, RO, SI, SK, UK
Aminopyralid	other	Pyridinecarboxylic-acid herbicides	C6H4Cl2N2O2	HRAC/WSSA 4	4 cases, 3 countries, 3 species	U	01/01/2015	31/12/2024	AT, BE, BG, CZ, DE, DK, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, IT, LT, LU, LV, NL, PL, PT, RO, SE, SI, SK, UK
Clopyralid	other	Pyridinecarboxylic-acid herbicides	C6H3Cl2NO2	HRAC/WSSA 4	4 case, 3 countries, 4 species	III	01/10/2021	30/09/2036	FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, IT, LT, LU, LV, NL, PL, PT, RO, SE, SI, SK, UK
Fluroxypyr	other	Pyridyloxyacetic-acid herbicides	C7H5Cl2FN2O3	HRAC/WSSA 4	6 cases, 3 countries, 4 species	U	01/01/2012	31/12/2024	AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, DK, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, LT, LU, LV, MT, NL, PL, PT, RO, SE, SI, SK, UK
Halauxifen-methyl	other	Pyridinecarboxylic-acid herbicides	C14H11Cl2FN2O3	HRAC/WSSA 4	<i>Not available</i>		05/08/2015	05/08/2025	AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, DK, EE, FI, FR, FR, FR, HU, IE, LT, LU, LV, NL, PL, PT, RO, SE, SI, SK, UK
Picloram	other	Pyridinecarboxylic-acid herbicides	C6H3Cl3N2O2	HRAC/WSSA 4	5 cases, 3 countries, 5 species	U	01/01/2009	15/02/2028	AT, BG, CZ, DE, DK, EE, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, LT, LU, LV, PL, RO, SE, SI, SK, UK
Triclopyr	other	Pyridyloxyacetic-acid herbicides	C7H4Cl3NO3	HRAC/WSSA 4	1 case, 1 country, 1 species	II	01/06/2007	15/12/2024	AT, BE, CY, CZ, DE, EL, ES, FR, FR, FR, IE, LU, NL, PL, PT, RO, SK, UK
Quinmerac	other	Quinoline herbicides	C11H8ClNO2	HRAC/WSSA 4	<i>Not available</i>	U	01/05/2011	31/07/2024	AT, BE, BG, CZ, DE, EE, EL, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, LT, LU, LV, NL, PL, RO, SE, SI, SK, UK
2,4-D	phenoxyphytohormones	Phenoxy herbicides	C8H6Cl2O3	HRAC/WSSA 4	47 cases, 16 countries, 25 species	II	01/01/2016	31/12/2030	AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, DK, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, IT, LT, LU, LV, MT, NL, PL, PT, RO, SE, SI, SK, UK
2,4-DB	phenoxyphytohormones	Phenoxy herbicides	C10H10Cl2O3	HRAC/WSSA 4	<i>Not available</i>	II	01/11/2017	31/10/2032	ES, IE, NL, UK
Dichlorprop-P	phenoxyphytohormones	Phenoxy herbicides	C9H8Cl2O3	HRAC/WSSA 4	2 case, 1 country, 2 species	II	01/06/2007	15/03/2025	

MCPA	phenoxyphytohormones	Phenoxy herbicides	C9H9ClO3	HRAC/WSSA 4	17 cases, 9 countries, 13 species	II	01/05/2006	15/08/2026	AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, DK, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, LT, LU, LV, MT, NL, PL, PT, RO, SE, SI, SK, UK
MCPB	phenoxyphytohormones	Phenoxy herbicides	C11H13ClO3	HRAC/WSSA 4	1 case, 1 country, 1 species	II	01/05/2006	15/08/2026	AT, BE, CZ, EE, FR, FR, FR, HU, IE, LT, LU, LV, PL, RO, SK, UK
Mecoprop-P	phenoxyphytohormones	Phenoxy herbicides	C10H11ClO3	HRAC/WSSA 4	3 case, 2 countries, 3 species	II	01/06/2004	31/01/2024	AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, LT, LU, LV, NL, PL, PT, SI, SK, UK
Phenmedipham	carbamates	Bis-carbamate herbicides	C16H16N2O4	HRAC/WSSA 5	1 case, 1 country, 1 species	U	01/03/2005	15/02/2025	AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, LT, LU, LV, NL, PL, PT, RO, SE, SK, UK
Terbuthylazine	triazine	Triazine herbicides	C9H16ClN5	HRAC/WSSA 5	6 cases, 3 countries, 5 species	III	01/01/2012	31/12/2024	AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, EL, ES, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, IT, LU, MT, NL, PL, PT, RO, SI, SK, UK
Metribuzin	triazine	Triazinone herbicides	C8H14N4OS	HRAC/WSSA 5	30 cases, 11 countries, 16 species	II	01/10/2007	15/02/2025	AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, IT, LU, LV, MT, NL, PL, PT, RO, SE, SI, SK, UK
Lenacil	uracil	Uracil herbicides	C13H18N2O2	HRAC/WSSA 5	6 cases, 2 countries, 5 species	U	01/01/2009	15/08/2025	AT, BE, CY, CZ, DE, EL, ES, FR, FR, FR, HU, IE, NL, PL, PT, RO, SK, UK
Chlorotoluron	urea	Urea herbicides	C10H13ClN2O	HRAC/WSSA 5	16 cases, 7 countries, 6 species	U	01/03/2006	15/08/2026	
Fluometuron	urea	Urea herbicides	C10H11F3N2O	HRAC/WSSA 5	<i>Not available</i>	U	01/06/2011	31/08/2024	
Metobromuron	urea	Urea herbicides	C9H11BrN2O2	HRAC/WSSA 5	<i>Not available</i>	III	01/01/2015	31/12/2024	AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, DK, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, LT, LU, LV, MT, NL, PL, PT, RO, SE, SI, SK, UK
Bentazon	other	Thiadiazine herbicides	C10H12N2O3S	HRAC/WSSA 6	3 cases, 2 countries, 3 species	II	01/06/2018	31/05/2025	BE, BG, CY, CZ, DK, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, IT, LT, LU, LV, NL, PL, PT, RO, SE, SI, SK, UK
Pyridate	other	Diazine herbicides	C19H23ClN2O2S	HRAC/WSSA 6	<i>Not available</i>	III	01/01/2016	31/12/2030	AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, DK, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, LT, LU, LV, MT, NL, PL, PT, RO, SE, SI, SK, UK

Glyphosate	other	Organophosphorus herbicides	C3H8NO5P	HRAC/WSSA 9	361 cases, 31 countries, 57 species	III	16/12/2017	15/12/2033	AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, DK, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, LT, LV, MT, NL, PL, PT, RO, SE, SI, SK, UK
Beflubutamid	amides and anilides	Amide herbicides	C18H17F4NO2	HRAC/WSSA 12	<i>Not available</i>		01/12/2007	31/10/2026	BE, BG, CZ, DE, EL, ES, FR, FR, FR, IT, LU, PL, RO
Diflufenican	amides and anilides	Anilide herbicides	C19H11F5N2O2	HRAC/WSSA 12	7 cases, 2 countries, 4 species	III	01/01/2009	15/01/2026	AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, DK, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, LT, LU, LV, MT, NL, PL, PT, RO, SE, SI, SK, UK
Picolinafen	other	Pyridinecarboxamide herbicides	C19H12F4N2O2	HRAC/WSSA 12	<i>Not available</i>		01/11/2016	30/06/2031	AT, BE, BG, CZ, DE, DK, EE, ES, FR, FR, FR, HU, IE, IT, LT, LU, LV, PL, SE, UK
Flurochloridone			C12H10Cl2F3NO	HRAC/WSSA 12	<i>Not available</i>		01/06/2011	15/03/2026	CZ, EL, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IT, PL, RO, SK
Clomazone	other	Unclassified herbicides	C12H14ClNO2	HRAC/WSSA 13	3 cases, 2 countries, 3 species	II	01/11/2008	15/06/2025	AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, DK, EE, EL, ES, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, LT, LU, LV, MT, NL, PL, PT, RO, SE, SI, SK, UK
Oxyfluorfen	other	Diphenyl ether herbicides	C15H11ClF3NO4	HRAC/WSSA 14	3 cases, 3 countries, 3 species	U	01/01/2012	31/12/2024	BG, CY, EL, ES, HR, MT, PL, PT, RO
Bifenox	other	Diphenyl ether herbicides	C14H9Cl2NO5	HRAC/WSSA 14	<i>Not available</i>	U	01/01/2009	31/03/2027	AT, BE, BG, CZ, DE, EE, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HU, IT, LT, LU, LV, NL, PL, RO, SE, SK, UK
Flumioxazin	other	Dicarboximide herbicides	C19H15FN2O4	HRAC/WSSA 14	2 cases, 1 country, 2 species	III	01/03/2022	28/02/2037	AT, BE, BG, CZ, DE, EL, ES, HR, HU, IE, LV, NL, RO, UK
Pyraflufen-ethyl	other	Phenylpyrazole herbicides	C15H13Cl2F3N2O4	HRAC/WSSA 14	2 cases, 1 country, 2 species		01/04/2016	31/03/2031	AT, BE, BG, CZ, DE, EL, ES, FR, FR, FR, HU, IE, LU, NL, PL, PT, RO, UK
Carfentrazone-ethyl	other	Triazolinone herbicides	C15H14Cl2F3N3O3	HRAC/WSSA 14	5 cases, 4 countries, 4 species		01/08/2018	31/07/2033	AT, BE, CZ, DE, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HU, IE, IT, LT, LU, LV, MT, NL, PL, PT, SE, SK, UK
Dimethachlor	amides and anilides	Chloroacetanilide herbicides	C13H18ClNO2	HRAC/WSSA 15	<i>Not available</i>		01/01/2010	15/10/2026	AT, BG, CZ, DE, EE, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, LT, LV, PL, RO, SI, SK, UK
Dimethenamid-P	amides and anilides	Amide herbicides	C12H18ClNO2S	HRAC/WSSA 15	1 case 1 country, 1 species	II	01/09/2019	31/08/2034	AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, LT, LU, LV, NL, PL, PT, RO, SE, SI, SK, UK

Metazachlor	amides and anilides	Anilide herbicides	C14H16CIN3O	HRAC/WSSA 15	Not available	III	01/08/2009	31/10/2026	AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, IT, LT, LU, LV, MT, NL, PL, PT, RO, SI, SK, UK
Pethoxamid	amides and anilides	Amide herbicides	C16H22CINO2	HRAC/WSSA 15	Not available		01/12/2018	30/11/2033	AT, BE, BG, CZ, DE, EL, ES, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, LU, PL, PT, RO, SI, SK
Napropamide	amides and anilides	Amide herbicides	C17H21NO2	HRAC/WSSA 15	Not available	U	01/01/2011	31/03/2027	AT, BE, BG, CZ, DE, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, LT, LU, LV, NL, PL, RO, SE, SI, SK, UK
Flufenacet	amides and anilides	Anilide herbicides	C14H13F4N3O2S	HRAC/WSSA 15	6 cases, 4 countries, 2 species	II	01/01/2004	15/06/2025	AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, EE, EL, ES, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, LT, LU, LV, MT, NL, PL, PT, RO, SI, SK, UK
Ethofumesate	other	Benzofurane herbicides	C13H18O5S	HRAC/WSSA 15	1 case, 1 country, 1 species	U	01/11/2016	31/10/2031	AT, BE, BG, CZ, DE, DK, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, LT, LU, LV, NL, PL, PT, RO, SE, SK, UK
Prosulfocarb	other	Thiocarbamate herbicides	C14H21NOS	HRAC/WSSA 15	1 case, 1 country, 1 species	II	01/11/2009	31/01/2027	AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, DK, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, LT, LU, LV, NL, PL, PT, RO, SE, SI, SK, UK
Tri-allate	other	Thiocarbamate herbicides	C10H16Cl3NOS	HRAC/WSSA 15	12 cases, 3 countries, 2 species	III	01/01/2010	31/03/2027	BE, FR, FR, FR, IE, NL, UK
Isoxaflutole	other	Isoxazole herbicides	C15H12F3NO4S	HRAC/WSSA 27	2 cases, 2 countries, 2 species	III	01/08/2019	31/07/2034	AT, BE, BG, CZ, DE, EL, ES, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, LU, NL, PL, PT, RO, SI, SK, UK
Mesotrione	other	Triketone herbicides	C14H13NO7S	HRAC/WSSA 27	16 cases, 3 countries, 4 species	III	01/06/2017	31/05/2032	AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, DK, EE, EL, ES, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, IT, LT, LU, LV, MT, NL, PL, PT, RO, SE, SI, SK, UK
Sulcotrione	other	Triketone herbicides	C14H13ClO5S	HRAC/WSSA 27	Not available		01/09/2009	30/11/2026	BE, BG, CZ, DE, EL, ES, FR, FR, FR, HU, LU, NL, PL, PT, RO, SK
Tembotrione	other	Triketone herbicides	C17H16ClF3O6S	HRAC/WSSA 27	10 cases, 2 countries, 3 species		01/05/2014	31/07/2024	AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, EL, ES, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, LU, NL, PL, PT, RO, SI, SK, UK
Aclonifen	other	Diphenyl ether herbicides	C12H9CIN2O3	HRAC/WSSA 32	Not available	U	01/08/2009	31/10/2026	AT, BE, BG, CY, CZ, DE, DK, EE, EL, ES, FI, FR, FR, FR, HR, HU, IE, IT, LT, LU, LV, NL, PL, PT, RO, SE, SI, SK, UK

Agroecological strategies as realistic alternatives for sustainable weed management in key European crops. A review

Abstract

Weed management is a critical aspect of sustainable agriculture, and agroecological strategies offer promising alternatives to synthetic herbicides. This review explores agroecological approaches for sustainable weed management in key European crops. These approaches encompass cultural, mechanical, and biological strategies, and the integration of digital technologies into agricultural practices. The review also examines the combined agroecological strategies tailored to specific crop and regional contexts and the current state of agroecological strategies for weed management, highlighting their importance in promoting sustainable agricultural systems. Our analysis demonstrates the significant advances made in understanding and implementing these strategies. The major points are: 1) Agroecological strategies provide effective and environmentally friendly weed management solutions, minimizing reliance on synthetic herbicides. 2) The integration of digital technologies enhances the precision and efficiency of agroecological practices, optimizing resource utilization and reducing environmental impact of synthetic inputs, 3) The variation of agroecological strategies depend on crop and field localization. In short, this review underscores the critical role of agroecology in addressing weed management challenges while promoting sustainability in European agriculture. By synthesizing existing knowledge and identifying emerging trends, this review provides valuable insights into the practical application and future directions of agroecological weed management strategies.

1. INTRODUCTION

In today's world, agriculture faces many challenges that threaten food security, environmental sustainability, and rural livelihoods. These challenges include heightened competition for renewable resources, ongoing malnutrition, rural poverty, consolidation of power within agricultural and food industries, increasing climate change impact, and concerning biodiversity declines. Addressing these intertwined issues will require a paradigm change in agricultural systems and fields, with deep transformations at different levels (FAO 2018; IPBES 2019; IPCC 2019). In this sense, agroecology (AE) emerges as a lifeline to achieve this paradigm change in agricultural production.

During the 1920s, Bensing (1928) first coined the term "Agroecology" to refer to the application of ecology in agriculture. Ten years later, he defined Agroecology as a basic agriculture science (Bensing 1938). It was not until the middle of the century that it began to be considered a holistic approach to agriculture. Nowadays, AE is regarded as an agricultural approach that takes into account the interconnectedness of ecological, socio-cultural, technological, economic, and political dimensions of food systems (Sümane et al. 2021), emphasizing biodiversity, soil health, natural resource conservation, and sustainable development (Wezel and Jauneau 2011). AE has a holistic view on agriculture and food systems to transform agroecosystems into sustainable systems through ecological science, agricultural practices, and social movements, advocating for socially equitable food systems, emphasizing food security, local knowledge, and the rights of farmers and rural communities (Wezel et al. 2020). AE represents a transdisciplinary field that goes beyond the boundaries of traditional disciplines like agronomy, ecology, sociology, economics, and anthropology. Therefore, AE seeks to build locally relevant food systems that strengthen the rural economy, promote fair and safe food production, and respect indigenous rights (Marchetti et al. 2020). In agroecological approach, all the stakeholders (including researchers, farmers, advisors, companies, consumers, etc.) collaborate across disciplinary boundaries to understand and address the interconnected ecological, social, economic, and political dimensions of agriculture and food systems (Galli et al. 2020). This transdisciplinary

approach recognizes that these systems are inherently complex and cannot be fully understood or addressed within the confines of any single discipline (Méndez et al. 2015; Nicot et al. 2018; Fernández-González et al. 2021). In the realm of agroecology, the integration of modern tools such as internet platforms has become indispensable, fostering stronger connections within a transdisciplinary framework. Websites like <https://www.agroecology-europe-hub.org/en/home> serve as vital hubs for knowledge exchange, collaborative research, and networking among diverse stakeholders involved in agroecological practices across Europe. Similarly, platforms like <https://agroecologymap.org/en/dashboard> provide interactive maps and databases, facilitating access to spatially explicit information on agroecological initiatives, resources, and opportunities. Through these online resources, stakeholders ranging from farmers and researchers to policymakers and consumers can engage in informed decision-making, share best practices, and contribute to the advancement of sustainable agricultural systems.

According to FAO (2018), the ten Elements of Agroecology integrate ecological principles with social and economic considerations, highlighting key ecological aspects like (1) diversity, (2) co-creation and sharing of knowledge, (3) synergies enhancing key functions across food systems, (4) efficiency in the agroecological practices reducing external resources, (5) recycling, which involves reducing economic and environmental costs, (6) resilience of ecosystems, communities and people, (7) protection and enhance of human and social values, (8) support of culture and food traditions, (9) advocating responsible governances from local to global, and (10) reconnecting producers and consumers through circular and solidarity economy.

Given the urgent need to address the complex challenges facing agriculture and food systems, adopting agroecological techniques is imperative. Not only because these techniques offer practical solutions to weed management and other agronomic issues but also because AE contributes to build resilient, sustainable, and socially fair food systems, which can withstand the uncertainties of the near future. While we are going through the complexities of the 21st century (population increase, extreme environmental events, water deficit, massive social migrations due to climate change,

etc.), AE stands out as a promising pathway towards a more sustainable, resilient, and safe agricultural future.

Agroecosystems are partially closed (self-sustainable) systems comprising living organisms (such as plants, animals, and microbes) and their environment managed by agroecological techniques. In the agroecosystems, different components are interdependent and interact regularly as reported by Caporali (2010). The general framework for describing the structure and functioning of an agroecosystem relies on an input/output framework. Within AE, biophysical and socio-economic elements are seamlessly intertwined, facilitating an ongoing resource transformation process across various spatial and temporal scales.

This manuscript focuses on evaluating agroecological strategies as viable and sustainable alternatives for weed management in key European crops, with the objective of reducing reliance on synthetic herbicides. It emphasizes how these strategies contribute to resilient agricultural systems and highlights barriers, advantages, and necessary future developments for their adoption. Weeds are responsible for significant crop losses, which cost farmers time and money. This, together with the initiatives of the European Union, such as the Farm to Fork Strategy (European Commission, 2022), for the reduction of the use of synthetic herbicides together with the vision of AE as a realistic transitional agricultural system for the European farms, is the reason why AE-related strategies are increasingly growing in popularity in the last years. Therefore, this review is essential for sustainable agriculture, as it will serve stakeholders with a critical exploration of methods that prioritise ecological balance, biodiversity conservation, and resource efficiency in farming practices.

AS offer innovative approaches for weed management, suppressing weed growth while enhancing soil health and biodiversity. AS for weed management can be categorized (Fig 1) as cultural (i.e., crop rotation, intercropping, cover crops, competitive varieties, crop seed management or false seedbed), mechanical/physical (i.e., tillage, mulching, solarisation, thermal weed control, vermicompost application, mowing or harrowing),

and biological/biotechnological (i.e., allelopathic plants, plant essential oils, natural bioactive compounds, or use of animals). Furthermore, by fostering a diverse agroecosystem, these strategies will naturally mitigate risks associated with pests and pathogens, reducing reliance on synthetic pesticides, and promoting long-term resilience. However, pesticide-free, non-organic production systems are emerging in Europe as a novel approach to agricultural pest management, offering a potential 'third way' between conventional and organic practices with lower adoption barriers and greater flexibility compared to organic farming (Finger and Möhring 2024). Since soil health is the base of agricultural productivity, incorporating AE principles into soil management strategies is essential to promote soil fertility, structure, and microbial diversity. Ultimately, this review underlines the fundamental role of AS in addressing the multiple challenges of modern agriculture to offer sustainable solutions for weed management, while promoting the health and resilience of agroecosystems.

Figure 1. Agroecological strategies for weed management.

2. WEEDS AND CROPS

The relationships between weeds and crops are intimate and ancient, returning to the earliest stages of agriculture (Harlan 1982). Weeds coincide spatially with crop plants

sharing a dynamic and intricate relationship within agricultural systems, profoundly impacting crop production, ecosystem health, and farm management practices (Jabran et al. 2015; Young et al. 2023). Weeds, broadly defined as undesired plants growing in crop fields, can represent a significant pressure on cultivated crops by competing for essential resources such as water, nutrients, sunlight, and space. This competition often results in reduced crop yields, ecological imbalances, compromised quality, and increased production costs for farmers (Ghosh et al. 2023). Beyond direct competition with crops for resources, weeds can also reduce flora biodiversity in the ecosystem, serving as reservoirs for pests and diseases and providing refuge and resources for organisms that can further threaten crop health and yield. These interactions between weeds, other pests, and diseases can create complex and interconnected problems for farmers, complicating pest management efforts and increasing reliance on chemical inputs (Sipes and Wang 2017; Dentika et al. 2021). The United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) estimated crop losses due to pests, including weeds, in around 20-40% globally. Gharde et al. (2018) observed that the presence of weeds growing with main crops resulted in yield losses of 36% in peanut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.), 31% in soybean (*Glycine max* (L.) Merr.), 25% in maize (*Zea mays* L.), and 19% in wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.). Moreover, Deutsch et al. (2018) suggested that every degree increase in global temperatures will increase pest-linked yield losses by 10-25%, which will complicate the management of weeds, even more, in the near future.

Weeds have developed various adaptive traits that confer a competitive advantage over crops and give weeds the capacity to adapt to the stress induced by humans (Sutherland 2004). This adaptation can be summarized in 10 different traits: general-purpose genotypes, life history strategies, ability to evolve rapidly, epigenetic capacity, hybridization, herbicide resistance, herbicide tolerance, cropping systems vulnerability, co-evolution of weeds with human management, and the ability to cope with climate change (Clements and Jones 2021). As a result, weeds can quickly colonize agricultural fields, gardens, and other disturbed habitats, establishing dense populations that further challenge crop growth and productivity, and for those reasons weeds density/frequency should be controlled.

Herbicides are chemical compounds used to control weeds by disrupting essential physiological processes in plant growth through various modes of action, including inhibition of photosynthesis, alteration of cell membrane integrity, blocking amino acid synthesis, and interference with plant growth regulators, ultimately leading to weed's death (Lushchak et al. 2018). However, their massive and indiscriminate application in recent decades has increased soil, air, and water pollution, increasing herbicide-linked costs in agriculture and serious problems for the ecosystem and human health (Ramírez-Morales et al. 2021). Moreover, excessive use of herbicides with similar modes of action exerts selective pressure on weed populations, favouring the survival and proliferation of individuals with natural or acquired resistance traits, thereby diminishing herbicide efficacy. Resistance mechanisms may involve mutations in the herbicide's target site or efficient compound metabolism (Vila-Aiub 2019; Gaines et al. 2020). Factors such as continuous selection pressure from repeated and exclusive use of herbicides with similar modes of action, genetic diversity providing advantageous traits, and seed dispersal contribute to the spread of resistance traits within and between weed populations (Vila-Aiub 2019; Gaines et al. 2020). This massive use of synthetic herbicides has induced the evolution of resistant weeds, which exponentially increased in the last thirty years, with more than 500 weed biotypes currently resistant to herbicides (Heap 2024).

Therefore, it is imperative to address the multifaceted challenges posed by weeds in agricultural systems to adopt holistic and integrated approaches that consider the ecological dynamics of weed-crop interactions. These approaches must prioritize sustainable farming practices that combine diverse friendly control methods, such as cultural, mechanical and biological. AS combine multiple control methods in a coordinated and strategic way, and they are essential for effectively managing weeds while maintaining the ecological balance of agroecosystems. By integrating diverse cropping systems, enhancing crop diversity, and minimizing soil disturbance, AE farming systems can reduce weed pressure, enhance ecosystem resilience, improve soil health, promote biodiversity, and foster long-term sustainability (Altieri 2019; Hawes et al. 2021).

3. AGROECOLOGICAL STRATEGIES (AS) FOR WEED MANAGEMENT

As previously stated in the introduction, AE is an innovative and sustainable farming approach that emphasizes the integration of ecological principles into agricultural systems. By harnessing nature's power, AS aims to eliminate synthetic inputs and promote biodiversity while maintaining or even increasing crop productivity (Gallardo-López et al. 2018; Hawes et al. 2021). In recent years, plenty of literature has explored various AS for weed control. These strategies encompass cultural, mechanical, physical, biological and biotechnological approaches for weed management (Wong et al. 2022; Ghosh et al. 2023). AS enclose a range of practices that promote sustainable and environmentally-friendly agriculture. These strategies are based on ecological balance, biodiversity, and resource conservation principles. These approaches prioritize natural processes and aim to minimize the use of synthetic inputs, such as chemical pesticides and fertilizers (Altieri 2019).

3.1. Cultural strategies

Cultural methods involve manipulating agricultural practices and cropping systems to create unfavourable conditions for weed growth. Examples of cultural methods include crop rotation, intercropping, and cover cropping, among others (Ofosu et al. 2023). Research has shown that these practices can effectively suppress weed growth by competing for resources such as light, water, and nutrients (Andrew et al. 2015). Five different and promising cultural AS are introduced in the following subheads (Fig. 2).

3.1.1. Crop rotation

Crop rotation is an essential AS that involves the sequential planting of different types of crops in the same field or plot (Kollas et al. 2015). The practice of crop rotation started thousands of years ago, but in the 1950s and early 1960s, the general idea that crop yields would be higher when using synthetic fertilisers and pesticides than when using crop rotation spread among farmers. Fortunately, this idea has changed, and crop

rotation is generally accepted to boost yield and profit while enabling continuous output (Gokhale and Sharma 2023), as rotational crops allow agronomic, environmental and socioeconomic benefits in the agroecosystem (Reddy 2017). Moreover, crop rotation is an effective method for weed management, introducing diverse selection pressures that control the presence of spontaneous plant species in the field without allowing the conversion of any of them into a dangerous weed for the crop (Sharma et al. 2021). In this way, crop rotation promotes the control of weeds by crops, as different crops may have different weed competition abilities (Selim 2019; Weisberger et al. 2019). For example, rice-soybean (Schermer et al. 2018), rice-winter wheat (Mishra et al. 2019) and corn–soybean-winter wheat (Simić et al. 2020) rotations resulted in a reduction of weed density while improving crop productivity in comparison with the respective monocropping.

Diversified crop mixtures increase resistance to pests and diseases, as farmers can include non-host plants in rotation, interrupting the life cycle of pests and pathogens that are specific to plant species (Reddy 2017), which is effective in short (Brust and King 1994) but also in medium and long-term production (Feiziene et al. 2016). In addition, in crop rotation, crop-associated weed rotation also occurs, and the crop cycle may be shorter than the weed cycle, leading to a situation where some weeds may not have the opportunity to complete their life cycle before the next crop is planted. This interruption in the weed life cycle can help reduce weed populations and manage weed pressure more effectively (Nichols et al. 2015). Crop rotation also can enhance yield productivity by increasing organic carbon content in soil (Pikuła and Rutkowska 2014), and N₂ fixation through the incorporation of leguminous crops in the rotation (Pokhrel and Pokhrel 2013). For example, Tamm et al. (2016) observed improved soil fertility and a high yield of cereals in a rotational experiment using red clover, alsike clover (*Trifolium hybridum* L.), Washington lupine (*Lupinus polyphyllus* Lindl.), biennial white sweet clover (*Melilotus albus* Medik.), annual Alexandria clover (*Trifolium alexandrinum* L.), and crimson clover (*Trifolium incarnatum* L.), as pre-crops for subsequent cereals (rye and winter wheat). Some studies showed that cereals produced significantly extra yields after each leguminous pre-crop, which concomitantly led to reduced use of fertilizers

(Talgre et al. 2009; Talgre et al. 2012) and optimized soil microbiome diversity, ultimately improving soil health (Esmailzadeh-Salestani et al. 2021; Liu et al. 2022). Venter et al. (2016) performed a meta-analysis of studies by comparing monocultures and crop rotations and observed that soils under higher diversity of rotational crops produced higher microbial richness (15.11%, $n = 26$) and diversity scores (3.36%, $n = 43$). Expert farmers often use a combination of key cash crops, filler or break crops, and cover crops in their rotations. Moreover, different crops have varying nutrient requirements, so rotational crops can help in preventing nutrient depletion and improving soil fertility (Venkatesh et al. 2017). In addition, crop rotation can be organised according to the specific needs of crops, e.g., regarding rooting depth, rotation with shallow and deep rooting crops can help to explore the different soil profiles for water and nutrients, which contribute to increase yields and thus to improve the physical properties of the soil, such as texture and bulk density (Reddy 2017). Farmers can improve soil health, reduce pest and disease pressure, and optimize nutrient availability by implementing crop rotation, leading to more sustainable and productive agricultural systems.

Figure 2. Examples of cultural strategies. (A) Crop rotation; (B) Intercropping; (C) Cover crops. Credit: (A) Fermate, (B) Yuelen, and (C) Olga Seifutdinova.

3.1.2. Intercropping

Intercropping is a widely used AS based on growing concurrently two or more crop species in the same field or plot over long time (crop association), in definite patterns without mixing (Bedoussac et al. 2015; Li et al. 2020). Intercropping is an eco-functional technique widely employed to enhance crop productivity (Qin et al. 2013) and to optimize land use efficiency (Kidane et al. 2017) while reducing greenhouse gas emissions when compared to monoculture fields (Naudin et al. 2014). This AS promotes complementarity between plants, enhances ecological processes in the soil, and provides various benefits for sustainable agriculture (Duchene et al. 2017). The selection of the crops must be carefully made, as two crops growing on the same plot may directly compete for resources. Above-ground and below-ground plant organs may interact in an intercropping system. However, by maximizing complementary interactions and reducing competing ones, intercropping aims to use physical, temporal, and spatial resources available above and below ground (Nasar et al. 2019).

Various factors, including the genotype of crops, plant density, and arrangement influence the effectiveness of weed suppression in intercropping systems. Different types of intercropping, such as fully mixed, relay, or strip, offer distinct advantages (Scavo and Mauromicale 2021). Moreover, the selection of allelopathic genotypes, understanding allelopathy as the potential of one plant species to control the development of other plants by releasing chemical compounds to the medium (Rice, 1984) enhances weed suppression when incorporated into intercropping systems. Cereal-legume intercropping stands out as a prevalent form of allelopathic intercropping. This is primarily because numerous allelopathic crops within the Poaceae and Fabaceae families were well-suited for this technique (Scavo and Mauromicale 2021). For instance, sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* L. Moench) intercropped with hairy vetch (*Vicia villosa* L.), and grass pea (*Lathyrus sativus*) showed improved weed control and forage yields (Rad et al. 2020). Recently, Villegas-Fernández et al. (2024), showed that intercropping faba bean (*Vicia faba* L.) with wheat did not reduce weed coverage but decreased weed biomass by 46.1% as compared with the faba bean monocrop. However, Leoni et al. (2022) mentioned the importance of selecting the correct intercropping as they observed that correct legume species intercropped with wheat

can reduce weed biomass up to 90% but, on the contrary, persial clover (*Trifolium resupinatum* L.), hairy vetch (*V. villosa*), barrel medic (*Medicago truncatula* Gaertn.), and shield medic (*Medicago scutellata* L.) boosted weed growth in the following spring in comparison with the control.

Furthermore, different intercropping patterns can increase overall crop productivity and yield stability. The complementary growth patterns of different crops can optimize the use of resources such as light, water, and nutrients (Tan et al. 2020; Maitra et al. 2021). For example, the combination of maize + cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* (L.) Walp.) enhanced more light interception than the sole cropping of maize (Ghanbari et al. 2010). Numerous studies revealed that the introduction of the legume-based intercropping system altered the microbial population and added fresh organic matter, increasing the availability of organic carbon, nitrogen, zinc, iron or phosphorus in the soil (Xue et al. 2016; Dai et al. 2019). This can result in higher total yields than monoculture crops, as Li et al. (2020) showed in a meta-analysis that included more than 200 intercropping experiments. Li and co-workers asserted that intercropping with low and high inputs resulted in around 24% more grain per hectare and around 26% less fertilizer per unit than in conventional agriculture of monocrops. Intercropping can be divided into three different types depending on the crops selected to be planted in the field: (i) Parallel intercropping: The crops used do not compete with each other; (ii) Associated crops: the yield of both crops is equal to the yield of each of the crops cultivated in monoculture. This type of pattern is used for minimizing the possibilities of total crop failure; and (iii) multi-tiered cultivation: The crops used have different heights, thus allowing maximum solar energy penetration, even when the planting density is high (Vlaiculescu and Varrone, 2022).

Intercropping systems have been found to improve nutrient cycling, as different crops may have different nutrient requirements and uptake patterns. For example, leguminous crops, such as beans or peas, can fix atmospheric nitrogen and improve soil fertility, benefiting neighbouring crops (Raza et al. 2019). Several plants can also change the pH of their rhizosphere soil and increase the availability of essential minerals such as P, K, Ca, and Mg (Sirohi and Bangarwa 2017; Surki et al. 2020). Combining

intercropping with high nitrogen availability in soil, such as simultaneous white clover intercropping, can increase cover crop biomass, reduce weed growth, and improve nitrogen accumulation while maintaining crop yields and quality (Vrignon-Brenas et al. 2018). This AS also contributes to pest and disease management. By growing different crops together, the risk of pest and disease outbreaks is reduced compared to monoculture systems, as some crop combinations exhibit natural pest-repellent properties or attract beneficial insects that help control pests (Brooker et al. 2015; Allen-Perkins and Estrada 2019). For example, intercropping faba bean and pea with Egyptian clover has been suggested to reduce infection by the holoparasitic plant *Orobancha crenata* Forsk (Fernández-Aparicio et al. 2010). Intercropping can help predators detect the presence of pests and eat them before they reach a suitable host plant reducing the foraging efficiency of herbivores (Angelella et al. 2016; Mansion-Vaquié et al. 2020; Huss et al. 2022). Moreover, flying pests are more likely to settle on unsuitable plants and leave the field instead of searching for a host plant on a field with diversified intercropping.

Additionally, intercropping can enhance soil structure and water retention, reducing erosion and improving soil health (Blaise et al. 2021). This ecological diversity can lead to a more balanced agroecosystem and reduce the need for synthetic pesticides, reducing the economic cost of cultivation, which is in accordance with an agroecological system.

In short, lower input costs, higher yields, and diversification of farm incomes through intercropping can collectively lead to increased farmer profits, reduced negative environmental impacts, and a more secure food supply (Löic et al. 2018; Yang et al. 2021).

3.1.3. Cover crops

Cover crops are an integral component of agroecological systems, providing numerous benefits for sustainable agriculture, such as the increase of organic matter in the soil and the reduction of weeds, other pests, and soil erosion.

These crops are live ground cover that is sown alongside or before the first crop, generally dying before the planting of the subsequent crop (Sharma et al. 2018; He et al. 2019). The potential of cover crops lies in the fact that they can act as big competitors for resources such as light, water, nutrients, and space as cover crops usually share several characteristics, including biomass output, fast growth, root development, and duration of biological cycle (Lemessa and Wakjira 2014). Cover crops contribute to soil organic matter, enhance nutrient cycling, and improve soil structure. García-Gonzalez et al. (2018) observed that cover crops promoted soil carbon sequestration at an annual rate of 180 kg C ha⁻¹ and promoted nitrogen retention at an annual rate of 13 kg N ha⁻¹, improving C and N stocks in soils. These authors also demonstrated that barley, used as a cover crop, could mitigate nitrate leaching and reduce inorganic N content in the upper ground layer, making N available for subsequent crops. Similar results were found by Frasier and collaborators (2016), who observed more N content, enhanced root biomass, total carbon and microbial biomass, and improved soil moisture and temperature in sorghum cultivated with cover crops than in monoculture. Cover crops also help to reduce soil erosion by providing ground cover and protecting the soil from wind and water erosion (Blanco-Canqui 2018).

Regarding weed management, cover crops play a crucial role in agroecological systems. By providing an advantage to seed-eating predators, mulches and cover crops can indirectly reduce weeds' density (Nichols et al. 2015). Furthermore, cover crops function as physical barriers on the surface of the soil, preventing weed emergence and making the germination of weed seeds more difficult (Gerhards and Schappert 2020; Sias et al. 2021). This AS is a highly effective strategy to intercept light, thereby hindering the germination and growth of numerous weed species. Furthermore, the decrease in light intensity is associated with alterations in soil temperature, further contributing to the delayed germination of weeds (Batlla and Benech-Arnold 2014). Weed suppression ability of cover crops depends on biomass production (McKenzie-Gopsill et al. 2022). It is important to choose species suitable for the local conditions. In northern regions, sowing time as early as possible is important to maximize the growing season of cover crops (Toom et al. 2019). In fact, using rye and barley as cover crops reduced weed

density by up to 79% in soybean fields (Weber et al. 2017). Tursun et al. (2018) tested six cover crops (*V. villosa* Roth, *Vicia pannonica* Crantz, Triticale + *V. pannonica*, *Phacelia tanacetifolia* Benth., and *Fagopyrum esculentum* Moench) over five weed species (*Amaranthus retroflexus* L., *Convolvulus arvensis* L., *Tribulus terrestris* L., *Sisymbrium officinale* L. Scop., and *Sorghum halepense* L.) and found a decrease in weed biomass of all treatments when compared to the weeds growing alone. Moreover, as stated by Ranaldo et al. (2021), the mixture of cover crops belonging to four main functional groups with different traits (i) vining growing large-seeded legumes, (ii) erect growing small-seeded legumes, (iii) grasses, and (iv) Brassicaceae, can favour weed management and improve crop production. They tested up to nine mixtures of cover crops belonging to different functional groups, and they found that the combination of these different but complementary traits could improve crop biomass and successful weed suppression in changing agroecosystems. Simultaneously, the use of heterogeneous cover crops can also modify arthropod communities. These animals are the natural predators of pests, so a higher number of arthropods could result in reduced pest populations and their consequent impact on crops, as observed by Gomez et al. (2018) in an olive grove.

Moreover, cover crops positively impact on climate resilience, as they increase soil organic matter, improve soil moisture retention, and enhance water infiltration, reducing the risk of drought and improving water availability for crops (Kaye and Quemada 2017).

Integrating cover crops into crop rotations is essential for maximizing their benefits. Farmers need to carefully plan and select cover crop species based on their specific goals and local conditions and factors such as climate, soil type, and desired ecosystem services. In short, cover crops are a valuable AS that contributes to soil health, weed and pest management, climate resilience, and overall sustainability in agriculture. Farmers can enhance the ecological balance, reduce reliance on synthetic inputs, and promote long-term agricultural productivity by incorporating cover crops into their systems.

3.1.4. Competitive varieties

One of the most important factors reducing agricultural crop yield in farming systems is competition between crops and weeds (Gallandt and Weiner 2015). Weeds can reduce crop productivity by competing for resources, such as water, light, nutrients, and space, affecting crop growth and development, or vice versa, with competitive crops leading to weed decline. Agroecological approaches for weed control aim to manage weed populations while minimizing negative impacts on the environment and crop production (Boutagayout et al. 2023; Boinot et al. 2024). These approaches often focus on enhancing crop competitiveness through crop diversification, cover cropping, optimizing resource use, and screening and selecting crop varieties with enhanced growth or weed control abilities (Sharma et al. 2021). In fact, according to Kunstler et al. (2016) and Khalaf (2019), crop-weed competition can emerge from both root and shoot growth. Accessions with robust initial growth and rapid canopy development can establish quickly in a crop-weed ecosystem, experiencing less susceptibility to the effects of weed competition. Poorter et al. (2012) state that resource competition can profoundly influence biomass acquisition and allocation. Deprivation of vital resources such as light, nutrients, and water can significantly constrain biomass accumulation and alter allocation patterns. Typically, plants experiencing restricted light levels prioritize biomass allocation to stems and leaves, whereas those facing water or nutrient limitations prioritize root allocation (Irving and Mori 2021). This competition phenomenon was investigated by Ringselle et al. (2017), who conducted co-cultivation experiments involving *Elymus repens* (L.) Gould and the weeds *Trifolium pratense* L., which is characterized by large leaf development, and *Lolium perenne* L., known for its extensive root system. Both experiments modified *E. repens* biomass, suggesting that plant species can modify their growth due to competition.

Plant competition also plays a crucial role in soil health by influencing nutrient cycling, microbial activity, and soil structure (Hartman and Tringe 2019). Plants can alter the composition and activity of soil microbial communities when competing for resources, affecting processes like decomposition and nutrient mineralization (Głodowska and

Wozniak 2019). Competition can also lead to changes in root exudation patterns, which can influence soil organic matter accumulation and aggregation. By shaping the distribution of roots and organic inputs in the soil profile, plant competition contributes to soil structure and stability (Lynch et al. 2022).

In short, competitive crops in agroecosystems help suppress weed growth, reduce the need for herbicides, enhance crop productivity (by efficiently using resources and shading out weed species), and contribute to improved soil health and ecosystem resilience (by affecting soil organic matter and soil structure). Competitive crop traits can be improved by adjusting planting density (Lemerle et al. 2013; Borger et al. 2016a), row spacing (Fahad et al. 2015; Borger et al. 2016b), crop orientation, sowing patterns (Olsen et al. 2012; Lemerle et al. 2013) and mixing genotypes of same crop (Lazzaro et al. 2018; Oveisi et al. 2021)

Designing cropping systems that minimize weed competition and maximize crop performance will promote sustainable agroecosystem production.

3.1.5. False seedbed

False seedbed is an AS based on preparing a regular seedbed and allowing the weeds to germinate instead of sowing the crop directly. With this cultural strategy, weeds can be repeatedly controlled before planting or sowing the crop. The false seedbed technique reduces seed bank in the upper layer of the soil, leading to a significant reduction of annual weeds' competition in the succeeding crops or crops (Dierauer et al. 2017). The false seedbed technique and the conventional seedbed differ in their agricultural approach to weed management.

In a conventional seedbed preparation, the soil is tilled, levelled, and prepared for planting the main crop directly. Weed control typically involves pre- or post-emergent herbicide applications to manage weed growth after planting. Moreover, conventional seedbed preparation often involves significant soil disturbance, such as plowing or tilling, to create a suitable environment for seed germination and crop establishment,

which, however, can also inadvertently promote weed seed germination and development (Lavanya et al. 2019)

In contrast, a false seedbed involves preparing the soil for planting, but delaying the sowing of the main crop to allow weed plants to emerge first (Kanas et al. 2020a; 2020b). This AS aims to disturb the soil as little as possible to prevent the germination of weed seeds. Light tillage or minimal disturbance practices are employed to remove existing weeds without promoting new weed growth (Busari et al. 2015; Travlos et al. 2020). In fact, De Cauwer et al. (2019) observed that false seedbed machinery, which did not or minimally disturb the soil, was the most appropriate for preventive control of *Galinsoga quadriradiata* L.

Although some researchers assert that seedbed preparation represents high costs in crop planting, being one of the most energy-consuming strategies (Patil et al. 2009), other researchers defend that the false seedbed technique reduces labour requirements for weeding compared to conventional seedbed (Schutte et al. 2021). By implementing weed control measures before planting, the false seedbed technique can potentially reduce the need for labour-intensive weed management during the crop growth stage, as found by Kanas et al. (2020b), who compared four treatments (direct sowing, direct sowing followed by post-emergence chemical control, false seedbed and false seedbed followed by post-emergence chemical control) and found that dry weight of the weeds *Phalaris minor* Retz. and *Lolium rigidum* Gaud. were between 75–85% and 31–55% lower, respectively, after the treatment with false seedbed. In a recent study with forage crops, Gazoulis et al. (2023) also observed less weed pressure on the crop *Hedysarum coronarium* L. and higher biomass production of the crop after preparing a false seedbed the year before sowing.

3.1.6. Fallow

Fallow refers to an AS in agricultural land management where the field is left uncultivated for a significant period, typically an entire growing season or longer (Żarczyński et al. 2023). Fallow includes *black fallow* that specifically refers to the dark

colour of the soil, which often becomes more fertile and enriched with organic matter over time, and other types of fallow, such as *green* or *natural fallow* in which land is covered with spontaneous herbaceous vegetation which can be grazed and manured by livestock (Güldner et al. 2021).

Fallow has historically been used to restore soil fertility, including chemical, physical and biological improvements, particularly in the soil organic matter and the soil structure, which results in improved belowground organic matter quality and better water use (Styger and Fernandes 2006). Fallow, especially bare fallow, is necessary in many cases to improve the yield of the subsequent crop. As mentioned by Fedyunin et al. (2022), some sunflower cultivars deplete soil moisture and nutrients significantly, while leading to a high seed infestation, rendering it an unfavourable precursor for subsequent crops. Hence, after sunflower cultivation, a fallow period becomes imperative. Furthermore, leaving the land fallow without vegetation is the only viable precursor for winter cereals in arid conditions. These crops efficiently utilize cold-season precipitation, giving them a notable advantage over spring crop yield values (Fedyunin et al. 2022).

Moreover, fallow can also be used together with other AS for weed control; allowing a field to lay fallow interrupts the life cycle of many weed species, impeding their spread. San Martín et al. (2018) tested a two-year rotation of summer fallow (SF) and reduced tillage fallow (RTF) for winter wheat. They found that weed density was lower when winter wheat was sown after RTF, as this method resulted in less competitive weeds. Typically, fallow is combined with mechanical or physical methods that might disrupt the typical succession of weed communities. This disruption could occur through actions such as cutting rhizomes, eliminating weed seedlings in their early stages, and depleting the weed seed bank. As a result, this process can impede the growth of weeds and inhibit their seed production. Over time, the number of viable weed seeds in the soil seedbank decreases, thus stopping the development of weeds and their seed production, which reduces the weed pressure in subsequent crops (Gu et al. 2019). Fallowing also allows natural ecological processes to suppress weed growth. For instance, the enhanced diversity of soil microorganisms, resulting from increased organic matter enrichment, favours the degradation of weed seeds by these

microorganisms. Moreover, the absence of crops can disturb specific weed species' habitat and food sources, ultimately resulting in population decline (Nikolić et al. 2020; Zhong et al. 2023).

The timing and duration of fallow periods may vary depending on local climatic conditions, cropping systems, and other factors. They can be strategically timed to coincide with periods of strong weed pressure or to break weed life cycles, such as fallowing during the wet season to prevent the spread of water-loving weeds or alternating fallow periods with crops susceptible to specific weed species to disrupt weed cycles (Thomsen et al. 2015).

Moreover, some authors as Żarczyński et al. (2022), proposed take benefit of these fallow periods by installing solar panels on fallow land to mitigate the economical losses that can be derived by the lack of cultivation.

3.1.7. Crop seed management

Crop seed management includes a range of practices to ensure the availability, quality, and effective utilization of seeds in agricultural production (Westengen et al. 2023). This strategy includes selecting appropriate varieties, treating seeds to enhance germination, and protecting the seeds against pests, storing seeds properly, testing seed quality before planting, using specialized equipment for planting, ensuring seed certification and quality assurance, and, in some cases, saving and exchanging seeds among farmers. These practices maximize crop yield, uniformity, and resilience to environmental stress (Westengen et al. 2023). There are three commonly used strategies for seed management: special planting dates, high plant density, and the use of high-quality seed material.

Special planting dates refer to strategically chosen times for sowing seeds according to factors such as climate, soil conditions, and crop requirements, which can help farmers to optimize crop growth and development, while minimizing the risks associated with adverse weather conditions, and maximizing yield potential (Domínguez-Hernández et al. 2022). For instance, planting early in the growing season may allow crops to take

advantage of optimal soil moisture and temperature conditions, avoiding drought, while planting later can help avoid potential frost damage or pest pressure (Peterson and Murphy, 2015). For example, Giordano et al. (2018) observed that early sowing of dark red varieties of *Z. mays* resulted in the accumulation of certain bioactive compounds during grain development due to the significant role played by weather conditions such as rainfall and temperature. Special planting dates can also be used for weed management in agriculture. By strategically selecting planting dates, farmers can disrupt the growth cycle of weeds, reduce weed competition with crops, and enhance the effectiveness of weed control measures (Scavo and Mauromicale, 2021). For example, planting crops earlier or later than usual planting windows for specific weed species can help avoid peak germination and emergence periods of weeds, reducing weed pressure during critical crop growth stages (Brown et al. 2022), as seen by Royo-Esnal et al. (2018), who asserted that sowing delay contributed to effective *Bromus diandrus* Roth population decrease, as well as economic income of the winter cereal yield increase. Additionally, planting crops when environmental conditions are less favourable for weed growth, such as during periods of low rainfall or extreme temperatures, can help suppress weed populations naturally (Bahadur 2015).

High plant density refers to planting crops with a greater number of plants per unit area than conventional planting densities (Postma et al. 2021). Increasing plant density can have several benefits, such as enhanced light interception and utilization, increased photosynthesis and high yields, and reduced weed competition through shading and allelopathic effects, which can improve weed control and reduce the need for herbicides while improving resource use efficiency, including water and nutrients (Shah et al. 2008; Kunz et al. 2016). For example, Bourgault et al. (2024) observed that increasing the lentil plant population is a highly effective means of suppressing weed growth and increasing grain yield. Similar results were found by Ahmadvand et al. (2009), who obtained low quantities of *Tribulus terrestris* L., *Eragrostis poaoides* Roem. & Schult, *Portulaca oleracea* L., and *Cynodon dactylon* (L.) Pers. in a high density potato plantation. This technique is closely related to the narrow row planting technique, which involves planting crops closer together in rows, creating a denser canopy that shades weeds and

reduces their ability to germinate and grow (Manalil et al. 2017). It has been reported to be effective not only for controlling weeds, such as *L. rigidum* (Borger et al. 2016a), but also for improving crop yields, as reported by Chauhan et al. (2017), who concluded that cultivating mungbean in narrower row spacing resulted in lower weed biomass and higher grain yield.

Finally, in agroecosystems, high-quality seeds are fundamental drivers for achieving optimal crop yields, sustainability, and resilience. These seeds not only possess superior genetic traits but also exhibit robustness and adaptability to diverse environmental conditions, resulting in seeds genetically pure, free from diseases, and with high germination rates. (Wimalasekera et al. 2015). By ensuring the purity, vigour, and uniformity of plant materials, high-quality seeds promote consistent crop establishment, vigorous growth, and enhanced resistance to biotic and abiotic stresses (Costa et al. 2021). Farmers can secure high-quality seeds either by procuring them from certified seed suppliers or by conserving seeds from their own high-performing crops. This process entails meticulous selection and storage practices, alongside the implementation of strategic planting and proficient crop management techniques. Additionally, it involves executing precise harvesting and drying methods, coupled with careful handling to reduce the risk of damage and contamination prior to storage in designated facilities. (Kameswara et al. 2017)

Integrating these strategies into crop seed management protocols can enhance crop productivity and foster sustainable agricultural systems. This is achieved by improving the efficiency of resource utilization, reducing environmental impacts, and bolstering farm profitability.

3.2. Mechanical and physical strategies

Mechanical and physical AS involve using machinery and physical tools to remove or suppress weeds. These methods include tillage, mulching, solarisation and harrowing, among others. Recent studies have focused on optimizing these practices to reduce the

negative impacts on soil health and increase their efficiency. Seven different and promising mechanical and physical AS are presented (Fig. 3).

3.2.1. Conservation Tillage

Tillage is the process by which soil is physically manipulated using various mechanical methods, such as digging, stirring, and overturning, with the help of tools and implements to alter its structure and composition (Kumar and Kumar 2022). For years, conventional tillage practices have been employed to control weeds and prepare seedbeds. However, nowadays, there is some controversy in using this technique, as it can result in detrimental effects on soil structure, organic matter content, and microbial diversity (Roger-Estrade et al. 2010; Weber et al. 2017). For example, Cabrera-Pérez et al. (2022) observed that conventional tillage in vineyard resulted in harmful effects on soil causing erosion, loss of soil structure and reduction in organic matter and productivity. Therefore, the main tillage technique in AE systems is conservation tillage (CT), which has emerged as a viable alternative that promotes sustainable agricultural practices through the minimization of soil disturbance, reduction of erosion and enhanced water retention, which improves soil health and structure over time (Busari et al. 2015).

Conservation tillage includes zero tillage (ZT), reduced (minimum) tillage, ridge tillage (RT), or contour tillage (COT) (Busari et al. 2015). No-till involves minimal or no soil surface disturbance except during planting. Minimum tillage reduces soil manipulation, typically limited to primary tillage implements. Ridge tillage entails planting crops in rows along or on top of ridges prepared before the cropping season. Contour tillage refers to tillage at right angles to the slope direction. These approaches promote soil conservation, moisture retention, and sustainable agricultural practices (Derpsch et al. 2014; Busari et al. 2015).

Conservation tillage practices play a pivotal role in weed management within agricultural systems. By leaving crop residues on the soil surface or disturbing the soil minimally during planting, CT creates a protective barrier that inhibits weed seed

germination and establishment (Pekrun et al. 2023). Additionally, studies have demonstrated that CT systems effectively suppress seed growth by causing physical damage to weed seeds, disrupting weed seed germination, decreasing viability, and reducing germination potential (Alhammad et al. 2023). Depending on the crop species, mixing different types of tillage can be beneficial for weed management. For example, Alhammad et al. (2023) revealed that CT-rice, together with ZT-wheat, significantly reduced weed emergence, distribution, and biomass, which was attributed to waterlogging that destroys weed habitat, followed by no-tillage, which does not allow underground weed seeds to come to the surface.

CT practices improve soil health by reducing erosion, enhancing soil structure, and increasing organic matter content, which supports stronger crop growth and helps crops outcompete weeds for resources (Khangura et al. 2023). While CT may present some challenges initially with weed control, such as increased weed pressure, its long-term benefits include sustainable weed management and improved ecosystem resilience (Cordeau et al. 2020).

Furthermore, reduced tillage can foster beneficial soil microbial communities contributing to natural pest suppression and nutrient cycling (Tahat et al. 2020). For example, organic farming and CT practices can significantly improve soil biota in globe artichoke grown in clay-loam soils (Leskovar et al. 2018). Additionally, the maintenance of soil cover provided by conservation tillage practices is a physical barrier to weed emergence. Weber et al. (2017) observed that reduced tillage resulted in a reduction of 85% of weed growth and the highest soybean crop yields compared to conventional tillage and no-tillage.

3.2.2. Mulching

Mulching involves covering the soil with a layer of living or dead material, which can be organic matter such as straw, compost, leaves, or cut grass (Iqbal et al. 2020); synthetic mulches like black plastic that must be removed at the end of the season (Amare and Desta 2021) or biodegradable foils (Abbate et al. 2023); or small cover crops grown

simultaneously with and near cash crops, called living mulches (Bashkar et al. 2021). Mulching offers various benefits, such as weed suppression, moisture retention, soil temperature regulation, erosion prevention, nutrient cycling, and enhanced soil structure (Khan et al. 2022). Living mulching is generally more effective for weed control than non-living mulching, as it can suppress weeds throughout the growing season. In contrast, non-living mulches, like cover crop residues, are more efficient at preventing weed seed germination and smothering very young weeds (Westbrook et al. 2022).

Various studies have consistently demonstrated the effectiveness of different mulching techniques for weed management. Asif et al. (2020) compared manual hoeing, plastic, rice straw, sawdust, and wheat straw mulches in maize cultivation and found that plastic and wheat straw mulches significantly increased plant height, grain yield, and harvest index compared to control plots. Wheat straw mulch also improved soil organic matter and carbon content, while manual hoeing, transparent, and rice straw mulches showed the lowest weed density and dry weight. Similarly, barley mulching enhanced tomato yields while controlling surrounding weeds (Campiglia et al. 2015), and rice straw mulches improved plant height and leaf count in *Stevia* plants (Taak et al. 2021). Mahmood et al. (2016) demonstrated the effectiveness of mixed mulches using chaffed herbage of sorghum, sunflower, rice, and maize in reducing weed density and biomass in maize fields. Living mulching of dyers woad (*Isatis tinctoria* L.) with leek (*Allium porrum* L.) grown in Denmark, and living mulching of broad sowed burr medic (*Medicago polymorpha* L., var. *anglona*) with cauliflower (*Brassica oleracea* L. var. *botrytis*) grown in Italy, resulted in effective weed management with no dependence on location leek, as dyers woad in Denmark, and cauliflower with broad sowed burr medic in Italy, effectively managed weeds regardless of location (Ciaccia et al. 2017).

Figure 3. Examples of mechanical and physical agroecological strategies. (A) mulching; (B) Vermicompost application; (C) Mowing; (D) Solarization. Credits: (A) Ronstik, (B) AnSyvanych, (C) Galina St, and (D) Ploeg.

Changes in incident solar radiation due to mulching can influence soil temperature, potentially delaying weed germination (Batlla and Benech-Arnold 2014). Water availability can be altered through transpiration, affecting shallow-rooted weeds more than deeper-rooted crops (Westbrook et al. 2022). Also, mulching can help maintain optimal moisture content, creating favourable conditions for soil organisms' activity and enhancing soil enzyme activity, soil biota diversity, and crop productivity in agroecological systems. Mulching reduces moisture evaporation from the soil and maintains a more constant soil temperature, which is crucial for crop growth and yield (Choudhary et al. 2018; El-Beltagi et al. 2022). Organic mulches eventually decompose and add organic material to the soil, improving soil fertility and structure (Prem et al. 2020). Both, weed suppression and main crop yield can be enhanced by carefully selecting suitable living mulches and implementing management practices that leverage the morphological, physiological, and developmental distinctions among main crops, living mulches, and weeds (Verret et al. 2017).

Mulching is particularly suitable for agroecological systems because it controls weeds, enhances soil health and structure, fosters beneficial microbiota, and increases crop

yields. For all these reasons, mulching can effectively reduce reliance on chemical inputs, aligning with sustainable agricultural principles.

3.2.3. Solarization

Solarization is a weed management technique that uses solar radiation and clear plastic to heat the soil and control weed species, mainly annual weeds (Frillman 2019). Solarization involves covering an irrigated area of soil with clear plastic during the warmest months of the season, which traps solar energy. Thanks to the vapour formed under the plastic, the temperature of the soil rises to levels that can kill weeds and also other pests in the agricultural field. Gill et al. (2017) noted that transparent polyethylene plastics from 50.8 to 101.6 μm may increase soil temperatures up to 54 °C in the 0-5 cm layer, reducing weed emergence by 45-78%. The heat generated under the plastic helps kill weed seeds, seedlings, and some soilborne pests in the top few inches of soil without leaving toxic residues in the soil and being unharmed for beneficial microbes present in the soil (Kapoor, 2020). Solarization can be effective in controlling many annual and some perennial weeds. For example, Samani et al. (2017) found a significant reduction in weed density after covering the soil with a clear polyethylene tarp for 6 weeks. Although they did not find any significant difference between 4 and 6 weeks solarization time, Kapoor (2020) found that the inhibitory effect on weeds increased as the duration of solarization increased, finding stronger weed inhibition after 8 weeks of soil solarization, followed by 6 and 4 weeks, and even higher productivity in the annual crop *Abelmoschus esculentus* Moench. Similarly, after covering the soil of an archaeological site with clear plastic, Kanellou et al. (2023) obtained 100% weed control during the first two months and a 90% during the following months. Similar results were found in the experiment of Muthumanickam and Anburani (2019), who controlled weed density and improved *Beta vulgaris* L. yield after using a 50 μm clear plastic on the soil.

In addition, the generated heat not only effectively controls weeds but also can have a positive impact on crop productivity. This was observed by Pereira et al. (2023), who concluded that the improved yields in lettuce using solarization were attributed to the

control of certain soil pathogens, enhanced root development, and increased nutrient availability due to higher soil temperatures (Singh et al. 2012; Bajwa et al. 2015). This is in concordance with the study of Safdar et al. (2021), which showed that N, P, K, and organic matter in the soil gradually increased with longer solarization times. The content of these minerals peaked after 12 weeks of solarization, coinciding with maximum weed control and an increase in sesame yield. This mechanism entails reducing the use of herbicides and other pesticides, making solarization a low-cost method. Additionally, polyethylene plastics can be reused, further enhancing their cost-effectiveness.

New studies are being done to search for new, inexpensive, and non-hazardous materials for solarization, such as the use of paraffin-wax emulsion or different types of biochar to cover the soil during solarization (Al-Kayssi and Al-Karaghoulis 2002; Hasan 2018). These new materials are slowly appearing to replace the use of plastic in solarization and avoid the post-treatment pollution related to plastic materials.

3.2.4. Thermal weed control

Although the previously mentioned physical methods (mulching and solarization) are considered preventive measures (Scavo and Mauromicale 2020), other thermal weed control methods such as flaming, hot water, steam, or freezing can be used in the early stages of weed growth. These methods have been reported to be more effective against young, dicotyledonous, erect, and broadleaf weeds (Pannacci et al. 2017; Mía et al. 2020; Monteiro and Santos 2022). Among these methods, flaming is the most popular mechanical approach. Flaming involves controlled flames typically generated by propane burners mounted on equipment that can be pulled or pushed through the field (Radicetti 2012). These flames can reach temperatures up to 1.900 °C, causing damage to the weed's cellular structure, leading to loss of cell function and ultimately plant death or severe damage. As a result, the weed's ability to compete with the crop is significantly reduced, often resulting in the weed's inability to survive beyond 2 to 3 days after the treatment (Fennimore et al. 2016; Scavo and Mauromicale 2020).

This method was found to be very effective against weeds. Stepanovic et al. (2016) found 70%, 88% and 90% weed control using different flaming methods such as broadcast, full, and banded, respectively. Dress and Balah (2016) determined that a flame speed of 0.6 km h⁻¹, the highest gas pressure (2 bar), and a flaming height of 15 cm was the best combination to manage narrow and broadleaf weeds, which are more easily controlled, with this method, than perennial weeds. Similar results were obtained by Kanellou et al. (2017), who asserted that annual broadleaf weeds were better controlled after flaming with propane than grasses and perennial broadleaf species.

However, there are some environmental aspects to be considered, as flaming could affect the emission of greenhouse gases due to combustion (Verma et al. 2023). Nevertheless, when compared to traditional weed management methods, the environmental impact of flaming can be considered low because (i) thermal weed control does not cause water, soil and therefore food contamination, which is caused by the use of herbicides, (ii) the use of this AS does not lead to weed resistance as herbicides do, which saves on the repetition of the method, and (iii) thermal weed control methods do not contribute to greenhouse gas emissions associated with the production, transport, and application of chemical inputs like fertilizers and pesticides, which are major contributors to agricultural emissions (Panhwar et al. 2019; Verma et al. 2023). By minimizing reliance on chemical inputs and reducing energy consumption, thermal weed control methods have the potential to mitigate greenhouse gas emissions associated with agricultural production, contributing to more sustainable and environmentally friendly farming practices.

3.2.5. Harrowing

Harrowing is a widely used mechanical weed control method that helps manage weed populations while minimizing the need for synthetic herbicides in agroecological systems. This AS involves mechanically disturbing the soil surface to uproot or bury weeds, disrupt weed seedlings, and prevent their growth (Peruzzi et al. 2017). Harrowing is usually done with specialized equipment such as brush hoes or weeders

harrows, and its timing and intensity depend on factors such as crop type, weed species, and soil conditions (Bručienė et al. 2022). This method is particularly effective for controlling small weeds before becoming established and can compete with crops for resources like nutrients, water, and sunlight (Hussain et al. 2018). Aikins and Afuaka (2012) obtained the lowest weed density, the highest dry cob weight, and the highest values of 1000-seed weight in a maize yield after disc harrowing treatment compared to disc ploughing only or not tillage. Soybean fields that include harrowing and hoeing as mechanical weed control methods resulted in 82% weed control efficiency and a 34% yield increase, compared to untreated control (Weber et al. 2016). However, harrowing has some constraints as the response to weed harrowing varies depending on the specific crop mixture, timing, and intensity of harrowing. While some mixtures show resilience and ability to recover from harrowing without significant yield penalties, others may experience decreased yield if harrowing is applied at certain growth stages or with high intensity. Additionally, the effectiveness of harrowing on weed control may vary across different crop mixtures and may not always correlate with increased crop yield or improved grain quality. Therefore, it is essential to consider the specific characteristics of the crop mixture and the timing of harrowing to optimize weed control and minimize potential negative impacts on crop yield and quality (Ogórek et al. 2019; Sobkowicz et al. 2020; Tendziagolska et al. 2022).

Unlike chemical herbicides, which may pose environmental and health risks, harrowing is an environmentally friendly weed management approach that avoids synthetic herbicides. This mechanical weed control method is commonly integrated into organic farming practices as part of an integrated weed management strategy, aligning with sustainable agriculture principles and environmental stewardship.

3.2.6. Vermicompost application

Vermicompost, a nutrient-rich organic fertilizer produced through the process of composting organic materials with the assistance of earthworms, is a common practice in agroecological farming due to its numerous benefits for soil health and plant growth

(Mistry 2015; Ahmed et al. 2022). Regarding weed management, while vermicompost itself might not directly suppress weeds, it can indirectly contribute to weed management through several mechanisms. Vermicompost improves soil structure and fertility, enhancing the overall health of the soil (Kumar et al. 2018). Healthy soils promote stronger and more competitive crop growth, which can help suppress weed growth by outcompeting resources such as water and nutrients, ultimately reducing weed pressure in agricultural fields (Şahin et al. 2018). Hasan et al. (2018) obtained longer carrot plants after using vermicompost. As well, Kamaleshwaran and Elayaraja (2021) obtained improved soil fertility, crop productivity and nutrient uptake in rice fields, and Aslam et al. (2019) observed that applying vermicompost to wheat fields improved crop yield and soil health, resulting in longer plants. Ceritoğlu and Erman (2020) also obtained the highest seed yield of lentils after applying vermicompost.

Vermicompost contains beneficial microorganisms that can suppress soil-borne pathogens, which could contribute to weed growth and promote a healthy soil microbiome that can create a less-favourable environment for weed proliferation. For instance, Aslam et al. (2018) found a reduction in insect infestation after adding vermicompost to the wheat, and Mistry (2015) confirmed that vermicompost is also an effective method to control plant pathogen and pests, as suppressing soil and foliar-transmitted plant diseases, such as *Pythium*, *Rhizoctonia*, *Plectosporium*, and *Verticillium*. Vermicompost application can also help reduce water runoff and improve water-use efficiency, improve soil quality, increase nutrient availability, boost crop productivity, and enhance pest and disease tolerance in agroecological systems (Oyege et al. 2023). Vermicompost is a sustainable alternative to synthetic fertilizers, which promotes the circular economy, and reduces the need for external inputs in agroecological farming.

3.2.7. Mowing

Mowing is a fundamental mechanical weed control strategy in agroecosystems. This AS involves regularly cutting weeds and unwanted vegetation using diverse mowing

equipment such as lawn-mowers, brush cutters, or tractor-mounted mowers (Abdulai, 2018). By cutting down weeds to ground level or below, the weed biomass is effectively reduced, limiting seed production and disrupting weed growth cycles, which prevent weed seed banks in the soil, contributing to long-term weed management strategies (Donald, 2006). Abdulai (2018) asserted the efficacy of between-row mowing in managing weeds in soybean fields, as this technique can remove weeds close to the ground without touching the crop. However, weed species vary in their response to mowing frequency and mowing height, as studied by Butlet et al. (2013), who evaluated the effect of mowing frequency and mowing height on four summer annual weed species (large crabgrass (*Digitaria sanguinalis* (L.) Scop.), barnyard grass (*Echinochloa crus-galli* L.), giant ragweed (*Ambrosia trifida* L.), and common lambsquarters (*Chenopodium album* L.) finding that repeated mowing resulted in limited weed growth and seed reproduction.

Furthermore, mowing promotes the growth and vigour of desirable vegetation by reducing competition for resources such as light, water, and nutrients. It can also enhance biodiversity and habitat quality by maintaining diverse plant communities and providing refuge for beneficial insects and wildlife (Donald 2006).

3.2.8. Laser and electrical weeding

Laser and electrical weeding are advanced, eco-friendly weed control technologies that provide effective alternatives to traditional chemical herbicides. Laser weeding uses high-precision lasers to identify and target weeds burning their tissues without harming nearby crops (Andreasen et al. 2022). There are three types of laser that has been used for weed control: the carbon dioxide laser (CO₂ laser) (Heisel et al. 2001, 2002), the diode laser (Wöltjen et al. 2008), and the fiber laser (Coleman et al. 2021). This method reduce chemical use, minimizes soil disturbance, and is particularly effective in fields with herbicide-resistant weeds due to its applicability in specific spots (Rakhmatulin et al. 2021). For example, laser weeding has proven successful against *L. rigidum* Gaud. (annual ryegrass) (Coleman et al. 2021), *Alopecurus myosuroides* Huds (black-grass) and

B vulgaris (sugar beet) (Andreasen et al. 2024), which are common in agricultural fields and difficult to manage with herbicides. Electrical weeding, on the other hand, uses high-voltage electricity to pass an electric current through the weeds, disrupting their cellular structure and causing them to dehydrate and die (Zhang et al. 2024). The technology for electric weed control can apply the electrical current to plants through two methods: spark-discharge or continuous electrode–plant contact (Slaven et al. 2023). Schreier et al. (2022) found that electric weed control not only can damage the seedlings but also reduced weed seed viability by 54% to 80% in *E. crus-galli*, *Xanthium strumarium* L. (cocklebur), *Ambrosia artemisiifolia* L. (common ragweed), *Setaria faberi* L. (giant bristleglass), *Ambrosia trifida* L. (giant ragweed), *Setaria pumila* L. (yellow foxtail), and *Amaranthus tuberculatus* L. (tall waterhemp). Both methods help maintain soil health and avoid chemical residues, making them ideal for sustainable and organic farming. These technologies offer versatile, efficient weed management solutions, particularly in integrated weed management systems where diverse approaches are combined for optimal control.

3.3. Biological and biotechnological AS

Biological and biotechnological weed control strategies use living organisms or biotechnological tools to manage weeds. Biological control relies on the use of an agent, a combination of agents, or biological processes to induce weed suppression. Research has shown promising results in using bioherbicides, which are derived from natural compounds, to target and control specific weed species selectively (Uludag et al. 2018).

3.3.1 Allelopathy

As previously mentioned, allelopathy, defined by Rice in 1984, includes both inhibitory and stimulatory effects of one plant on another through the release of chemical compounds called allelochemicals (Fig. 4), which can reach the other plants by root exudation, volatilization, microbial transformation or leaching from leaves. This plant–plant interaction can be directly or indirectly driven by soil microbial transformation of

the allelochemical compounds released by plants to the soil. In agroecosystems, allelopathy influences various interactions between plants and other organisms, contributing significantly to the ecosystem’s dynamics (Aslam et al. 2017). The release of allelochemicals into the soil can interfere with the microbiota, inhibiting or stimulating somewhat specific microbial populations (Xiao et al. 2020), which can affect surrounding plants or affect the structure and moisture of the soil.

Figure 4. Methods of release of allelochemicals from allelopathic plants and its effects on surrounding plants.

Allelopathy is driven by plant-specialised metabolites that have been evolutionarily selected for thousands of years to help plants to survive in the ecosystem. This plethora of natural compounds can control the presence of other organisms in the ecosystem, natural or agricultural, establishing complex multi-trophic interactions, including weed-to-weed control. Therefore, AE can take advantage of this group of compounds already in the plants for their “use” in weed control. That is why allelopathy has been increasingly studied in the agroecosystems since the late 20th century. Many major crops, such as rice (*Oryza sativa* L.), wheat (*Triticum sp.*), sunflower (*Helianthus sp.*), maize (*Z. mays*), canola (*Brassica napus* L.), millet (*Pennisetum glaucum* L.), and buckwheat (*Fagopyrum sp.*), can manage surrounding weeds through these chemical compounds. For example, wheat has shown potential for managing dicot and monocot weeds, such as *L. rigidum* and *P. oleracea* through root exudation (Wu et al. 2000; Vieites-

Álvarez et al. 2023a); sunflower leaf extracts with allelochemical compounds induced significant inhibitory effects on germination and plant length of *Bidens pilosa* L. (Makaza et al. 2022); rice also showed inhibitory effects on germination percentage, root length, and dry matter of *E. crus-galli* (L.) Beauv. (Rahaman et al. 2021); and recently, Szwed et al. (2020) showed that a very low percentage (1%) of the aqueous extract of 14-day buckwheat plants was able to inhibit root development of wild oat (*Avena fatua* L.), yellow foxtail (*Setaria glauca* (L.) P. Beauv.), barnyard grass (*E. crus-galli*), common windgrass (*Apera spica-venti* (L.) P. Beauv.), and catchweed bedstraw (*Galium aparine* L.) due to the allelochemicals present in the aqueous extract. Also, cereal rye (*Secale cereale* L.) has shown to suppress weeds by means of allelopathic compounds (Tabaglio et al. 2013; Silva and Bagavathiannan 2023). The allelopathic properties of crops can be exploited in other methods previously mentioned in this review for sustainable weed management, such as cover cropping, intercropping, mulching, etc. (Farooq et al. 2020). Even Hussain et al. (2022) showed that wheat plants exuded more allelopathic compounds to the field when crop and weed plants were at the same density than when crop plants number was higher than the number of weed plants, which supports the agroecological principle of biodiversity, as wheat did not see weeds as a threat as long as their density was lower than that of wheat. Also, allelopathic plants can distinguish between competitor and collaborator neighbours, adjusting their allelochemical production accordingly, which can shape plant communities to control invasive species (Kong et al. 2018).

However, the allelopathic potential varies among crop species and even among different genotypes of the same crop, so screening and selecting the stronger allelopathic genotypes is a step towards a more sustainable agriculture. This is supported by the research of Vieites-Álvarez et al. (2024), who compared the allelopathic potential of up to 30 different buckwheat genotypes obtaining very diverse allelopathic potentials in front of monocot and dicot weeds.

In short, the economic benefits of allelopathy in agriculture are multifaceted. By selecting allelopathic crops, farmers can reduce their reliance on synthetic herbicides, leading to cost savings associated with herbicide purchases and application.

Additionally, using allelopathic crops for cover crops can suppress weed growth, reducing the need for manual weeding or mechanical weed control measures, which can be labour-intensive and costly. Furthermore, allelopathic plants can enhance soil health and fertility, improving farm productivity. So, integrating allelopathic plants into agricultural systems can contribute to sustainable weed management practices while offering economic benefits to farmers.

3.3.2. Plant essential oils

Plant essential oils (EO) are increasingly recognized for their potential contribution to AE. These oils, known for their volatility, derive from plants specialised metabolites, are species-dependent, have a lipophilic chemical structure, and can be present in glandular hairs or plant cell walls. EO are present in various plant organs, including bark, leaves, stems, flowers, roots, and fruits (Chen et al. 2019). EO comprise compounds like nitrogen-containing compounds, phenolic acids, monoterpenes and sesquiterpenes, constituting intricate blends of specialised metabolites (Chen et al. 2019). These oils, derived from various plant organs, have bioactive constituents that exhibit the ability to impede weed or pests' proliferation (Verdeguer et al. 2020a). EO's phytotoxic effects have been widely demonstrated, i.e., *Carlina acaulis* L. and *Calotropis procera* Aiton. EOs were very effective in controlling *B. pilosa* L. (Al-Rowaily et al. 2020; Álvarez-Rodríguez et al. 2023); *Foeniculum vulgare* Mill. EO induced a decrease in germination and growth of *P. oleracea* and *A. retroflexus* (Gharibvandia et al. 2022). *Juniperus sabina* L. EO affected significantly the development of *Melilotus officinalis* L., *Trigonella bessaeriana* Ser., and *Myosotis arvensis* (L.) (Semerdjieva et al. 2022); the EO from above ground parts of *Pulicaria somalensis* O. Hoffm. exhibited inhibitory potential against the weeds *Dactyloctenium aegyptium* (L.) Willd. and *B. pilosa*; and different concentrations of *Thymbra capitata* (L.) Cav. EO inhibited the germination and seedling growth of different weeds, such as *Erigeron canadensis* L., *Sonchus oleraceus* L., *C. album*, *Setaria verticillata* (L.) P.Beauv., *A. fatua* L., *Solanum nigrum* L., *A. retroflexus*, *P. oleracea*, and *E. crus-galli* (Verdeguer et al. 2020b). For a deep review of the phytotoxic potential of essential oils see Verdeguer et al. (2020a).

Moreover, essential oils have effectively repelled or eliminated pests and pathogens, thereby reducing reliance on synthetic chemicals for pest and disease management (Raveau et al. 2020). For example, the EO of *Angelica archangelica* L. showed antifungal activity against some species of *Fusarium* sp., *Botrytis cinerea*, and *Alternaria solani* (Fraternale et al. 2016), while EO derived from turmeric (*Curcuma longa* L.) showed efficiency in vivo and in vitro against *Aspergillus flavus* (Hu et al. 2017).

Their low environmental impact and minimal toxicity make EOs ecologically sound alternatives in agroecosystems, thereby fostering sustainable agricultural practices to manage weeds (Spada et al. 2021). Their high phytotoxic activity and ability to affect several targets at the same time, make EOs a new avenue for the development of new bioherbicides (Verdeguer et al. 2020a).

3.3.3. Isolated natural bioactive compounds

Natural bioactive compounds derived from plants, microbes, or other organisms offer promising solutions for various applications in AE. These compounds possess biological activities that can be beneficial for weed suppression, pest management, disease control, and soil health improvement (Singh and Yadav 2020). Natural biocides often exhibit insecticidal, fungicidal, bactericidal, nematocidal, and herbicidal properties, emerging as valuable alternatives to synthetic chemicals in agricultural practices (Thiviya et al. 2022). Most recent research shows the bioherbicidal potential of these plant specialised metabolites. For example, Araniti et al. (2018) demonstrated the ability of the phenolic rosmarinic acid to induce programmed cell death in *Arabidopsis thaliana* (L.) Heynh seedlings by inducing oxidative burst and, concomitantly, mitochondrial dysfunction. Recently, López-González et al. (2023) and Álvarez-Rodríguez et al. (2023) showed that the bioactive compounds *trans*-cinamaldehyde and harmaline respectively induced morphological changes and inhibited plant growth of *A. thaliana*. As well, Graña et al. (2017) and López-González et al. (personal communication) found auxin-like effects on *Arabidopsis* cell structure and morphology of the natural compounds scopoletin and pelargonic acid, respectively, suggesting their valuable use as auxinic

bioherbicides. Promising results were also found for the compounds chalcone (Díaz-Tielas et al. 2014), citral (Graña et al. 2013; 2016), and norharmane (López-González et al. 2020), which induced not only strong reduction on the development of the model plant *A. thaliana*, but also on crop-associated weeds, showing the potential specificity of plant natural compounds when used in specific agroecosystems. Interesting are also the field studies of Muñoz et al. (2022) and Torres-Pagán (2024), which showed the herbicidal ability of pelargonic acid and the terpenoids carvacrol, thymol, eugenol, and citral to manage weeds under field conditions.

Some plant-based bioherbicidases are already on the market, such as Beloukha (BELCHIM), Herbistop (COMPO), and MiSSiTO® (AlphaBio) with pelargonic acid as main active ingredient, GreenMatch™ and Avenger® Weed Killer from *Citrus* sp., Weed Slayer® and Weedzap® from *Syzygium aromaticum* (L.) Merr., or fast acting weed killer Concentrate (AVENGER Products), based on a combination of more than one plant natural compound. For a deep review of commercialized bioherbicides, see Hasan et al. (2021).

Natural bioactive compounds are biodegradable and typically have a low environmental impact, aligning with sustainable agriculture principles and ecological stewardship (Singh and Mirza 2020). Ongoing research aims to explore the potential of these compounds, optimize their efficacy, develop novel formulations, and integrate them into holistic agroecological approaches for resilient and environmentally friendly farming systems.

3.3.4. Use of animals (i.e., herbivorous)

The use of animals in AE includes various practices that promote sustainable and holistic farming systems, integrating livestock such as cattle, sheep, goats, poultry, and insects into agricultural landscapes to enhance soil fertility, pest control, and nutrient cycling (Dumont et al. 2018). For example, rotational grazing systems involve moving livestock through different paddocks to mimic natural grazing patterns, improving soil health, and reducing weed pressure (Badgery et al. 2017; Byrnes et al. 2018). According to Sarabi

(2019), seed predation is an important way to suppress weed seeds from agricultural ecosystems. Chauhan et al. (2010) noted a significant decrease in the abundance of weed seeds on the soil surface in fields with high populations of invertebrates, particularly fire ants (*Solenopsis geminata*). Similarly, Ichihara et al. (2021) demonstrated that an increase in cricket density led to a reduction in the emergence of seedlings of *Lolium multiflorum* Lam. The use of animals in AE extends to practices like agroforestry, where trees and shrubs are integrated with crops and livestock to create diverse and resilient ecosystems (Wilson et al. 2016). Animal manure and compost from livestock provide valuable organic matter and nutrients for soil fertility, reducing the reliance on synthetic fertilizers (Loss et al. 2019). Furthermore, pollinators such as bees and other beneficial insects play essential roles in crop pollination and ecosystem biodiversity, contributing to sustainable food production (Isaacs et al. 2017). Overall, the judicious integration of animals into agroecological systems can enhance ecological balance, increase agricultural productivity, and promote environmental sustainability.

3.4. Green digitalization of agriculture

Green digitalization in agriculture refers to integrating digital technologies and data-driven approaches to promote environmental sustainability, resource efficiency, and climate resilience in agricultural practices. It encompasses a wide range of technologies and applications to optimise resource use, reduce environmental impact, and improve the overall sustainability of agricultural production systems. Key aspects include precision agriculture, smart farming systems, data analytics for informed decision-making, supply chain transparency, and climate-smart practices. This transformative shift toward sustainability empowers farmers to optimize productivity while minimizing environmental impact and addressing challenges like climate change and food security (Gebresenbet et al. 2023).

Figure 5. Drone obtaining high-resolution aerial imagery. Credit: Ekkasit919.

3.4.1. Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs)

Drones, unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), have obtained significant attention in recent years as tools transforming precision agriculture (PA). UAVs offer farmers access to high-resolution aerial imagery and multispectral data in an autonomous way operated through sensors, microprocessors and electronic gadgets, facilitating tasks like crop growth monitoring, stress detection, disease identification, environmental surveillance and yield estimation (Maes and Steppe 2019; Mohsan et al. 2022). Drones can vary their configuration and mechanisms including the speed, weight and operation covering large areas efficiently, thus offering timely information for better decision-making (Fig. 5). Equipped with thermal sensors, they can detect temperature variations and water stress. There are two main types: fixed-wing airplanes and rotary-motor helicopters. Fixed-wing drones have higher speeds and cover larger areas, while rotary motor drones are more versatile but have limited battery life (Mohsan et al. 2022; Nath 2023).

Esposito et al. (2021) reviewed the use of drones for the identification of both monocot and dicot weeds such as *A. palmeri*, *C. album*, *C. arvense*, *Phalaris* spp., *Avena* spp., and *Lolium* spp. in the most cultivated crops worldwide such as *Triticum* spp., *H. vulgare*, *B. vulgaris*, and *Z. mays*. The rapid and specific identification of weeds using UAVs, enables farmers to precisely target and treat weed-infested areas, reducing herbicide usage, minimizing environmental impact, and optimizing crop yields. Additionally, drones offer

the advantage of accessibility, allowing for quick and cost-effective weed monitoring and management across large agricultural areas.

3.4.2. Variable Rate Technology (VRT)

Variable Rate Technology (VRT) is a precision agriculture practice that enables farmers to vary the rate of application of inputs such as fertilizers, pesticides, and seeds across different areas of their fields based on spatial variability and crop requirements (Ahmad and Mahdi 2018). Instead of applying inputs uniformly, VRT utilizes data-driven approaches to tailor application rates based on specific conditions within the field. These data may include information on soil characteristics, nutrient levels, crop health, and yield potential, collected through various technologies such as GPS, sensors, drones, and satellite imagery (Ahmad and Mahdi 2018).

By integrating data from soil maps, yield maps, and other sources, and optimizing input application according to the unique needs of different areas within a field, farmers can create prescription maps that guide VRT equipment to apply inputs at optimal rates maximizing resource efficiency, minimize input waste, and improve overall crop performance (Karunathilake et al. 2023). VRT can be used for seeding, weed control, applying fertilizers such as phosphorus or nitrogen (Ahmad and Mahdi 2018). For example, Song et al. (2021) developed a variable-rate fertilizer control system applied to a UAV-based granular fertilizer spreader to automatically adjust the fertilizer application rate based on a prescription map area. This allows for more targeted and efficient use of resources, reducing input costs, minimizing environmental impact, and optimizing crop yields.

3.4.3 Weed map

Weed mapping is a sophisticated tool that harnesses a technology-driven approach to weed management. This AS involves mapping the distribution and density of weeds within a field (Parket 2018). This process typically involves two phases. First, data collection on weed population across the field. This data can be gathered through

remote sensing (satellite imagery and aerial drones equipped with cameras capture high-resolution images of the field), ground-based sensors (sensors mounted on vehicles or handheld devices can measure parameters such as weed biomass, leaf area index, or chlorophyll content, providing quantitative data on weed density and distribution), and GPS (Global Positioning System) technology, which is used to precisely geolocate weed infestations within the field, allowing for accurate mapping of weed distribution (Pallotino et al. 2019; Quamar et al. 2023). Then, once collected, the data is processed and analysed to create a visual representation of weed distribution, often referred to as a "weed map", which involves image processing, classification algorithms and spatial analysis (Quamar et al. 2023). The prompt detection of weed infestations in aerial imagery allows the development of site-specific weed management (SSWM) strategies, leading to significant herbicide savings, reduced environmental impact, and increased crop yield (Sa et al. 2018). For example, Pantazi et al. (2017) used remote sensing for mapping *Silybum marianum* (L.) Gaertn among other vegetation in a field with *Avena sterilis* L. being predominant, using a multispectral camera (green-red.NIR) and a UAV for the acquisition of high-resolution images. However, it can also be used for pest management, as shown by Herrmann et al. (2018), who experimented with two spectrometer systems mounted on a moving platform at ground level to detect non-visual soybean foliage symptoms induced by *Fusarium virguliforme*.

This map helps farmers identify areas of the field with high weed pressure, allowing for targeted weed control interventions. The map can also inform decisions about bioherbicide application, cultivation practices, or other weed management strategies.

3.4.4 Site-specific application of herbicides or bioherbicides

Site-specific or sectorised application of herbicides or bioherbicides involves precisely targeting these substances to specific weed-infested areas within a field rather than applying them uniformly across the entire field (Pavlović et al. 2022). As explained before, this targeted approach begins with farmers identifying weed hotspots through advanced mapping techniques such as remote sensing or GPS mapping (Pavlović et al.

2022). Once weed-infested areas are identified, precision agriculture technologies, such as GPS-guided sprayers, come into play, as the robot used by Khan et al. (2018) in a corn field, which could detect the weeds and kill them by spraying with a GPS control system, image processing detector, and a spray control system, which was very effective controlling weeds. These sophisticated systems enable farmers to accurately deliver herbicides or bioherbicides to the targeted locations with precision and efficiency. Farmers can minimize herbicide usage while maximizing effectiveness, reducing environmental impact, and optimizing resource utilization by focusing herbicide application on areas with the highest weed pressure.

The site-specific application approach offers several benefits. Firstly, the overall herbicide is reduced, leading to cost savings for farmers and reducing the environmental footprint associated with the chemical inputs (Gerhards et al. 2022). Secondly, farmers can achieve more effective weed management outcomes by concentrating weed control efforts where they are most needed, resulting in healthier crops and higher yields (Gerhards et al. 2022). Additionally, by integrating site-specific applications into broader integrated pest management (IPM) strategies, farmers can adopt a holistic approach to weed control that combines chemical, cultural, biological, and mechanical methods. This alignment with sustainable agricultural practices promotes long-term environmental stewardship and resilience while reducing reliance on chemical inputs.

In essence, *in-situ* application represents a targeted, efficient, and environmentally sustainable approach to weed management, taking advantage of advanced technologies and integrated pest management principles to optimize weed control efforts while minimizing environmental impact and maximizing agricultural productivity.

4. COMBINED AGROECOLOGICAL STRATEGIES

The latest literature on AS for weed control highlights the importance of integrating multiple strategies to achieve effective and sustainable weed management approaches (Riemens et al. 2022; Benaragama et al. 2024). The combination of cultural, mechanical, and biological methods is more successful in reducing weed populations and minimizing

herbicide use than relying solely on a single strategy (Monteiro and Santos, 2022). For example, allelopathic varieties are commonly used with other weed management methods, as the allelochemicals present in plant tissues and the possibility to release them to the medium enhance the effects over weeds. Vrignon-Brenas et al. (2018) observed that intercropping the allelopathic crop wheat with white clover resulted in decreased weed shoot dry matter with improved wheat yields and protein content. Shahzad et al. (2021a) compared different crop rotations (fallow-wheat, rice-wheat, cotton-wheat, mungbean-wheat and sorghum-wheat) with different AS such as false seedbed and allelopathic water extracts obtaining reductions of more than 50% of weed density. They propose planting wheat after mungbean (*Vigna radiata* (L.) R. Wilczek) for better wheat yields. Jodaugine et al. (2018) used different allelopathic mulches to assess their effects over the germination and growth of *Raphanus sativus* L., *Daucus sativus* Röhl., and *Lactuca sativa* L. obtaining diverse results depending on the mulch and the target cultivar, being the grass mulches at 1:10 concentration the most effective. Sturm et al. (2018) evaluated the effects of six different cover crop species over three weeds in the presence or absence of active carbon (used as an adsorbent for allelopathic substances in the soil). They found that the effects over the weeds were minimised when the carbon adsorbed the allelochemicals, suggesting its importance in weed management.

Scavo and Mauromicale (2021) assert that cover cropping, mulching, intercropping, and green manuring are often indicated as distinct and separate techniques. However, they can be considered synonymous with slight modifications due to the similar mode of action derived from allelochemicals. Brooker et al. (2015) observed that by increasing the diversity of the soil's microbial population and facilitating the transport of allelochemicals into the soil, intercropping could improve the allelopathic weed–cover crop interactions and, as a result, the phytotoxic effects. These techniques can be blended or drawn on each other; for example, Vicent-Cabout et al. (2019) reviewed the use of mulches coming from cover crops to obtain better production in maize and soybean. To join these techniques, a special machine, the roller crimper, is used to cut the cover crops, creating a dense layer of plant residues (i.e., mulch) connected to the

soil by the roots and conserving soil moisture, reducing erosion, and suppressing weed growth (Navarro-Miró et al. 2019).

Numerous researchers have investigated the integration of cover crops into crop rotation systems (Chu et al. 2017; Marcillo et al. 2017; Jensen et al. 2021). Grasses, legumes, and crucifers have been found to enhance weed suppression, boost soil fertility, and mitigate soil erosion (Couédell et al. 2019). Additionally, cover crops serve multiple purposes, such as providing green manure, acting as dead mulch by leaving crop residue in place, or serving as living mulch through intercropping with the main crop (Bunch 2023; Dzvene et al. 2023)

Tillage is often combined with other techniques to achieve integrated and sustainable crop management. MacLaren et al. (2021) recommended combining reduced tillage with crop rotation to obtain better results for weed management, while Abdollahi and Munkholm (2014) affirmed that this is true not only for weed management but also for improving soil quality. Similar results were found by Yin et al. (2016), who, after mixing tillage, mulching and intercropping, obtained an optimized soil temperature and improved soil water utilization in arid environments, which is very favourable for combating climate change. Reduced tillage is also recommended when fallow is used, as it disrupts the weed seed bed of the soil by interrupting its life cycle and thus improving the purpose of fallow period (San Martín et al. 2018). Kumar et al. (2020) observed that the higher productivity and economic profitability of the rice-fallow system improve after incorporating crop rotation with winter crops such as chickpea, lentil, and safflower combined with conservation tillage techniques. A combination of agroforestry, cover cropping, and crop rotation can help to improve soil fertility, reduce erosion and provide habitat for beneficial organisms (Fahad et al. 2022). Additionally, integrating precision agriculture technologies, such as GPS-guided machinery and remote sensing, with conservation tillage practices can optimize resource use, reduce input costs, and minimize environmental impact (Nath 2023).

By combining these and other agroecological approaches, farmers can create more resilient and sustainable farming systems that balance economic viability with

environmental stewardship, ultimately contributing to food security and rural livelihoods.

5. AGROECOLOGICAL STRATEGIES VS SYNTHETIC HERBICIDES

Agroecological strategies and synthetic herbicides represent two different approaches to managing weeds in agriculture. However, it is imperative to move towards a sustainable system that eliminates chemical inputs. Both systems are environmentally and economically different.

Regarding environmental impact, AS prioritize using ecological principles to minimize negative environmental impacts to promote biodiversity, soil health, and ecosystem resilience (Çakmakçı et al. 2023). In contrast, classical synthetic herbicides can have negative environmental effects, such as soil degradation, water pollution, and harm to non-target organisms (Abbas et al. 2018; Thiour-Mauprivez et al. 2019). Moreover, AS focus on long-term sustainability by reducing reliance on external inputs and promoting natural processes aiming to build resilient farming systems that adapt to changing conditions (Leippert et al. 2020; Hawes et al. 2021). Synthetic herbicides are often associated with input-intensive agriculture and can contribute to environmental pollution and the development of herbicide-resistant weeds (Scavo and Mauromicale 2021). AS often emphasize integrated weed management, which combines multiple tools and techniques to effectively manage weeds. This approach includes cultural, mechanical, physical and biological practices like those explained in detail in the previous sections, prioritizing the health and safety of farmers, consumers, and the environment. By reducing synthetic chemicals, AS aim to minimize potential risks associated with pesticide exposure. On the other hand, synthetic herbicides might carry health risks for applicators and can leave residues on agricultural products.

The adoption of AS can vary depending on the region, crop, and local farming traditions. Factors such as market demand, access to resources, and knowledge transfer play a role in adopting these strategies. However, farmers may encounter several challenges when transitioning to AS on their farms. These challenges include a lack of knowledge and

awareness about agroecological principles, financial constraints that hinder investments in new equipment and training, difficulties accessing markets that value agroecological products, and concerns about risk and uncertainty associated with adopting new practices. Additionally, social and cultural factors may contribute to resistance to change within agricultural communities, while the lack of supportive policies, incentives, and extension services can impede adoption. Limited access to water, land, seeds, and inputs further complicates the transition to agroecological farming, particularly in marginalized or resource-constrained regions. Addressing these challenges requires a multi-faceted approach involving education, capacity-building, financial support, market development, policy reform, and institutional coordination. By overcoming these barriers, farmers can realize the potential benefits of agroecological farming for sustainable agriculture and food security.

6. MOST COMMONLY USED AGROECOLOGICAL STRATEGIES DEPENDING ON REGION AND CROP IN EUROPE

Agroecological strategies have a strong local impact, varying depending on the region and crop, as well as several other local conditions. Different regions have varying climates and biogeographic characteristics, such as temperature, rainfall, soil type, and topography. These factors influence the selection of crops and the suitability of specific agroecological practices. For example, certain crops may thrive in warm and humid climates, while others may be better suited to cooler and drier regions. Farmers from a particular region may have specific practices that are well-adapted to the local conditions and have proven successful over time. That is why AS are often influenced by local farming traditions and knowledge that have been developed and passed down through generations. Moreover, different crops have varying growth requirements, including nutrient needs, water requirements, and pest and disease vulnerabilities. AS need to be tailored to meet the specific needs of each crop. Certain crops may benefit from companion planting or intercropping, while others may require specific soil management techniques. Regarding pest and disease pressure, the prevalence and

severity can vary across regions and crops, so AS need to be adapted to the specific challenges faced in each region. This might involve biological control methods, crop rotation, or resistant crop varieties. Finally, socioeconomic factors, such as market demand, labour availability, and access to resources, can also influence the choice of agroecological strategies. Farmers must consider the economic viability and practicality of implementing certain practices based on the local context.

In this context, we gathered data about the common AS in nine different European biogeographic regions (Mediterranean, Atlantic, Boreal, Continental, Pannonian, Anatolian, Steppic, Macaronesian, and Black Sea), depending on the type of crop (horticultural, arable or perennial), and the weeds to be managed. In the next tables (Table 1 to Table 9), we can see a relation among the most common AS, their main description, and the targeted crops and weeds collected from the different regions.

6.1. Mediterranean

Due to its proximity to the Mediterranean Sea, the Mediterranean region features hot, dry summers and mild, wet winters. This climate supports diverse agricultural systems but challenges water management and irrigation. The region is known for cultivating a variety of crops, including olives, grapes and citrus fruits, among others, which are well-suited to its unique climate. These crops are essential to the region's economy and cultural heritage. The table 1 compiles the main AS used for different crops and associated weeds, reflecting the specific needs and challenges of managing these agricultural systems in such a variable environment.

Table 1. Most commonly used agroecological strategies (AS) in Mediterranean region, targeted crop species and targeted group of weeds. C: Cultural; M: Mechanical; P: Physical; B:biological, BT: Bio-Technological.

Type of crop	Name of AS	Type of AS	Key- description of AS	Targeted crop species	Targeted group of weeds	Ref.
Arable	Tillage	M	Inter-row cultivator Flex-tine harrow Hand weeding	Spelt, chickpea, winter wheat and lentil	<i>C. album</i> L.	Baldivieso-Freitas et al. (2018)
	Crop rotation	C	Six two-crop rotations. The two	barley-barley fodder; barley-buried vetch;	<i>Anacyclus clavatus</i> and <i>L. rigidum</i>	Lacaste et al. (2017)

			crops sown every year	barley-pea; barley-sunflower		
False seedbed	C M	Use of two false seedbeds + tillage	Forage cereal, legume intercrops. <i>L. multiflorum</i> Lam.; <i>T alexandrinum</i> L.	Winter weeds, sterile oat (<i>Avena sterilis</i> L.) and wild mustard (<i>Sinapis arvensis</i> L.)	Gazoulis et al. (2022)	
Cover crops	C	Use of 6 legume winter cover crops species as green manure	Grain corn (<i>Zea mays</i> L.)	Weed community	Boulet et al. (2021)	
Crop rotation	C	Agroecological service crops (ASCs) combined with in-line tillage roller crimper.	Melon (<i>Cucumis melo</i> L.)	Weed community	Ciaccia et al. (2020)	
Combined agroecological strategies	C B	Animal breeding, crop association, crop diversification, crop rotation, aromatic plants, light/no tillage, nest-boxes for insects, organic/no fertilizers, organic/no herbicides	Tomato, pepper, onion, potato, lettuce, zucchini, eggplant, and melon.	Weed population	Palomo-Campesino (2022)	
Hortic.		Agroecological service crops combined with the use of no-till roller crimping	Comparison of agroecological service crop with no-till roller crimping (NT-RC) and green manuring (T-GM)	Green -pepper, savoy cabbage, tomato, cauliflower, butternut squash	Weed density under NT-RC was lower than under T-GM	Navarro-Miró et al. (2022)
			In-line tillage-roller crimper	<i>Brassica oleracea</i> var. <i>botrytis</i> L., <i>Brassica oleracea</i> var. <i>sabauda</i> L.	Autumn-winter weeds	Navarro et al. (2019)
	Tillage		In-line tillage-roller crimper	Tomato (<i>Solanum lycopersicum</i> L.), pepper (<i>Capsicum annuum</i> L.)	Spring-summer weeds	Navarro et al. (2019)
Living mulch	C	Growing in-season agro-ecological service crops as living mulch (LM).	Organic vegetable cropping systems.	Weed population	Ciaccia et al. (2016)	

		<i>Medicago polimorpha</i> L., var. <i>anglona</i>	<i>Brassica oleracea</i> L. var. <i>botrytis</i>		
	C	Use of legume permanent living mulches	Organic conservative vegetable systems	Weed population, more effective in dicotyledonous than in monocotyledonous weed control	Leoni et al. (2020)
Brush hoeing	M	Brush hoe once a year	Tomato	<i>P. oleracea</i> L., <i>A. retroflexus</i> L., <i>C. album</i> L., <i>Cyperus rotundus</i> L. and <i>Echinochloa</i> spp.	Mari et al. (2020)
Mulch	P	Biodegradable mulches: Black oxo., plastic mulch, recycled brown paper, black paper mulch and barley (<i>Hordeum vulgare</i> L) straw	Tomato	Annual weeds	Cirujeda et al. (2012)
	P	Biodegradable mulches: biodegradable plastic films, paper mulches	Pepper	<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> L.	Mari et al. (2020)
Cover crops	C	Use of <i>Trifolium fragiferum</i> L. as cover crop	Vinneyards	Adventitious weeds. Reduced the presence of <i>C. arvensis</i> L.	Abad et al. (2020)
Intercrops	C	Intercropping practices adopted in monocultural woody crops, with herbaceous crops covering (faba bean, purslane, cowpea, and barley/vetch mix)	Mandarin orchards	Annual weeds	Martin-Gomiz et al. (2022)
Perennial	M	Tillage was performed twice a year (in autumn and spring)	Mandarin crop, almond crop	Annual weeds	Martínez-Mena et al. (2021)
	M	Tillage twice a year	Almond crop	Annual weeds	Marin-Gomiz et al. (2021)
	M	Tillage is harrowed 2–3 times a year at 20–30 cm	Almond crop	Annual weeds	De-Leijster et al. (2020)
Weed covers	C	Maintenance of spontaneous weed cover in the alleys from autumn to spring	Olive crop	Annual weeds	Chamizo et al. (2017)

Bioherbicides	BT	Testing of different bioherbicides for weed control	Vineyard	<i>Erigeron bonariensis</i>	Cabrera-Pérez et al. (2022)
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6.2. Atlantic

Atlantic climatic conditions typically occur in regions bordering the Atlantic Ocean, characterized by mild winters, relatively cool summers, and moderate yearly precipitation. These conditions are influenced by maritime air masses, which bring moisture and regulate temperatures. Coastal areas experience milder temperatures than inland regions due to the ocean's moderating effect. Fog, mist, and high humidity are common features of Atlantic climates, fostering lush vegetation and diverse ecosystems. However, these regions may also experience occasional storms and high winds, particularly during winter. Agriculture benefits from the consistent moisture and moderate temperatures, supporting the cultivation of a wide range of crops, including grains, vegetables, fruits, and pastureland. The region is particularly well-suited for growing staple crops such as wheat, barley, and potatoes (Table 2). Additionally, the abundant pastureland is ideal for dairy farming, contributing to the region's robust agricultural output.

Table 2. Most commonly used agroecological strategies (AS) in Atlantic region, targeted crop species and targeted group of weeds. C: Cultural; M: Mechanical; P: Physical; B:biological, BT: Bio-Technological.

Type of crop	Name of AS	Type of AS	Key- description of AS	Targeted crop species	Targeted group of weeds	Ref.
	Tillage	M	In-line tillage-roller crimper	<i>Brassica oleracea</i> var. <i>capitata</i> L.	Autumn-winter weed species	Navarro et al. (2019)
Hortic.	Agroecological service crops combined with the use of no-till roller crimping	C	Comparison between two agroecological service crops (ASC) management strategies no-till roller crimping (NT-RC) and green manuring (T-GM).	Red cabbage, white cabbage	Weed density under NT-RC was lower than under T-GM	Navarro-Miró et al. (2022)
	Straw incorporation	C	Incorporation of small grain cereal straw in cereals, incorporation of straw in maize	Cereals	Weed community	Hijbeek et al. (2022)
Arable	Agroecological management	C	Green waste, compost, cover crops, crop residue incorporation, reduced soil	Cereals (spring barley, winter barley and winter	Targeted weed management	Squire et al. (2022)

disturbance and surface wash (non-inversion tillage), enhanced arable biodiversity (targeted weed management, diverse field margins, IPM strategies) wheat), and two broad leaf crops (winter oil seed rape and spring beans)

6.3. Boreal

Boreal climatic conditions are found in northern regions characterized by long, cold winters and short, cool summers, with coniferous forests dominating the landscape and permafrost in some areas. Precipitation is moderate to low, and snowfall is common during winter, creating a distinct winter landscape. Agriculture in boreal regions is limited due to the short growing season and harsh climatic conditions. However, some areas support crops like barley, oats, and potatoes (Table 3), as well as livestock grazing on pastureland during the brief summer months.

Table 3. Most commonly used agroecological strategies (AS) in Boreal region, targeted crop species and targeted group of weeds. C: Cultural; M: Mechanical; P: Physical; B:biological, BT: Bio-Technological.

Type of crop	Name of AS	Type of AS	Key- description of AS	Targeted crop species	Targeted group of weeds	Ref.
Arable	Winter cover crops	C	Green manures as winter cover crops	5 field crop rotation (with and without winter cover crops)	Annual overwintering and perennial weeds	Madsen et al. (2016)
	Winter cover crops, different nitrogen rates	C	Green manures as winter cover crops in organic systems, Herbicides in conventional systems	5 field crop rotation (with and without winter cover crops, herbicides)	Annual overwintering, summer annual and perennial weeds	Kuht et al. (2016)
Hortic.	In-line tillage-roller crimper, winter cover crops	M C	Effects of the usage of in-line tillage-roller crimper versus green manure	Depending on the project partners (data from seven field experiments)	All	Navarro-Miró et al. (2019)

6.4. Continental

Continental climates often exhibit distinct seasonal changes, with snowy winters and warm summers, and a wide temperature range between seasons. Precipitation varies, and especially in recent years is difficult to predict. Agriculture in continental climates is diverse, supporting a range of crops, including grains, fruits, vegetables, and livestock, with irrigation often necessary in drier regions to supplement rainfall. Limiting factors for agricultural suitability in the European Continental climate include water table depth, precipitation, temperature, terrain slope, soil porosity, SOC, and topsoil texture. While there's no space left for crop expansion, regions with extensive wheat and corn cultivation could potentially shift to crops like barley, sunflower, sugar beet, and potato. Weed control in this region focuses primarily on cultural methods, such as enhancing crop rotation biodiversity and proper tillage practices, with flame weeding also playing a localized role (Table 4).

Table 4. Most commonly used agroecological strategies (AS) in Continental region, targeted crop species and targeted group of weeds. C: Cultural; M: Mechanical; P: Physical; B: biological, BT: Bio-Technological.

Type of crop	Name of AS	Type of AS	Key- description of AS	Targeted crop species	Targeted group of weeds	Ref.
Arable	Spring cereals mixtures	C	At least two different cereal species mixed together in the seeding machine in equal proportions)	Barley + oats, oats + triticale, barley + triticale	Annual spring weeds	Klima et al. (2020)
	Winter cereals mixtures	C	Each mixture of two shares: 67% + 33% and 50% + 50%	Barley + rye, wheat + triticale	Annual overwintering weeds	Zajać et al. (2014)
	Cereals + legume mixtures	C	50% spring triticale + 50% peas	Spring triticale + peas	Spring annuals (<i>C. album</i>)	Gorski et al. (2022)
	Linseed + peas mixture	C	50% linseed + 50% peas	Linseed + peas	Spring annuals	Zajać et al. (2013)
	Cover crops and application of beneficial soil bacteria	C BT	Combination of <i>Azotobacter chroococcum</i> + Plant Growth Promoting Rhizobacteria and a mixture of red clover and Italian ryegrass as a cover crop	Spring barley	<i>C. album</i> , <i>Sinapis arvensis</i> , <i>Tripleurospermum inodorum</i> and <i>Elymus repens</i>	Plaza et al. (2023)
	Harrowing (Weeder harrow)	M	Plant emergence is an appropriate growth stage for single	Oats + spring triticale	Spring annuals	Sobkowicz et al. (2020)

		harrowing of oat-triticale mixture. Two cultivations on the same day should not be planned earlier than at the beginning of tillering			
Crop and cultivar mixtures	C	Oats as a supporting crop in lentil allowed crop-weed competitiveness reducing weed number and dry weight	Oats + lentil, lentil in one or two varieties	Spring annuals	Kraska et al. (2019)
Cultivar and row spacing	C	Soybean cultivar affects weed infestation, lower number of weeds in cv. Merlin and narrow rows spacing (22.5 cm)	Soybean	Spring annual, <i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	Gaweda and Kopcewicz (2023)
Cultivar	C	Cvs for organic system: Borowik, Subito, and Tomko, which showed competitiveness against weeds	Spring triticale	Spring annuals	Feledyn-Szewczyk et al. (2020)
Soil plowing	M	Lowest weed number under mouldboard plowing	Peas and narrow lupin	Spring annuals, <i>C. album</i> , <i>Viola arvensis</i> , <i>Anthemis arvensis</i> , <i>Cirsium arvense</i>	Bojarszczuk and Podlesny (2020)
Soil plowing and crop rotation	C M	In conventional tilling and crop rotation with 2-year long alfalfa, winter wheat, forage maize, winter wheat, sugar beet, and spring barley, were the lowest weeds	Forage maize	Spring annuals	Chovancová et al. (2019)
Soil aggregate+ relay intercropping	C M	Soil aggregate + stubble relay intercrop (white mustard) decrease weed infestation	Spring wheat	Spring annuals, <i>Capsella bursa-pastoris</i> , <i>Viola arvensis</i> and <i>C. album</i>	Cyplik et al. (2020)
CrossCutter Knife CrossCutter Disc	M	Ultra-shallow soil cultivation CrossCutter Knife CrossCutter Disc	Winter cereals	Voluntary oilseed rape	Kozak (2019)
Bioherbicides	BT	Water extract <i>Sorghum bicolor</i>	Maize, wheat, triticale	Spring annuals	Żurek et al. (2019)
Tillage practices and straw-management,	C M	Oilseed rape production under the autumn water stress conditions in Romania	Rapeseed	Annual and perennial	Hälmajan et al. (2012)

	seed-bed preparation					
Perennial	Inter-row weed management of low or high intensity	C M CH	Inter-row weed management	Vineyard	Annual spring weeds	Fiera et al. (2020)
	Thermal weed control, mulching	P	Flame weeding, steaming, hot water, mulching	Vineyard	Annual spring weeds	Voevod et al. (2019)

6.5. Pannonian

Pannonian climatic conditions are prevalent in the Pannonian Basin of Central Europe, characterized by hot, dry summers and cold, moderately wet winters, with relatively low precipitation overall. This climate type is influenced by its inland location, away from maritime influences, resulting in distinct seasonal variations and occasional extremes in temperature. Summers are typically hot and sunny, while winters can be cold with occasional snowfall. Agriculture in Pannonian climates is well-suited for cultivating crops such as maize, wheat, sunflower, and grapes for winemaking (Table 5), often supported by irrigation due to the limited rainfall during the growing season.

Table 5. Most commonly used agroecological strategies (AS) in Pannonian region, targeted crop species and targeted group of weeds. C: Cultural; M: Mechanical; P: Physical; B:biological, BT: Bio-Technological.

Type of crop	Name of AS	Type of AS	Key- description of AS	Targeted crop species	Targeted group of weeds	Ref.
Perennial	Intercropping	C	Trees and crops mixed in agroforestry system, 6 different soil cover (3 plants + mulch + geotextile + bee pasture mix)	Perennial monocots and dicots	Perennial monocots and dicots	Nichols et al. (2015), Zubay et al. (2021)
	Soil cover	M				
	Mulching	P				
	Biological/Bio-tech strategy	B BT	Weed repellent plant cultivation	Perennial monocots and dicots	Perennial monocots and dicots	Nichols et al. (2015) Zubay et al. (2021)
Hortic.	Biological/Bio-tech strategy	CH	Use of essential oils and natural extracts (+ physical methods if necessary)	Berries	Perennial monocots and dicots	Korres et al. (2018) Burgos et al. (2014)

Arable	Mechanical/Physical strategy	M P	Reasonable tillage	Durum wheat	Annual spring and summer weeds	Wozniak et al. (2014)
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6.6. Anatolian

Anatolian climatic conditions prevail in the Anatolian Peninsula of Turkey, characterized by a diverse range of climates influenced by its geographical location between Europe and Asia and its varied topography. Generally, Anatolian climates exhibit hot, dry summers and cold, wet winters, with significant variability depending on altitude, proximity to the coast, and regional microclimates. Summers are typically hot and arid, while winters can be cold with variable precipitation, including snowfall in higher elevations. Agriculture in Anatolian climates is diverse, supporting the cultivation of various crops such as grains, fruits, vegetables, and pulses, with irrigation often necessary in drier regions to supplement limited rainfall and support crop growth throughout the year (Table 6).

Table 6. Most commonly used agroecological strategies (AS) in Anatolian region, targeted crop species and targeted group of weeds. C: Cultural; M: Mechanical; P: Physical; B:biological, BT: Bio-Technological.

Type of crop	Name of AS	Type of AS	Key- description of AS	Targeted crop species	Targeted group of weeds	Ref.
Hortic.	Weed flaming	P BT	1) Weed flaming (75, 90 propane gas/ha), 2) Vermicompost, 3) Flame (75, 90 kg/ha)+ Vermicompost	Apricot	<i>Sorghum halepense</i> , <i>Tribulus terrestris</i> , <i>Amaranthus</i> spp., <i>Chenopodium album</i>	Arslan and Tursun (2021)
	Intercropping	C BT	Intercropping + Vermicompost	Pistachio	<i>Sorghum halepense</i> , <i>A. retroflexus</i> , <i>Avena</i> spp., <i>C. arvensis</i>	Göksu and Kolören (2018)
	Cover crops	C BT	Intercropping. 1) Cover crops (alfalfa or ryegrass). Vermicompost. 2) Alfalfa +Vermicompost. Ryegrass + vermicompost.	Hazelnut	<i>Setaria</i> spp., <i>Ranunculus</i> spp., <i>Pteridium aquilinum</i> , <i>Euphorbia</i> spp.	Jepson et al. (2019)

Arable	Weed flaming	P BT	Weed flaming (75, 90 propane gas/ha). Vermicompost. Flame (75, 90 kg/ha)+ Vermicompost.	Cotton	<i>Sorghum halepense</i> , <i>X. strumarium</i> , <i>S. nigrum</i> , <i>Physalis philadelphica</i>	Arslan and Tursun (2021)
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6.7. Steppic

The steppe climate, typified by dry, continental conditions, manifests across extensive regions of the Eurasian and North American continents. This climate zone is distinguished by its hot summers and cold winters, indicative of the pronounced seasonal temperature variations characteristic of these areas. These regions typically receive low to moderate precipitation, often concentrated in the summer months, with variable amounts of snowfall in winter. Steppe climates are known for their vast grasslands and sparse vegetation, with occasional shrubs and trees scattered throughout the landscape. Agriculture in steppe climates is challenging due to limited precipitation and extreme temperature fluctuations. However, certain crops such as wheat, barley, and sunflowers (Table 7) can be cultivated with irrigation in more favourable locations. Grazing livestock on natural grasslands is also common in steppe regions.

Table 7. Most commonly used agroecological strategies (AS) in Steppic region, targeted crop species and targeted group of weeds. C: Cultural; M: Mechanical; P: Physical; B:biological, BT: Bio-Technological.

Type of crop	Name of AS	Type of AS	Key- description of AS	Targeted crop species	Targeted group of weeds	Ref.
	The effect of tillage systems on weediness	C	(A) Seeding rates. (B) Sowing depth. (C) Options for basic tillage: Deep loosening, plowing, discing.	Corn, winter cereals, and sunflower	Perennial	Kryvenko et al. (2019)
	Crop rotation for growing field crops	C	3, 4 and 5 fields crop rotation	Corn, winter cereals and sunflower	Perennial	Shuvar et al. (2019)
Arable	Agroecological weed control	BT C M	Seeds were treated with formulated product, BioZeaFert. Cover crop species were used, chose with farmer option to be a mix of wheat and flax in order to use the advantages of cover crops with fibrous roots. Mechanical weeding was applied.	Maize	Annual and perennial weeds	Petcu et al. (2023)

Manual weeding /hoeing	M	The cultivation by hoed methods is considered the environmentally weeds control, improves the aerohydric system and the eco-environment feed soybean	Soybean	Annual and perennial weeds	Ionescu and Ionescu (2012)
Water retention / mulching	C	Agro-ecological differentials in soybean crop evapotranspiration and implications for adaptation to Climate Change	Soybean	Annual spring weeds	Molua (2010)
Crop rotation and fertilization level	C	The role of crop rotation and nitrogen fertilization level upon the economic indicators at wheat and corn crops in condition of a Long Term Experience	Winter wheat	Annual spring weeds	Gidea et al. (2015)

6.8. Macaronesian

Macaronesian climatic conditions are found in the Macaronesia region, which includes the Azores, Madeira, the Canary Islands, and Cape Verde (Table 8). These islands are characterized by a subtropical climate influenced by the surrounding ocean, resulting in mild temperatures, relatively low-temperature variation between seasons, and high humidity levels. Macaronesian climates are known for their pleasant, temperate conditions, with warm summers and mild winters. Precipitation varies across the islands, with some areas experiencing relatively high rainfall while others are more arid. Agriculture in Macaronesia is diverse, with crops such as bananas, grapes, citrus fruits, and tropical flowers thriving in favourable growing conditions. Additionally, the islands' unique ecosystems support a rich biodiversity of endemic plant species.

Table 8. Most commonly used agroecological strategies (AS) in Macaronesian region, targeted crop species and targeted group of weeds. C: Cultural; M: Mechanical; P: Physical; B:biological, BT: Bio-Technological.

Type of crop	Name of AS	Type of AS	Key- description of AS	Targeted crop species	Targeted group of weeds	Ref.
-	Biological control	Agricultural	Using insects present in the area for weed control	-	Groups of weeds	Domínguez and Siverio (2019)

6.9. Black-Sea

Black Sea climatic conditions are prevalent in the regions surrounding the Black Sea, characterized by a humid subtropical climate with distinct seasons influenced by maritime influences and proximity to mountain ranges. Summers are typically warm and humid, while winters are mild and relatively wet, with snowfall common in higher elevations. The Black Sea region experiences moderate to high precipitation throughout the year, with a peak in rainfall during the spring and autumn months. This climate type fosters lush vegetation and supports various crops, including grains, fruits, vegetables, and tea. Agriculture in the Black Sea region benefits from the fertile soils and abundant rainfall, making it one of the most productive agricultural areas in the world (Table 9).

Table 9. Most commonly used agroecological strategies (AS) in Black Sea region, targeted crop species and targeted group of weeds. C: Cultural; M: Mechanical; P: Physical; B:biological, BT: Bio-Technological.

Type of crop	Name of AS	Type of AS	Key- description of AS	Targeted crop species	Targeted group of weeds	Ref.
Hortic.	Cover crops	C BT	Intercropping. 1) Cover crops (alfalfa or ryegrass). Vermicompost. 2) Alfalfa +Vermicompost. Ryegrass + vermicompost. Sing insects present in the area for weed control	Hazelnut	<i>Setaria</i> spp., <i>Ranunculus</i> spp., <i>Pteridium aquilinum</i> , <i>Euphorbia</i> spp.	Jepson et al. (2019)

7. CONCLUSIONS / FUTURE STEPS

The comprehensive review of agroecological strategies (AS) for sustainable weed management in key European crops underscores the myriad of effective alternatives to conventional chemical-based approaches available to farmers. These strategies, encompassing cultural, mechanical, and biological methods and the integration of cutting-edge digital technologies, not only offer viable weed control solutions but also champion sustainability, biodiversity, and ecosystem health principles. Adopting agroecological practices allows farmers to significantly reduce their reliance on synthetic inputs, thereby minimizing environmental impacts and bolstering the resilience of agricultural systems against the challenges of climate change and pest pressures.

The review highlights the importance of a holistic approach to weed management by emphasizing the critical need for tailoring these strategies to align with local conditions, crop types, and regional challenges. It is essential to continue fostering research, education, and knowledge exchange to refine further and expand the application of agroecological practices. Collaboration emerges as a key theme, urging farmers, researchers, policymakers, and agricultural stakeholders to join forces in overcoming barriers and scaling up the adoption of agroecological approaches. Developing and implementing supportive policies and incentives are vital in encouraging farmers to transition towards agroecology. Such measures could include financial support, technical assistance, and access to markets that value and reward sustainably produced agricultural products.

Efforts to raise awareness and build capacity among farmers are paramount, emphasizing providing training, extension services, and establishing demonstration plots to showcase the tangible benefits of agroecological approaches in real-world farming contexts.

In conclusion, the shift towards agroecological farming systems heralds a promising future for more sustainable and resilient agriculture in Europe and beyond. By embracing agroecology, farmers stand at the forefront of achieving significant environmental benefits, economic viability, and social well-being for current and future generations. This review not only consolidates existing knowledge but also opens avenues for innovative research and practical application, marking a significant step towards realizing agroecological strategies' full potential in addressing modern agriculture's multifaceted challenges.

In sum, embracing agroecological strategies is not just a choice but a necessity for the future of agriculture. It is a commitment to sustainability, resilience, and the health of our planet. The take-home message is clear: by integrating cultural, mechanical, biological methods, and digital innovations, farmers can transition towards more sustainable practices that yield profound benefits for the environment, economy, and society. The journey towards agroecological farming is a collective endeavour that

requires all stakeholders' support, innovation, and collaboration. As we move forward, let us champion these practices as a means to manage weeds and as a foundational pillar for a sustainable agricultural legacy. Together, we can cultivate a future where agriculture thrives in harmony with nature, ensuring food security and well-being for future generations.

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